

Evaluating the Impact of Non-Profit Organizations on the Implementation of the European Green Deal

EDITH CRISTINA EUAN DIAZ

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Thesis investigates the role of Non-Profit Organizations (NPOs) in implementing the European Green Deal (EGD), focusing on their involvement, funding, and impact on project outcomes.

Effective environmental solutions require partnerships among NPOs, governments, and the private sector. The EGD exemplifies such collaborative efforts, aiming to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050. These collaborations leverage the strengths of each sector: regulatory oversight from governments, innovation from the private sector, and community engagement from NPOs, etc. NPOs provide expert knowledge, raise public awareness, and engage communities. They influence policy through research and advocacy, ensuring policies are scientifically grounded. NPOs are also indispensable in bridging the gap between scientific knowledge and public action.

Power imbalances can marginalize NPOs, especially when private sector interests dominate. Despite these challenges, NPOs remain essential for effective environmental action. Ensuring equitable power dynamics and robust frameworks is critical to maintaining a focus on sustainable and inclusive development.

The analysis of 73 EGD projects reveals a total of €960.61 million in EU funding, with additional contributions bringing total project costs to €1.24 billion. Private Sector Entities and Educational Institutions receive most of the funding, while NPOs receive a smaller share, averaging €489,106.95 per partner compared to the overall average of €489,106.95. This funding disparity may limit their capacity to contribute fully to the EGD's goals.

The study combines data analysis of EGD projects and a survey of NPOs involved in these projects. The analysis included the information of 237 NPOs (out of the total of 1,574 unique partners taking part in the EGD). The survey gathered insights on NPO roles, contributions, and challenges, providing a comprehensive understanding of their impact on EGD initiatives.

NPOs are involved in various capacities, significantly contributing to project management, advocacy, and technical solutions. On average, each EGD project involves four NPOs, with some projects engaging significantly more, such as SchoolFood4Change with 21 NPOs and ZeroW with 15. However, funding distribution shows significant variability, with many NPOs receiving less than the average amount. Geographically, NPO participation is concentrated in Western and Southern Europe, indicating better infrastructure and funding opportunities in these regions.

Summary of the Overarching Policy Recommendations:

1. **Equitable Funding and Incentive Structures:** Balance funding between large and small NPOs, secure long-term funding, and foster innovation through competitive mechanisms.
2. **Enhanced Collaboration and Networking:** Promote strategic partnerships and facilitate knowledge exchange among NPOs, EU bodies, and local governments.
3. **Capacity Building and Technical Support:** Provide technical assistance and training to smaller NPOs, and support technological innovations.
4. **Inclusive and Diverse Participation:** Incentivize diverse NPO engagement and increase public and stakeholder participation with educational initiatives.
5. **Regulatory Frameworks and Monitoring:** Develop regulatory frameworks, simplify administrative processes, and ensure systematic monitoring and evaluation for sustainability.

NPOs play a critical role in the success of the EGD by translating policy into action and engaging communities. Addressing strategic and financial constraints is essential to maximize their contributions. By understanding and supporting the integral role of NPOs, policymakers and funders could ensure the effective implementation of the EGD and similar initiatives.

INTRODUCTION

The [European Green Deal](#) [1] aims to make the European Union (EU) the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. This transformative initiative targets key areas like clean energy, zero pollution, sustainable industry, and biodiversity preservation, aiming for zero net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, economic growth decoupled from resource use, and ensuring no person and no place is left behind. It also serves as a recovery strategy from the COVID-19 pandemic, with one-third of the €1.8 trillion investments from the [NextGenerationEU Recovery Plan](#) [2] and the EU's seven-year budget dedicated to financing the EGD. The European Commission (EC) has proposed policies to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels.

There are 73 projects funded under the EGD Call [3] (see Appendix 1, detailed information is also displayed on the [list of project descriptions](#) [3] and comprehensive details can be found on [CORDIS](#) [4]), with over €1 billion in investment, and are critical to implementing the EGD. These projects span diverse areas, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable agriculture, circular economy, and biodiversity preservation. They focus on developing innovative solutions to reduce

greenhouse gas emissions, enhance energy efficiency, promote sustainable practices, and restore ecosystems. By fostering collaboration and sharing best practices, these projects aim to accelerate the EU's transition to a sustainable and climate-neutral economy, ensuring that economic growth is decoupled from resource use and that no person or place is left behind.

IMPORTANCE OF NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS (NPOS) IN EGD

NPOs are essential actors in the global effort to address climate change and environmental sustainability. They often interact with the EC and other governmental bodies by participating in consultations, implementing projects, and advocating for policy changes [5]. The EGD's official page also [highlights the crucial role of various stakeholders, including NPOs, in addressing climate change](#) [1]. Locally, NPOs engage with communities to raise awareness, mobilize grassroots actions, and deliver services directly, as seen in the work of [global environmental organizations listed by Donorbox](#) [6]. Internationally, they collaborate with other organizations to share knowledge, resources, and strategies, which is evident in the [SHARED GREEN DEAL project](#) [7], where NPOs drive local action and influence sustainability policy. NPOs like [Slow Food](#) exemplify how grassroots actions can translate into effective policy work, [advocating for sustainable food and farming systems](#) [8]. Due to their ability to operate at both the grassroots and policy levels, NPOs can act as catalysts for change, driving the implementation of comprehensive and inclusive strategies like the EGD.

The success of the EGD hinges on the active participation and collaboration of multiple sectors, ensuring equity and plurality in its implementation. Involvement from diverse societal groups, including industry, academia, local governments, and civil society organizations, fosters a comprehensive approach to tackling climate challenges. This inclusive strategy ensures that the transition to a sustainable economy is fair and just, benefiting all citizens and leaving no one behind. However, NPOs often face significant challenges, including limited funding, bureaucratic hurdles, and the need for sustainable capacity-building programs. Reports from the [Urban Institute](#) [9] and the [National Council of Nonprofits](#) [10] highlight that restricted funding and barriers to capacity building are persistent issues for NPOs, hindering their effective operation. Additionally, articles from [Unit4](#) [11] and [Nonprofit Megaphone](#) [12] emphasize the difficulty in securing consistent funding and the constraints imposed by short-duration grants. Addressing these challenges through supportive policies and streamlined funding mechanisms is essential to maximize the impact of NPOs and ensure the successful realization of the EGD's objectives.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE

NPOs have historically shaped environmental policy and advocacy in Europe since the environmental movements of the 1960s and 1970s, establishing a foundation for contemporary environmental governance structures [13]. Civil society organizations (CSOs) are crucial in advocating sustainable practices, influencing policy development, and managing projects aimed at reducing carbon emissions and enhancing biodiversity [6]. Their involvement has ensured comprehensive and inclusive policies that address the needs of marginalized communities and ensure equitable outcomes [14]. Recently, outside Europe, NPOs have played a vital role in public-private partnerships (PPPs), as evidenced by Ugwu et al., who demonstrate the effectiveness of PPPs in mobilizing resources for clean energy infrastructure [15]. Adanma et al. further emphasize the need for adaptive governance structures that include multilateral agreements and civil society participation [16]. In Korea, the evolution of stakeholder networks towards more inclusive and localized governance models in forest conservation, illustrates the potential of CSOs in enhancing environmental governance [17]. Beyond advocacy and project management, NPOs also conduct research, raise public awareness, and facilitate knowledge exchange, reinforcing their status as trusted actors capable of mobilizing public support and influencing policy decisions [18]. CSOs are therefore pivotal in implementing effective and inclusive environmental governance frameworks.

THEORIES ON COLLECTIVE ACTION AND ENVIRONMENTAL ADVOCACY

Theories of collective action and environmental advocacy provide critical insights into how diverse actors collaborate to address environmental challenges. Mancur Olson's theory of collective action highlights the free-rider problem, where individuals are less likely to contribute to a common goal without selective incentives, a concept particularly relevant in environmental advocacy where the benefits of a clean environment are shared by all [19]. Elinor Ostrom expanded this by demonstrating that communities can manage common resources effectively through self-organization and collective governance, challenging the idea that only top-down regulations or privatization can

prevent the "tragedy of the commons" [20]. These foundations underscore the importance of CSOs and NGOs, which mobilize resources and coordinate activities to facilitate cooperation. The EGD exemplifies these theories by fostering collaboration among stakeholders, to achieve its ambitious sustainability targets [4]. Meka and Venkateswarlu (2024) recently highlighted the critical role of collective action in attaining Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), advocating for enhanced international cooperation and innovative financing mechanisms [21]. Collective action theories embed into environmental advocacy, policymakers and practitioners could then develop more inclusive, resilient, and effective governance structures that align with the interconnected nature of global environmental challenges.

STAKEHOLDER THEORY IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROJECTS

In the context of environmental projects, Stakeholder theory [22] underscores the necessity to account for the diverse interests and influences of various stakeholders, including governments, NGOs, local communities, investors, and future generations. The application of stakeholder theory in environmental projects is particularly pertinent given the complexity and long-term nature of environmental impacts [23]. Competing arguments in stakeholder theory often revolve around the prioritization of interests and the distribution of benefits and burdens. Some argue that prioritizing environmental sustainability may come at the expense of short-term economic gains [24], while others contend that long-term economic stability and prosperity are inextricably linked to sustainable environmental practices [25]. Effective stakeholder engagement ensures that diverse perspectives are integrated, leading to more resilient and widely supported outcomes [26]. These debates are critical in shaping policies and investments, and understanding the dynamics and competing interests of stakeholders is essential for the successful implementation of large ambitious initiatives.

COLLABORATION MODELS: NPOS, GOVERNMENTS, AND THE PRIVATE SECTOR

Collaboration between NPOs, governments, and the private sector is essential for addressing complex environmental challenges and achieving sustainable development goals. These collaborations can take various forms, including Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), multi-stakeholder alliances, and hybrid organizations that blend elements of all three sectors. Effective collaboration models are characterized by clear governance structures, shared objectives, and mechanisms for accountability and transparency. For instance, the European Climate Pact brings together NPOs, businesses, and governmental entities to promote climate actions and exchange best practices [27]. Similarly, globally, the [Global Reporting Initiative](#) (GRI) exemplifies how international collaborations between these sectors can enhance sustainability reporting and drive corporate responsibility [28]. Proponents argue that such collaborations leverage the strengths of each sector: the regulatory power and oversight of governments, the innovation and efficiency of the private sector, and the advocacy and community engagement capabilities of NPOs [29]. These synergies can lead to more effective and comprehensive environmental solutions. However, critics caution that power imbalances can lead to the marginalization of NPOs, particularly when private sector interests dominate the agenda, potentially prioritizing profit over public good [30]. Examples from the rest of the world, such as the United Nations (UN)'s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) partnerships, demonstrate both the potential and the challenges of such collaborations. These global partnerships highlight the importance of equitable power dynamics and the need for robust frameworks to ensure that all voices are heard and that the primary focus remains on sustainable and inclusive development [31].

NPOs are integral to the environmental policy landscape, offering expert knowledge, raising public awareness, and fostering engagement. These organizations harness scientific expertise and research to inform policymaking and implementation, often serving as trusted advisors to governments and international bodies. For instance, the [World Wildlife Fund](#) (WWF) provides comprehensive data and analysis on biodiversity and conservation, influencing global policy decisions [32]. Similarly, European NPOs like the [European Environmental Bureau](#) (EEB) play a crucial role in shaping EU environmental policies through rigorous research and advocacy [33]. By leveraging their specialized knowledge, NPOs ensure that environmental policies are grounded in the latest scientific findings and best practices, enhancing their effectiveness and credibility. In addition to their expert advisory role, NPOs are pivotal in raising public awareness and engagement on environmental issues. Through targeted campaigns, educational programs, and community initiatives, these organizations educate the public and mobilize collective action. [Greenpeace](#)'s global campaigns on climate change and pollution, for example, have significantly heightened awareness and prompted policy changes [34]. In Europe, the [Climate Action Network](#) (CAN) has effectively engaged citizens in climate advocacy, contributing to the ambitious goals of the EGD [35]. However, competing arguments highlight challenges such as limited resources and potential biases. Critics argue that some NPOs may prioritize visibility over substantive impact, leading to superficial engagement [36]. Despite these challenges, the role of

NPOs remains indispensable in bridging the gap between scientific knowledge and public action, ensuring that environmental initiatives are both informed and inclusive on a global scale [37].

FRAMEWORKS FOR PPPS IN ENVIRONMENTAL INITIATIVES

PPPs have emerged as a critical mechanism for addressing complex environmental challenges by leveraging the strengths of both the public and private sectors. These partnerships involve collaborative agreements where public entities and private companies share resources, risks, and rewards in pursuing common environmental objectives. The frameworks guiding PPPs in environmental initiatives often emphasize the alignment of incentives, transparent governance, and equitable distribution of benefits and responsibilities. These frameworks are designed to foster innovation, efficiency, and scalability in projects such as renewable energy development, sustainable infrastructure, and conservation efforts [38]. Competing arguments regarding PPPs often center on issues of accountability, effectiveness, and equity. Proponents argue that PPPs can mobilize private capital, expertise, and innovation, leading to more efficient and effective environmental solutions [39]. However, critics contend that these partnerships can sometimes prioritize private profit over public good, leading to imbalances in the distribution of benefits and a lack of accountability to the public [30]. Effective frameworks for PPPs in environmental initiatives (such as the EGD) must therefore incorporate robust mechanisms for stakeholder engagement, transparent reporting, and rigorous evaluation to ensure that both public and private interests are adequately addressed and that the overarching environmental objectives are met.

EFFECTIVENESS OF NPOS IN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

NPOs play a crucial role in the implementation of environmental policies by acting as intermediaries between the public, private sectors, and governmental bodies. These organizations leverage their expertise, resources, and networks to influence policy and practice. NPOs contribute to environmental policy implementation through advocacy, public education, and on-the-ground projects that demonstrate sustainable practices, mobilizing communities and influencing public opinion to shape policy agendas and ensure the enforcement of environmental regulations [40]. Competing arguments about the effectiveness of NPOs often revolve around issues of scale, funding, and accountability. Proponents argue that NPOs bring essential grassroots perspectives and innovative solutions that complement governmental efforts, particularly in areas where state capacity is limited [41]. They emphasize that NPOs can operate with greater flexibility and responsiveness compared to bureaucratic government structures [36]. NPOs may also face challenges in scaling their initiatives and ensuring long-term impact without consistent funding and institutional support. Additionally, concerns about the accountability and transparency of NPOs arise, particularly when they rely heavily on private donations or international funding sources [42]. NPOs are seen as vital partners in achieving ambitious environmental targets set by the EGD, but their effectiveness will depend on their ability to collaborate effectively with other stakeholders and secure sustainable funding.

FUNDING PATTERNS AND THEIR IMPACT ON NPOS' EFFECTIVENESS

Funding patterns play a critical role in determining the effectiveness of NPOs in environmental policy implementation and advocacy. NPOs typically rely on a mix of funding sources, including government grants, private donations, foundation support, and international aid. These funding streams can significantly influence the capacity of NPOs to carry out their missions, shape their strategic priorities, and affect their operational sustainability. In Europe, organizations like the [European Climate Foundation](#) receive substantial funding from philanthropic sources, enabling them to conduct extensive research and advocacy on climate policy [43]. Similarly, globally, entities such as the [Global Environment Facility](#) (GEF) provide critical financial support to NPOs working on international environmental projects [44]. These funding patterns allow NPOs to maintain independence and flexibility, crucial for innovative and responsive environmental actions. Competing arguments about the impact of funding on NPOs' effectiveness often focus on issues of dependency, accountability, and strategic alignment. Proponents assert that diverse and sustainable funding sources enhance the resilience and adaptability of NPOs, allowing them to scale their impact and maintain long-term initiatives (Young, 2000). Conversely, dependency on external funding, particularly from government or corporate sources, can compromise the autonomy of NPOs, potentially leading to mission drift where organizational priorities are skewed to align with donor interests rather than grassroots needs [37]. For example, in regions where NPOs heavily rely on international aid, such as parts of Africa and Asia, there can be tensions between local environmental priorities and the agendas set by foreign donors [45]. Securing diverse funding is essential for NPOs to effectively carry their activities while maintaining their integrity.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The involvement and impact of NPOs in the implementation of the EGD projects are critical areas that require deeper understanding, particularly regarding funding allocation, project execution, and the achievement of overarching objectives. These organizations often serve as keystones of innovation and community engagement, bridging the gap between policy ambitions and on-the-ground action. Their roles range from advocating for sustainable practices and influencing policy development to directly managing projects that aim to reduce carbon emissions, enhance biodiversity, and promote sustainable growth. By examining how these entities are funded, the strategies they employ in project execution, and their effectiveness in contributing to the EGD's goals, stakeholders can identify best practices, potential bottlenecks, and opportunities for scaling successful initiatives. This insight is crucial not only for maximizing the impact of current investments but also for informing future policy and funding decisions, ensuring that the ambitious targets of the EGD are met through collaborative, innovative, and impactful actions.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What role do Non-Profit Organizations play in the implementation of the European Green Deal, and how does their involvement and funding contribute to the deal's objectives?

HYPOTHESIS

The effectiveness of the European Green Deal in achieving its climate neutrality and sustainability targets by 2050 is disproportionately influenced due to the lack of strategic engagement and funding of Non-Profit Organizations (e.g., Associations and NGOs), whose contributions could amplify project impacts, foster innovation, and facilitate broader societal acceptance and participation.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology, further detailed below and in Appendix 2, consisted of two complementary phases: analytical study and a survey. In the analytics phase, we collected comprehensive data on the 73 EGD projects from project descriptions and the CORDIS database [4], including project details and participant information. We created a detailed database and classified into five overarching academic and economic categories, facilitating a structured analysis. Additionally, we categorized the project partners, identifying 1964 entries in the CORDIS database, which corresponded to 1574 unique partners since it was found that 390 partners participated in two or more projects. These partners were further classified into five overarching organizational categories: Governmental Bodies, Private Sector Entities, Educational and Research Institutions, NPOs, and International Organizations. In the survey phase, launched on April 18, 2024, targeted NPOs involved in these projects using a 20-question survey distributed via email and social media. The survey's final version, was designed to assess the impact of NPOs contributions, understand collaboration dynamics, identify challenges and solutions, evaluate sustainability measures, and collect recommendations.

ANALYTICS

PROJECT CLASSIFICATION

We collected comprehensive information on projects funded under the EGD from the project descriptions available in ref. [3] and additional details on CORDIS [4]. After identifying the project websites, these were also included in our dataset. The full details of this classification are contained in Appendix 2, section: Project classification.

We created a comprehensive database and then classified the projects into 20 academic categories. These were then consolidated into five overarching academic categories: 1) Environmental and Earth, 2) Engineering and Technology, 3) Social Sciences and Governance, 4) Health and Medical Sciences: Includes Medical and Health Sciences, and Biotechnology, and 5) Agricultural and Food Sciences. The projects were also classified into 20 economic categories and further consolidated into five overarching economic categories: 1) Environmental Sustainability, 2) Energy and Resource Management, 3) Societal Development and Governance, 4) Technology and Innovation, and 5) Infrastructure and Urban Development.

PARTNER CLASSIFICATION

The details of this classification are contained in Appendix 2, section: Partner classification. We include here a summary of the methodology.

OVERARCHING CATEGORY - ACTIVITY TYPE

For further classification, we considered the main activities of the organizations and identified 59 distinct activity types (refer to refer to Appendix 2, Section: Organization and Activity Type

Classification), with a detailed focus on NPOs. These activity types were categorized under several groups: Education and Research (including universities, research institutions, and public research organizations), Governmental Bodies (including government agencies, ministries, and public utilities), International Organizations (such as intergovernmental networks and international organizations), Non-Profit Organizations (including hospitals, charities, think tanks, and cooperatives), and Private Sector Entities (including private companies, corporations, and consulting firms).

These activity types were then matched with overarching organizational categories like those used by CORDIS [4]. Governmental Bodies encompass entities responsible for implementing laws and policies at various levels, such as government agencies and ministries. Private Sector Entities include for-profit organizations of varying sizes and industries, such as private companies and corporations. Educational and Research Institutions are focused on providing education and conducting research, including universities and research institutes. NPOs were more granular for the purpose of our study since they operate for social, educational, charitable, or environmental purposes, including NGOs and social enterprises. International Organizations operate across multiple countries, focusing on global issues such as trade, health, and development, including entities like the UN.

ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES CLASSIFICATION

We classified the partners in the projects based on their economic activities, inferred from their websites and other information sources. Initially, we identified 531 distinct entries for sector descriptions, which were then categorized into 30 sectors (refer to Appendix 2, Section: Economic activities classification). These 30 initial categories were further consolidated into 15 major categories for a more structured analysis. The major categories include Aerospace, Defense, and Aviation; Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources; Biotechnology and Life Sciences; Business, Finance, and Consulting; Construction, Engineering, and Architecture; Education and Research; Energy and Environmental Solutions; Health and Medical Services; Industry and Manufacturing; Information, Communication, and Technology; Public Services and Government; Safety, Emergency, and Security; Science, Technology, and Innovation; Transportation and Urban Development; and Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies.

CHALLENGES IN CLASSIFYING EGD PROJECTS AND PARTICIPANTS

As discussed in Appendix 2, the classification system for EGD projects and their participants is comprehensive and systematic, but it faces several limitations due to its reliance on manual processes and a minor role of Natural language Processing (NLP) tools. We processed 1964 different entries for participants across 73 EGD projects, resulting in a vast amount of data. Manual classification involves subjectivity, as different experts may interpret project descriptions differently, leading to potential inconsistencies. Human error in data entry and categorization is also a risk, even with multiple checks. Language and translation issues complicate categorization, as regional terminologies may not translate accurately. Additionally, the diversity of legal statuses for organizations across different countries can introduce further complexity, as some special legal entity statuses may be unfamiliar. Project descriptions can be ambiguous, and many projects are interdisciplinary; a simple classification approach was used to address this. Organizations often engage in multiple activities, making it challenging to classify them under a single category. Despite these challenges, the author did her best to ensure a robust and detailed classification, acknowledging that the versatile activities of some corporations and the inherent limitations of manual and targeted NLP processes can affect the consistency and accuracy of the database.

SURVEY

A second phase of the study involved a survey targeting NPOs participating in the EGD projects.

FINAL VERSION OF THE SURVEY

An initial version of the survey presented in the thesis concept contained 10 questions, which evolved later into a final version of the survey containing 20 questions in total. The transcript of the Final Version is included in Appendix 3.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FINAL VERSION OF THE SURVEY

The final version of the survey (see Appendix 3) aims to gather comprehensive insights into the experiences, challenges, and perceptions of NPOs involved in EGD projects. It seeks to assess the impact of these organizations by asking them to rate their contributions and describe specific achievements, thereby gauging their effectiveness and identifying influential contributions. Additionally, the survey examines collaboration dynamics with other stakeholders, explores the challenges faced by NPOs and their strategies for overcoming obstacles, and evaluates the sustainability and long-term impact of the projects. By collecting recommendations for policymakers

and funders, the survey aims to provide insights to enhance future EGD projects and guide the development of more effective policies, funding structures, and support systems.

The survey data will serve multiple analyses, including evaluating the effectiveness of NPOs in contributing to EGD projects, identifying best practices, and recognizing common challenges and barriers. It will also analyze the nature and benefits of collaborations between different stakeholders to improve future partnerships and gather insights into sustainability measures to ensure long-term maintenance of project outcomes. Finally, the data could inform policymakers and funders about the practical needs and recommendations from NPOs, helping to refine and enhance the design, implementation, and funding of similar initiatives.

OUTREACH

Initial Contact through Project Websites: We began by visiting the official websites of projects involving NPOs to gather general contact information.

Direct Outreach to Non-profit Organizations

The questionnaire was launched on April 18, 2024, and sent to the public contact emails of the projects and the contact emails of the NPOs found online on the project description website [here](#) and individual organization websites. A follow-up campaign was conducted on April 25, 2024, by contacting organizations via the CORDIS project website. This involved using the "Contact the organisation" feature.

A second reminder was sent via email and CORDIS on May 6, 2024, with a final reminder sent to non-responding projects on May 13, 2024. The questionnaire was closed on May 15, 2024.

Social Media Outreach

Social media outreach was performed on LinkedIn on April 18, 2024, with a post [here](#). A second post was made on May 5, 2024, tagging the LinkedIn pages of the projects [here](#). Direct messages were also sent through this platform, inviting projects to participate in the survey.

ANALYTICAL STUDY: NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS

INSIGHTS GAINED FROM THE GENERAL ANALYSIS OF THE EGD

A comprehensive analysis of the EGD projects has been conducted and is detailed extensively in Appendix 4. This section provides a summary and highlights the most significant facts and figures from that analysis.

The study reveals the intricacies and variations in funding and total project costs for EGD projects. With 73 projects receiving a combined total of €960.61 million in EU funding, the average funding per project is approximately €13.16 million, while the total costs amount to €1.24 billion. This difference is attributed to the significant financial contributions made by project partners beyond the EU funding. The distribution of funding shows a median of €11.02 million, indicating that most projects receive less than the average amount, with a positive skewness of 1.50 suggesting a concentration of lower funding amounts.

The analysis, depicted in Table 6 and Table 7, shows considerable variability in both funding and project costs. The range of EU funding spans from €50,000 to €52.99 million, while total project costs vary from €71,429 to €148.96 million. The high standard deviations of €9.80 million for funding and €20.47 million for costs, along with the skewness values, underscore the diverse financial landscapes of these projects. This variability is further supported by the confidence levels indicating the reliability of the mean estimates for both EU contributions and total project costs.

Examining the distribution of funding across academic categories, Engineering and Technology emerge as the primary beneficiaries, receiving 42% of the total EU contributions. This is followed by Environmental and Earth Sciences with 24%, and Social Sciences and Governance with 19%. Health and Medical Sciences, along with Agricultural and Food Sciences, receive 8% and 7% of the funding, respectively. The detailed breakdown of these categories reveals the emphasis on technological innovation and environmental sustainability.

From an economic perspective, the funding allocation reflects a strong focus on Energy and Resource Management, which accounts for 46% of the total EU funding. Environmental Sustainability follows with 32%, while Infrastructure and Urban Development, Societal Development and Governance, and Technology and Innovation receive 12%, 7%, and 3%, respectively. This distribution underscores the strategic priorities of the EGD, aimed at enhancing energy efficiency, sustainable resource management, and urban development.

The analysis of the distribution of organizations participating in EGD projects reveals a diverse composition. Out of 1,574 organizations, Private Sector Entities make up the largest group with 684 organizations (43%), followed by Educational and Research Institutions with 498 organizations (32%).

NPOs account for 237 organizations (15%), Governmental Bodies comprise 148 organizations (9%), and International Organizations are the smallest group with 8 organizations (0.4%). This highlights the significant involvement of the private sector and educational institutions, with NPOs also playing a crucial role in the initiatives.

The distribution of EU funding among unique partners shows significant disparities, with an average funding of €489,106.95 per partner. However, the high standard deviation and skewness values indicate a concentration of funding among a few organizations, while many receive considerably less. This skewed distribution calls for a more equitable allocation of resources to ensure broader participation and impact. The cascading funding analysis further emphasizes this need, as significant variability exists in the amounts allocated to third parties. NPOs, receiving €106.41 million, play a vital role in addressing social and environmental goals. Despite their smaller share compared to private sector entities and educational institutions, their contribution is significant in achieving the EGD's objectives.

Table 6 details the net EU funding distribution: Educational and Research Institutions receive €390.60 million, Governmental Bodies €54.39 million, International Organizations €2.25 million, NPOs Organizations €106.41 million, and Private Sector Entities €406,99 million. The total funding amounts to €960.61 million, underscoring the crucial roles of private sector entities and educational institutions in the EGD projects.

The relatively smaller funding for governmental and international organizations, at €54.39 million and €2.25 million respectively, indicates their specialized but critical roles. Governmental bodies ensure policy alignment and regulatory support, while international organizations contribute to global cooperation on environmental issues.

This analysis presented in Appendix 3 lays the groundwork for further exploration of NPOs' impact. The next sections will focus on NPOs with a similar approach.

GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF NPOS

In our analysis of the 73 EGD projects, we identified 237 unique NPOs participating. The map shown in Figure 1 displays the global distribution of these NPOs, with Belgium showing the highest concentration with 41 organizations. Significant numbers are also observed in, Spain (28), Italy (26), and France (21). This clustering indicates that Western and Southern Europe are primary hubs for non-profit activities. Countries like Germany and the Netherlands also show notable figures with 15 and 22 organizations, respectively. Outside of Europe, the presence of NPOs is sparse. In Africa, countries such as Burkina Faso, Ghana, and Morocco each host only one NPOs. Similarly, in South America, Chile has only one NPO. This stark contrast highlights a potential need for increased non-profit activities and support in these regions, suggesting a disparity in the distribution of resources and organizational support globally.

Figure 1 Global Distribution of NPOs participating in the Green Deal

The bar charts in and Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate the distribution of NPOs across different regions in Europe and selected regions worldwide, respectively. Figure 2 focuses on the European continent, showing that Western Europe hosts the largest number of NPOs, with 107 entities. This is followed by Southern Europe with 71 organizations, Northern Europe with 26, and Eastern Europe with 21. This distribution indicates a higher concentration of NPOs in the more economically developed and politically stable regions of Europe, likely reflecting better infrastructure, funding opportunities, and supportive regulatory environments. Figure 3 presents data for regions

Figure 2 Number of NPOs in Europe per Region

outside Europe, highlighting significantly lower numbers of NPOs. Southern Africa, Western Africa, and Western Asia each have 3 NPOs, while Eastern Africa, Northern Africa, and Southern South America each have only 1. This stark contrast underscores a disparity in the global distribution of NPOs, suggesting a potential need for increased support and development in these regions to address local needs and promote sustainable development. The lower numbers in these areas may reflect challenges such as limited funding, political instability, and less developed infrastructure for non-profit operations.

Figure 3 Number of NPOs in Europe per Rest of the World

NPOS PRESENCE IN EGD PROJECTS

ANALYSIS OF NPOS INVOLVEMENT IN EGD PROJECTS

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of NPOs across various EGD projects. The data indicates that 15 projects, accounting for 20.55% of the total, do not involve any NPOs. The most common number of NPOs per project is 2, with 21 projects (49.32% cumulatively) falling into this category. Projects with 4 NPOs are also frequent, comprising 16 projects and bringing the cumulative percentage to 71.23%. As the number of NPOs increases, the frequency of such projects decreases significantly. For instance, only 12 projects have 8 NPOs, and a few projects have even higher numbers, with the maximum being 22 NPOs in a single project. This suggests that while most projects engage a small number of NPOs, a few projects stand out by involving a substantially larger number, reflecting diverse project scopes and capacities for collaboration.

Figure 4 Distribution of NPOs in EGD Projects

Furthermore,

Table 14 in Appendix 5 reveals that, on average, each project includes approximately 4 NPOs, with a mean of 3.88 and a standard error of 0.49. The median number of NPOs per project is 3, indicating that half of the projects have three or fewer NPOs, while the mode of 0 highlights that 15 projects do not involve any NPOs. The standard deviation of 4.19 and a sample variance of 17.55 demonstrate considerable variability in NPOs involvement across projects.

The distribution is positively skewed (skewness of 1.71) with a higher peak and heavier tails (kurtosis of 3.49) than a normal distribution, indicating a few projects with significantly higher numbers of NPOs. The range of 21, with a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 21 NPOs per project, underscores the diversity in NPOs participation. The total count of 283 NPOs participations across all projects, with a 95% confidence interval of ± 0.98 around the mean, further supports the reliability of these findings. This count includes multiple participations by some of the 237 unique NPOs. This statistical overview highlights the varied yet substantial role of NPOs in EGD projects, pointing to opportunities for enhancing their involvement.

PROJECTS' HIGHLIGHTS

Through the analysis shown above it was found that projects, such as [SchoolFood4Change](#) and [ZeroW](#), which involve 21 and 15 NPOs respectively, stand out for their extensive engagement with NPOs. These projects likely require broad-based collaboration and diverse expertise, hence the high number of NPOs partners. Other high-end projects include [Agro2Circular](#) and [WaterLANDS](#), with 13

NPOs each, and [EcoeFISHent](#) with 14, reflecting the need for comprehensive stakeholder involvement in achieving their ambitious goals in areas such as sustainable food systems and water resource management.

In the middle range, projects like [ARSINOE](#), with 8 NPOs, and [MERLIN](#), with 7, demonstrate a balanced approach to NPO involvement, indicating significant but more focused collaboration. Similarly, projects like [SHARED GREEN DEAL](#) and [TREEADS](#), each involving 7 NPOs, highlight substantial yet manageable partnerships aimed at achieving their objectives in sustainability and environmental management.

At the low end of the spectrum, several projects, such as [ALTERNATIVE](#), [PROMISCES](#), and [CIRCULAR FOAM](#), do not include any NPOs, suggesting a different focus or strategy that relies less on NPO participation. Projects like [I-CISK](#) and [ENOUGH](#), each with only 2 NPOs, reflect minimal but targeted engagement, possibly due to the specific expertise required or the project's scope. Refer to Appendix 1 for detailed information on each specific project.

CONSORTIUM ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES IN EGD PROJECTS

When establishing a grant consortium for EGD projects, it is crucial to assign roles based on the level of participation to ensure effective collaboration and the achievement of project objectives (see Appendix 2, Section Consortium roles and responsibilities in EGD projects). The Coordinator manages the project, submits reports and deliverables, and acts as the intermediary with the EU Granting Authority, ensuring all administrative requirements are met. Participants execute substantial parts of the project, prepare grant documentation, and report on progress, being directly funded by the EU. Third Parties provide additional support and resources necessary for the project but do not receive direct funding from the EU; their funding is cascaded from the Coordinator or Participants, enhancing the consortium's capabilities with expertise, services, or goods that Participants may lack.

NPOS PARTICIPATION IN EGD PROJECTS

The statistical analysis of the 237 NPOs involved in the 73 EGD projects reveals a varied landscape of participation roles and significant contributions across different projects. The following points summarize the diverse roles and participation levels of NPOs in the EGD projects:

- **Number of Coordinators:** Four NPOs serve as Coordinators in the EGD projects, overseeing project management and ensuring alignment with EU requirements.
- **Number of Participants:** A substantial 222 NPOs act as Participants, executing key project tasks and contributing to the overall success of the initiatives.
- **Number of Third Parties:** Fourteen NPOs function as Third Parties, providing specialized support and resources through cascaded funding from Coordinators or Participants.
- **Only Coordinators:** Three NPOs are solely Coordinators, focusing exclusively on project oversight and management.
- **Only Participants:** A majority of 220 NPOs participate solely as Participants, emphasizing their primary role in project execution.
- **Only Third Parties:** Twelve NPOs are exclusively Third Parties, providing critical support and expertise without direct EU funding.
- **Coordinators also as Participants:** One NPO that serves as a Coordinator is also involved as a Participant in other projects, highlighting its multifaceted engagement.
- **Third Parties also as Coordinators:** One NPO operates as both a Third Party and a Coordinator, indicating its versatile role in project management and support.
- **Third Parties also as Participants:** Two NPOs participate as both Third Parties and Participants in other projects, demonstrating their extensive involvement and contribution.
- **All Types:** One NPO is involved in all three roles—Coordinator, Participant, and Third Party—showcasing its comprehensive engagement and significant impact across the EGD projects.

KEY EXAMPLES OF NPO INVOLVEMENT IN DIFFERENT CONSORTIUM ROLES

A total of four NPOs serve as Coordinators, overseeing project execution and ensuring compliance with EU directives. Notably, [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) appears as a Coordinator twice, coordinating multiple projects while also participating in nine projects and providing third-party support in one project. This underscores its multifaceted engagement in urban sustainability initiatives. A substantial number of 222 NPOs act as Participants, directly executing project tasks. For instance, the [Stichting Global Resilient Cities Network](#) participates in four projects focused on urban resilience, contributing significantly to sustainable urban development. The [Prospex Institute](#) is involved in three projects centered on social and environmental innovation. Additionally, fourteen NPOs function as

Third Parties, providing specialized support and resources. [Bioforum](#), for example, participates as both a Third Party and a Participant, aiding in organic agriculture initiatives. Most organizations are solely Participants, with 220 NPOs dedicated exclusively to project execution. Examples include the [Stichting Dutch Marine Energy Centre](#), which coordinates one project in energy solutions. Twelve NPOs are exclusively Third Parties, providing critical support, such as [Wetlands International - European Association](#), which focuses on environmental conservation. Furthermore, several NPOs demonstrate versatile roles within the consortia. One notable example is [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#), which not only serves as a Coordinator but also participates in nine other projects and provides third-party support in one project, showcasing comprehensive engagement across multiple dimensions. Two NPOs, [Bioforum](#) and [Fundacion Para El Fomento De La Investigacion Sanitaria Y Biomedica De La Comunitat Valenciana](#), operate as both Third Parties and Participants, demonstrating their extensive involvement and flexibility in contributing to various projects.

DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTION OF NPO TYPES

The investigation into 237 NPOs reveals a diverse landscape of entities contributing to various sectors within the framework of the EGD. These organizations are classified into ten categories: Association, Charity, Confederation, Consortium, Cooperative, Federation, Foundation, Non-Profit Organization, Think Tank, and Union (refer to Appendix 2, section: Partner classification, Subsection: Classification and examples of Non-Profit Organizations in EGD projects).

Figure 5 illustrates this distribution, underscoring the predominance of Associations and Foundations. The largest group, Associations, accounts for 45% of the total, indicating a significant presence of entities formed around common purposes or activities, such as local government sustainability initiatives and technological innovation in specific industries. Foundations, making up 25%, play crucial roles in funding and supporting initiatives across various domains, while NPOs at 15% highlight a range of activities that do not fit neatly into other categories.

Figure 5 Distribution of NPO Types

Consortiums, Cooperatives, and Federations collectively account for 11%, reflecting collaborative efforts in large-scale projects, mutual benefit operations, and joint advocacy for common goals. Think Tanks and Unions, each constituting 1%, indicate focused research and advocacy roles within the broader landscape. This distribution emphasizes the varied mechanisms through which NPOs contribute to the EGD, from grassroots associations to well-funded foundations and specialized think tanks.

HIGHLIGHTS OF THE DIVERSITY OF NPOS

Examining the activities and projects of specific NPOs enriches our understanding of their impact within the EGD framework. For instance, [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#), an Association based in Germany, leads with 12 projects focused on urban planning and development, highlighting its significant role in promoting sustainable urban environments. Similarly, the [European Environmental Bureau](#), a Federation, supports environmental protection advocacy, emphasizing the importance of collective action in addressing environmental challenges.

Charities also play a crucial role in environmental conservation, as seen with the [Westcountry Rivers Trust LBG](#) in the UK, which works on natural resource management and environmental sustainability. Another notable charity, [The Scottish Wildlife Trust LBG](#), is dedicated to wildlife conservation and environmental education. Foundations such as [Sihtasutus Eestimaa Looduse Fond](#) in Estonia contribute significantly to climate science, supporting extensive research in climate and environmental sciences. In addition to associations and foundations, other types of NPOs contribute significantly to the EGD objectives. For instance, Consortia like [Tecnoalimenti SCPA](#) in Italy focus on food technology research, while Cooperatives such as [Irish Rural Link Co-Operative Society Limited](#) in Ireland support energy and environmental solutions. Think Tanks like [Collaborating Centre On Sustainable Consumption And Production GGMBH](#) in Germany conduct essential research on sustainability. These examples illustrate

the diverse mechanisms through which NPOs advance the goals of the EGD, ranging from localized projects to broad, collaborative research initiatives.

DISTRIBUTION OF NET EU FUNDING AMONG THE TYPES OF NPOS

An examination of the net EU funding allocated to various types of NPOs reveals significant insights into the financial distribution within this sector. From a total of €106,412,815.09 in net EU funding, the distribution is markedly uneven across different types of NPOs, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Associations receive the largest share of funding, totaling €52,102,266, which accounts for 49.0% of the total net EU funding. Foundations receive €30,676,057, representing 28.8% of the total funding. NPOs account for €11,987,872, making up 11.3% of the total funding. Consortia, which receive €3,603,441, represent 3.4% of the total funding. Cooperatives, such as the Irish Rural Link Co-Operative Society Limited in Ireland with €89,950, make up 2.4% of the total funding. Federations receive €2,780,801, accounting for 2.6% of the total funding. Think Tanks receive €1,408,375, or 1.3% of the total. Charities, with €1,008,041 in funding, represent 0.9% of the total. Confederations and Unions receive the least funding, with €148,500 (0.1%) and €149,631 (0.1%) respectively.

Figure 6 Distribution of Net EU Funding Among the different NPO Types

Associations receive the largest share of funding, totaling €52,102,266, which accounts for 49.0% of the total net EU funding. Foundations receive €30,676,057, representing 28.8% of the total funding. NPOs account for €11,987,872, making up 11.3% of the total funding. Consortia, which receive €3,603,441, represent 3.4% of the total funding. Cooperatives, such as the Irish Rural Link Co-Operative Society Limited in Ireland with €89,950, make up 2.4% of the total funding. Federations receive €2,780,801, accounting for 2.6% of the total funding. Think Tanks receive €1,408,375, or 1.3% of the total. Charities, with €1,008,041 in funding, represent 0.9% of the total. Confederations and Unions receive the least funding, with €148,500 (0.1%) and €149,631 (0.1%) respectively.

EXAMPLES OF DISTRIBUTION OF NET EU FUNDING AMONG THE DIFFERENT NPO TYPES

Some examples include the [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) in Germany, which receives €6,580,153.74 for urban planning and development, and [Prospex Institute](#) in Belgium, which receives €2,502,250 for media, marketing, and cultural studies. These organizations exemplify how Associations leverage significant funding to drive diverse initiatives. Notable examples of Foundations include [Sihtasutus Eestimaa Looduse Fond](#) in Estonia, receiving €2,403,325 for climate and environmental sciences, and [Idryma Technologias Kai Erevnas](#) in Greece, which receives €1,659,875 to support education and research. Impactful entities in the NPOs category include [We Are Here Venice](#) in Italy, receiving €1,690,822 for social sciences and humanities, and [Internationella Kemikalisekretariatet](#) in Sweden, which receives €862,876.75 for climate and environmental sciences.

Consortia examples include the [Consorzio per la Promozione della Cultura Plastica Proplast](#) in Italy, receiving €865,490 for manufacturing services. Examples of Cooperatives include the [Irish Rural Link Co-Operative Society Limited](#) in Ireland, receiving €89,950, emphasizing collaborative approaches in sectors like energy solutions. Exemplars of Federations include the [European Environmental Bureau](#) in Belgium, receiving €1,433,750 for environmental advocacy, and [Solidar](#) in Belgium, receiving €210,687.50. Think Tanks include the [Collaborating Centre On Sustainable Consumption And Production GGMBH](#) in Germany, noted for its work in environmental sustainability with €1,074,625. Charities are exemplified by the [Westcountry Rivers Trust LBG](#) in the UK, receiving €958,437.50 for forestry and natural resources. The [Lithuanian Confederation of Industrialists](#), receiving €148,500, and [Enosi Katanaloton Poiotita Tis Zois](#) in Greece, receiving €149,631.25, demonstrate focused efforts in industrial services and consumer goods, respectively.

DISTRIBUTION OF NPOS AND THEIR FUNDING ACROSS ECONOMIC SECTORS

The proportional representation of NPOs within 15 overarching economic sectors is shown in Figure 4 (see Appendix 2 for further information about the categories). The data reveals that the largest proportion of NPOs, 29%, is involved in the "Energy and Environmental Solutions" sector, reflecting a significant focus on sustainability and environmental initiatives within the EGD projects. Following this, 23% of the NPOs operate within the "Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources" sector, indicating a strong emphasis on agricultural and natural resource management. Other notable sectors include "Education and Research" and "Transportation and Urban Development," each comprising 8% of the NPOs. "Science, Technology, and Innovation" and "Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies," account for 7% and 6%, respectively. Smaller representations are observed in sectors such as "Business, Finance, and Consulting" and "Information, Communication, and Technology," each with 6 NPOs, or 2% of the

total. Sectors like "Aerospace, Defense, and Aviation," and "Biotechnology and Life Sciences," have the least representation, with only 2 and 1 NPOs respectively, underscoring their minimal involvement in the projects.

Figure 7 Distribution of NPOs across economic sectors

The NPOs Net EU Funding Distribution in Sectors is shown in Figure 8. The "Energy and Environmental Solutions" sector received the highest funding, amounting to €32.46 million, representing 30.5% of the total funding. The "Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources" sector follows with €18.70 million, accounting for 17.6% of the total funding. Additionally, the "Transportation and Urban Development" sector received considerable funding of €16.63 million, or 15.6% of the total. Close to 7% are "Education and Research", "Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies", "Science, Technology, and Innovation" with 7.1%, 6.9% and 6.8%, respectively. Smaller funding allocations were observed in sectors such as "Business, Finance, and Consulting" (€2.25 million) and "Industry and Manufacturing" (€3.64 million), with minimal involvement from sectors like "Aerospace, Defense, and Aviation" and "Biotechnology and Life Sciences."

Figure 8 Distribution of net EU funding for NPOs across economic sectors

Analyzing the distribution of the number of organizations per category reveals some proportional discrepancies compared to the funding distribution (see Figure 7). For instance, while the "Energy and Environmental Solutions" sector, with 68 organizations, received the highest funding, the "Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources" sector, with 54 NPOs, received significantly less funding proportionally. Conversely, the "Transportation and Urban Development" sector, with only 18 organizations, received 15.6% of the total funding, indicating a higher per-organization funding allocation. Similarly, the "Education and Research" sector, with 18 organizations, received around 7.1% of the total funding, suggesting a balanced but slightly higher per-organization funding than some other sectors. prioritization of certain initiatives.

NPOS PARTICIPATION IN MULTIPLE EGD PROJECTS

The statistical analysis shown in Table 15 in Appendix 5 provides an overview of the number of projects involving NPOs. The average number of projects per NPO is approximately 1.18, with a median and mode of 1, indicating that most NPOs are involved in just one project. The standard deviation of 0.81 and the high skewness (10.44) and kurtosis (133.53) values suggest that while most NPOs participate in a single project, a small number of NPOs are engaged in multiple projects, creating a distribution with a long right tail. The range of 11, with the minimum and maximum values being 1 and 12 respectively, further underscores the disparity in participation levels. The count of 237 unique NPOs illustrates the widespread but varied involvement of these organizations in EGD projects. The confidence interval

indicates high precision in estimating the mean number of projects per NPO, supporting the reliability of these findings.

EXAMPLES OF NPOS PARTICIPATING IN MULTIPLE PROJECTS

Several NPOs are notably active across multiple EGD projects, showcasing their extensive involvement and expertise in various environmental and sustainability initiatives. Leading the list is the [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) from Germany, which participates in 12 projects. This high level of engagement underscores ICLEI's pivotal role in promoting local government sustainability initiatives across Europe.

In the Netherlands' [Stichting Global Resilient Cities Network](#), engaged in 4 projects, reflects its focus on enhancing urban resilience and sustainability.

Several other organizations are involved in multiple projects, albeit at a lower frequency. For instance, the [Prospex Institute](#) (Belgium), [Idryma Technologias Kai Erevnas](#) (Greece) and the [Verein Der Europaeischen Buergerwissenschaften - ECSA E.V.](#) from Germany each participate in 3 projects. Additionally, organizations like [Wavec/Offshore Renewables](#) from Portugal and [Energy Cities/Energie-Cites Association](#) from France are involved in 2 projects each, indicating their targeted yet impactful contributions in their respective fields.

ANALYSIS OF NET EU FUNDING DISTRIBUTION TO NPOS IN EGD PROJECTS

GENERAL ANALYSIS OF NET EU FUNDING FOR NPOS

Table 16 in Appendix 5 contains the statistical analysis of EU funding allocated to NPOs involved in the EGD projects, revealing significant disparities in funding distribution. The average amount of EU funding received by NPOs is approximately €448,999.22, with a median of €279,125.00, indicating that half of the NPOs receive this amount or less. The mode of €0 reflects that three organizations do not receive any EU funding, highlighting some level of exclusion within the funding distribution. The standard deviation of €586,220.72 and sample variance of €3.44E+11 show substantial variability in the funding amounts. The high kurtosis (51.54) and skewness (5.73) values suggest a highly skewed distribution with a few NPOs receiving much larger amounts of funding, leading to a long right tail. This is further evidenced by the wide range of funding amounts, from €0 to €6,580,153.74.

The total sum of €106,412,815.10 in EU funding distributed across 237 NPOs. The confidence interval further supports the reliability of the mean estimate, highlighting the precision of the analysis despite the high variability. These statistics underscore the uneven distribution of EU funding among NPOs, suggesting that while many organizations receive modest funding, a select few receive substantial amounts, reflecting potential strategic priorities or varying capacities among the NPOs.

Figure 9 illustrates the distribution of NPOs against the net EU funding they receive within the EGD projects, along with the cumulative percentage of organizations by funding amount. A significant observation is that the highest frequency of organizations falls within the funding bins of €100,000 to €250,000, with the highest concentration at the €150,000 and €200,000 bins, each involving 24 and 27 organizations, respectively. This indicates that most NPOs receive moderate levels of funding, reflecting a centralized distribution around these amounts. The cumulative percentage line rises steeply within these bins, reaching approximately 45.57% at €250,000. This suggests that nearly half of the NPOs receive funding up to this amount. As the funding amount increases beyond €250,000, the frequency of NPOs receiving higher amounts decreases significantly. For instance, fewer NPOs are seen in higher funding bins, such as €1,000,000 or more, with only a small number reaching up to €6,580,153.74.

The data distribution is positively skewed, with a long tail extending to the right. This indicates that while many NPOs receive relatively modest funding, a few receive significantly higher amounts, contributing to the overall skewness of the distribution. The cumulative percentage reaches close to 100% at around €7,000,000, confirming that all NPOs fall within this range. The distribution of funding highlights the presence of a core group of NPOs receiving mid-range funding and a smaller subset receiving considerably higher amounts. This pattern suggests strategic allocation of funds where a majority are supported to a moderate extent, ensuring broad participation, while a select few receive substantial funding, possibly reflecting their larger scale operations or critical roles in the projects.

Figure 9 Distribution of Net EU Funding Among NPOs in EGD Projects

NPOS HIGHLIGHTS IN EGD FUNDING

At the high end of Net EU Funding, a few NPOs stand out for receiving substantial EU funding, reflecting their pivotal roles in large-scale environmental and sustainability initiatives. [CLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) (Germany) leads with €6,580,153.74, emphasizing its significant influence in local government sustainability efforts. [Prospex Institute](#) (Belgium) also stands out with a significant funding amount of €2,502,250.00, reflecting its crucial involvement in fostering participatory and inclusive environmental initiatives. The [Sihtasutus Eestimaa Looduse Fond](#) (Estonia) follows with €2,403,325.00, highlighting its key role in nature conservation. Additionally, [Stichting Dutch Marine Energy Centre](#) (Netherlands) and [WWF Vilag Termeszefi Alap Magyarorszag Alapitvany](#) (Hungary) received €1,625,711.25 and €954,261.25 respectively, showcasing their critical contributions to marine energy and wildlife conservation.

In the middle tier, organizations like [Energy Cities/Energie-Cites Association](#) (France) with €1,025,584.25 and [Rikolto Belgie](#) (Belgium) with €743,375.00 play essential roles in regional and community-focused sustainability projects. The [Association Internationale Villes et Ports](#) (France) and the [Verband Kommunaler Unternehmen eV](#) (Germany) received €847,768.75 and €542,500.00 respectively, demonstrating their involvement in urban and utility sector sustainability.

At the lower end, NPOs such as the [Conseil des Architectes d'Europe](#) (Belgium) with €301,785.00 and the [Federazione Nazionale Cooperative della Pesca Associazione](#) (Italy) highlight contributions to specialized sectors like architecture and fishing cooperatives. Other notable recipients include the [Open & Agile Smart Cities](#) (Belgium) with €271,875.00 and the [European Environmental Bureau](#) (Belgium) with €1,433,750.00, underscoring their efforts in promoting smart city initiatives and environmental advocacy.

The very low end includes NPOs like [Wetlands International - European Association](#) (Netherlands) with €198,362.50, the [Association Française pour la Promotion des Equipements et Services Aeroportuaires et ATC Proavia](#) (France) with €185,437.50, and the [Mediterranean Information Office For Environment, Culture And Sustainable Development Association](#) (Greece) with €208,875.00. These organizations, though receiving smaller grants, contribute significantly to niche areas such as wetland conservation and sustainable development in Mediterranean regions. Another example is the [Asociacion Ecovalia](#) (Spain) with €60,937.50, focusing on organic farming and sustainable agricultural practices.

In summary, the EU's funding distribution among NPOs for the EGD projects is marked by substantial variability, reflecting a strategic approach that balances significant allocations to key players with broader support to numerous smaller entities.

COMPARISON BETWEEN NET EU FUNDING FOR ALL ORGANIZATIONS AND NPOS

A comparison of the funding allocations for all organizations, contained in Appendix 4, Section: Analysis and distribution of partners in EGD projects, versus the subset presented above containing only NPOs reveals significant disparities and provides important insights into the distribution and effectiveness of funding.

FUNDING DISPARITIES

The statistical analysis of EU funding allocation among 1,574 unique partners shows a mean funding per partner of €489,106.95, which is substantially higher than the mean funding of €448,999.22 received

by NPOs. This difference indicates that on average, all organizations receive more funding compared to NPOs, which might reflect the larger scale or broader scope of projects undertaken by for-profit or governmental entities. The higher average funding for all organizations could be due to their ability to mobilize more resources and their larger operational capacities.

The median funding for all organizations is €304,000.00, which is higher than the median for NPOs (€279,125.00). This further underscores that funding is somewhat skewed towards larger entities with possibly greater resource requirements. The mode for all organizations is €0, indicating that 31 organizations do not receive any funding, compared to the three NPOs receiving no funding. This suggests that NPOs, although receiving smaller amounts on average, are more likely to receive some level of funding, reflecting their critical role in achieving EGD objectives at various scales.

VARIABILITY IN FUNDING

The standard deviation of €1,174,802.23 for all organizations is much higher than the €586,220.72 for NPOs, indicating greater variability in funding amounts among all organizations. This is consistent with the observed high kurtosis (474.96) and skewness (17.97) for all organizations, compared to 51.54 and 5.73, respectively, for NPOs. These statistics suggest that a few organizations receive disproportionately high funding amounts, skewing the overall distribution. This significant variability indicates that while many organizations receive moderate funding, a select few are awarded substantially higher amounts, potentially due to their larger project scales or strategic importance.

The cumulative percentage distribution for all organizations shows a steep rise at lower funding levels, indicating that a large proportion of organizations receive smaller amounts of funding. This pattern is similar for NPOs, with the highest frequency of funding concentrated between €100,000 and €250,000. However, the tail of the distribution extends much further for all organizations, reflecting the presence of large entities receiving extensive funding amounts up to €36,480,465.00. For NPOs, the maximum funding observed is €6,580,153.74, showing a narrower distribution range.

ANALYSIS OF NET EU FUNDING DISTRIBUTION TO THIRD PARTIES

PATTERNS OF THIRD-PARTY COLLABORATIONS AMONG NPOS

Figure 10 illustrates the distribution of third parties associated with NPOs. The data indicates that most NPOs (9 out of 17) that have Third Parties are associated with only one. This suggests that most NPOs prefer or are limited to collaborating with a single external partner. For example, [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) in Germany and the [Federazione Nazionale Cooperative della Pesca Associazione](#) in Italy each engage with only one third party. Other organizations, such as [Stiftelsen Världsnaturfonden WWF](#) in Sweden and [Stichting Wetlands International](#) in the Netherlands, also exemplify this pattern of minimal external collaboration.

Figure 10 Distribution of Third-Party Collaborations Among NPOs

A smaller group of NPOs (3 organizations) are linked to two third parties: the [International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements European Union Regional Group](#) in Sweden, [Corila - Consorzio Per Il Coordinamento Delle Ricerche Inerenti Al Sistema Lagunare Di Venezia](#) in Italy and [ECATS International Association AISBL](#).

Another 3 organizations have four third parties, i.e., [Acta Association de Coordination Technique Agricole - Les Instituts Techniques Agricoles](#) in France, the [European Association For Storage Of Energy](#) in Belgium, and [ECCSEL European Research Infrastructure Consortium](#) in Norway.

Notably, the [Alliance Europeenne De Recherche Dans Le Domaine De L'energie](#) in Belgium stands out by being connected to ten third parties, indicating a much broader network of collaboration. This high level of engagement reflects its extensive involvement in various initiatives and its capacity to manage multiple partnerships.

The absence of NPOs with five, six, seven, or eight third parties suggests that while there is a range of third-party engagements, extremely high numbers of partnerships are rare. The data reflects a skewed distribution where most NPOs maintain a limited number of third-party collaborations, with only a few extending their partnerships to a larger network. This pattern may indicate resource constraints, strategic choices, or sector-specific factors influencing the extent of external collaboration among NPOs.

ANALYSIS OF CASCADING FUNDING TO THIRD PARTIES IN EGD PROJECTS

The statistical analysis presented in Table 17 in Appendix 5 is an overview of the cascading funds distributed from NPOs to Third Parties. This analysis provides insights into the distribution and variability of these funds across different NPOs. The analysis reveals that the average amount of cascading funds distributed to third parties is approximately €277,719.64 per NPO, with a median of €192,500.00. This suggests that while some NPOs cascade substantial funds, most projects distribute moderate amounts. The mode of €30,000.00 indicates that this amount is the most common value of cascading funds across the projects analyzed. The standard deviation of €326,373.58 and sample variance of €1.0652E+11 indicate a high degree of variability in the cascading funds. The positive skewness (1.46) and kurtosis (0.93) further suggest that while most NPOs cascade lower amounts, a few projects distribute significantly higher funds to third parties, creating a long right tail in the distribution. The range of cascading funds spans from €0 to €1,056,438.00, highlighting the diverse funding strategies and resource allocations among different NPOs. The total sum of cascading funds is €4,721,233.87 across 17 NPOs.

CONCLUDING REMARKS OF THE ANALYTICAL STUDY

The analysis of NPO involvement in EGD projects reveals a varied and significant contribution from these entities across multiple initiatives. With an average of nearly four NPOs per project, their involvement is crucial in achieving the ambitious goals set by the EGD. The substantial variability in the number of NPOs per project, indicated by the standard deviation and range, underscores the diverse nature and scale of these projects. The positive skewness and kurtosis values further highlight that while many projects engage a small number of NPOs, a few projects involve significantly higher numbers, reflecting their expansive and collaborative scope.

Projects like [SchoolFood4Change](#) and [ZeroW](#), which involve 21 and 15 NPOs respectively, exemplify extensive collaboration, likely necessary for tackling complex issues such as sustainable food systems and water resource management. Conversely, projects with fewer or no NPOs may focus on more specialized or less collaborative aspects of the EGD. This diversity in NPOs involvement is indicative of the different approaches required to address the challenges.

The varied roles within consortia, from Coordinators to Participants and Third Parties, highlight the flexibility and adaptability of NPOs in contributing to EGD projects. With four NPOs serving as Coordinators, 222 as Participants, and 14 as Third Parties, their contributions are critical in driving project execution and providing specialized support. The ability of some NPOs to serve in multiple roles, such as the [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#), demonstrates their comprehensive engagement and pivotal role in project management and execution.

Examining the distribution of net EU funding shows that most NPOs receive moderate levels of funding, with a core group receiving higher amounts. This strategic allocation ensures broad participation while supporting key players with substantial funding to drive significant initiatives. The variability in funding amounts, with a high standard deviation and a positively skewed distribution, indicates that while many NPOs receive modest funding, a select few receive significantly higher amounts.

The involvement of NPOs in multiple projects also highlights their extensive engagement and expertise. Organizations like [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) and [Stichting Global Resilient Cities Network](#) demonstrate their capacity to contribute across several initiatives, enhancing their impact and fostering collaboration across different sectors.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS EMERGING FROM THE ANALYTICAL STUDY

Drawing from the analysis of NPO involvement shown above, the insights highlight the need for more equitable funding distribution, increased collaboration, and enhanced operational support NPOs, with the following focus points:

- **Equitable Funding Distribution:** Funding varies significantly, with a few NPOs receiving much while many get little. Policies should aim to balance funding more fairly, increasing support for smaller and medium-sized NPOs to enhance their impact on EGD goals. This ensures broader participation and maximizes collective impact.
- **Support for Collaboration and Networking:** NPOs play diverse roles, highlighting the need for collaboration. Policies should foster strategic partnerships and networks, enabling knowledge exchange and resource sharing to boost EGD project effectiveness. This aligns with the EU's focus on collaborative innovation to tackle complex challenges.
- **Capacity Building and Technical Support:** Smaller NPOs often struggle with EGD complexities. Providing targeted technical assistance, training, and capacity-building can empower these

organizations. Simplifying administrative procedures and guiding EU compliance can help NPOs focus on their core activities, supporting inclusive growth and resilient communities.

- **Incentivizing Diverse Participation:** Diverse NPOs engagement brings varied perspectives and expertise. Policies should incentivize participation from different sectors and regions, ensuring widespread benefits of the EGD. This includes targeted outreach and support for NPOs in underserved areas critical to sustainability.
- **Fostering Innovation through Competitive Funding:** Competitive funding mechanisms that reward innovation can drive progress in EGD initiatives. Policies should support pilot projects and experimental programs, allowing NPOs to test and scale new ideas. This aligns with the EU's strategy to foster innovation for climate action and sustainable development.

SURVEY ANALYSIS

The second phase of our study involved a comprehensive questionnaire aimed at NPOs engaged in EGD projects. This survey was conducted from April 18, 2024, to May 15, 2024.

SURVEY ANALYSIS OF ORGANIZATIONAL INVOLVEMENT IN EGD PROJECTS

Upon the survey's closure, we received responses from 27 individuals representing 26 organizations. To maintain some confidentiality, the organizations' names have been anonymized. Below is an analysis of the types of organizations that participated and the sectors they represent.

The responses were primarily from educational and research institutions (6 responses), NPOs (20 responses), and governmental bodies (1 response). Among the educational and research institutions, a notable participant was a research organization with approximately € 5.3 million in net EU funding, involved in engineering and technology. Governmental bodies were also represented, exemplified by a public body dedicated to economic development with € 845,358 in funding. The distribution of the 20 responses received from individuals representing NPOs, categorized by organization type, is shown in Figure 11. Most responses came from Foundations, accounting for 9 responses. Associations followed with 7 responses, highlighting their significant presence among the surveyed entities. Cooperatives and Federations each had 1 response, indicating a smaller representation. Additionally, there was 1 response from a Think Tank and 1 from an uncategorized NPO.

Figure 11 Distribution of NPO Types Among Survey Responses

Figure 12 Distribution of NPOs' Responses by Economic Sector

Cooperatives and Federations each had 1 response, indicating a smaller representation. Additionally, there was 1 response from a Think Tank and 1 from an uncategorized NPO.

The distribution of NPOs' responses by economic sectors is shown in Figure 12. From the 20 responses received, the majority were from the "Energy and Environmental Solutions" sector, accounting for 8 responses. This is followed by the "Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources" sector with 6 responses. The remaining sectors include "Science, Technology, and Innovation" with 2 responses, and one response each from "Business, Finance, and Consulting," "Education and Research," "Health and Medical Services," and "Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies."

Such NPOs comprised for example, an agricultural cooperative with € 350,656 in funding is actively engaged in the forestry and timber industry. Additionally, an association with € 1.2 million in funding focuses on technology and innovation, while another, with € 612,750 in funding, is dedicated to environmental conservation. Foundations also played a critical role, with one conservation foundation receiving € 1.3 million and another think tank focused on environmental sustainability receiving € 1.1 million in funding.

GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF THE SURVEY RESPONSES

Figure 13 is a map illustrating the geographic distribution of responses from NPOs participating in the EGD projects. The data reveals that the highest number of responses came from Spain, with four responses. This is depicted by the darkest shade of blue on the map. France, Italy, and Portugal each contributed three responses, shown in a slightly lighter shade. Germany, Estonia, the Netherlands, and Sweden each provided two responses, indicated by a moderate blue shade. Additionally, Austria, Hungary, Namibia, Norway, Romania, and Switzerland each had one response, marked by the lightest shade of blue.

When comparing this response distribution to the overall participation of organizations in the EGD, some disparities become evident. For instance, Spain, which has 28 NPOs involved, provided four responses, indicating a reasonable level of engagement. However, Italy, with 26 NPOs, also had only three responses, suggesting lower engagement relative to its size. Similarly, France and the Netherlands, with 21 and 22 NPOs respectively, each provided only three and two responses, indicating potential underrepresentation.

Furthermore, countries like Austria and Switzerland, which have 6 and 2 NPOs respectively, each provided only one response, highlighting moderate proportional representation. On the other hand, Namibia, with only two NPOs, managed to contribute one response, which is significant.

Figure 13 Geographic Distribution of Survey Responses

REPRESENTATIVENESS OF SURVEY RESPONSES AMONG NPOS IN EGD PROJECTS

Figure 14 depicts the number of responses received from NPOs participating in various EGD projects. Each bar represents a specific project and the number of responses associated with it. The data shows that the **Agro2Circular** project received 2 responses from NPOs, while **ARV**, **EcoeFISHent**, **ENOUGH**, **GreenSCENT**, **LOCALISED**, **MERLIN**, **oPEN Lab**, **PestNu**, **PHOENIX**, **REST-COAST**, **SUPERB**, and **TREEADS** each garnered 1 response. The **EU-SCORES** project had 3 responses, indicating a relatively higher engagement. **RI-URBANS** and **SteamBioAfrica** each received 2 responses. Notably, the **SchoolFood4Change** project received the highest number of responses, totaling 4. The **WaterLANDS** project also had 2 responses.

Figure 14 Number of Responses per EGD Project from NPOs

To evaluate the representativeness of the survey responses, it is essential to compare these response numbers to the total number of NPOs involved in each project. For instance, **Agro2Circular** includes 13 NPOs but received only 2 responses, reflecting a response rate of approximately 15%. Similarly, **EcoeFISHent** involves 14 NPOs and had just 1 response, translating to about a 7% response rate. The **SchoolFood4Change** project, with 21 NPOs, had 4 responses, indicating a response rate of around 19%. Projects like **ARV** and **MERLIN**, each involving 7 NPOs, received only 1 response, highlighting lower engagement levels. Conversely, the **EU-SCORES** project, which involves 2 NPOs, had a full response rate with all entities participating. This pattern suggests that projects with fewer NPOs, such as **EU-SCORES**, demonstrate higher response rates compared to larger projects.

SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Questions 1-6 of the Survey were designed to identify the organizations and projects, and to track the responses. All data has been processed, with personal information removed to ensure confidentiality. Below, we discuss the findings from the remainder of the questionnaire, specifically questions 7-19. Question 20 served solely to obtain consent for follow-up communication and does not provide additional data for analysis. For a full transcript of the questionnaire, please refer to the Appendix 3.

SCALE OF ORGANIZATIONAL INVOLVEMENT IN EGD PROJECTS

Question 7 was: **"What is the scale of your organization's involvement in the project?"**. The results are depicted in the figure, illustrating the distribution of responses across different types of organizations: Educational and Research Institutions, Governmental Bodies, and NPOs.

The data indicates that NPOs are predominantly involved in the projects, with 10 respondents indicating a major role and 7 indicating a moderate role. This reflects their significant contribution to the EGD projects, particularly in managing major components or influencing several aspects of the projects. Educational and Research Institutions are also active, with 4 indicating a leading role and 1 indicating a major role. The Governmental Body indicated a leading role.

Figure 15 Scale of Organizational Involvement in Green Deal Projects by Organization Type

SELECTION METHODS FOR PARTICIPATION IN EGD PROJECTS

For question 8, **"How was your organization selected to participate in this Green Deal project?"**, the results, depicted in Figure 16, show that the most common method of selection was an "Invitation from the Lead Organization", particularly for NPOs, with 12 responses. This indicates a strong reliance on direct invitations from project leaders to form the consortiums. The "Partnership Formation" method also had a notable presence, with 4 NPOs and 2 Educational and Research Institutions participating through this method.

"Applications" were another common entry method, with 3 responses from Educational and Research Institutions, 1 from Governmental Bodies, and 2 from NPOs. This demonstrates that formal application processes are a significant pathway for project participation across different organization types. There were fewer instances of "Government Recommendations" and "Network or Association Memberships", suggesting that these methods are less commonly used for selecting participants. Only one response indicated selection through "Research Collaboration" and another through "Other," reflecting more unique or less common pathways into the projects.

Figure 16 Selection Methods for Participation in Green Deal Projects

TOPICAL INVOLVEMENT IN EGD PROJECTS

In question 9, we asked participants, **"In what capacity is your organization involved in the Green Deal project?"** and provided multiple roles for respondents to select from.

The distribution of responses by organizational type across various capacities is shown in Figure 17. NPOs reported significant involvement in Research and Analysis (14 responses), Community Engagement (11 responses), and Advocacy (9 responses). These organizations are also active in Project Management and Technical Solutions, with 9 and 7 responses respectively. Educational and Research Institutions primarily contribute to Research and Analysis (6 responses) and Technical Solutions (5 responses), while Governmental Bodies show a more balanced involvement across different capacities, though less prominently.

Figure 17 Roles of Organizations in EGD Projects by Organization Type

Figure 18 is a bar chart that illustrates the number of roles that NPOs assume in EGD projects, ranging from 1 to 7. Specifically, 3 NPOs take on 1 role, 3 NPOs take on 2 roles, 7 NPOs take on 3 roles, 2 NPOs take on 4 roles, 7 NPOs take on 5 roles, 3 NPOs take on 6 roles, and 1 NPO takes on 7 roles. This data reveals that while a small number of organizations join projects with a specific mission, taking on only one role, most organizations demonstrate versatility by undertaking multiple functions throughout the project.

Figure 18 Number of Different Roles

ORGANIZATIONAL IMPACT ON EGD PROJECTS

In question 10, we asked participants, "How would you rate the impact of your organization's contributions to the project on a scale from 1 to 10?" The scale ranged from 1 (No noticeable impact) to 10 (Extremely impactful), allowing respondents to evaluate the significance of their contributions to the project's outcomes.

The results, depicted in Figure 19, show the distribution of responses by organizational type and their self-assessed impact on the EGD projects. The majority of NPOs rated their impact as a 7, with 10 responses, indicating a moderate to high level of perceived influence. Additionally, several NPOs rated their impact as 8 (2 responses), 9 (4 responses), and 10 (2 responses), suggesting that a significant number of these organizations see their contributions as highly impactful.

Figure 19 Impact of Organizational Contributions to EGD Projects

Educational and Research Institutions also reported high impact levels, with 3 responses rating their impact as 10, indicating a strong belief in their crucial contributions to project success. Other ratings from this group included 7 (1 response), 8 (2 responses), and 9 (1 response), highlighting a generally positive assessment of their impact.

CONTRIBUTIONS OF ORGANIZATIONS TO EGD PROJECTS

Question 11 asked, "What specific contributions has your organization made to the project's execution and outcomes?" The anonymized insights are as follows. Educational and Research Institutions have been pivotal in providing scientific research, technological advancements, and policy analysis. Their contributions include the coordination and implementation of advanced air quality tools in urban Europe, preparation of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) for offshore asset inspection and

maritime ecosystem monitoring, and the research and development of methodologies for integrating offshore wind farms with other technologies. They have also conducted studies on energy and adaptation pathways for cities and led project management tasks and major campaigns, providing essential outreach and awareness generation.

NPOs have been extensively involved across multiple facets of the EGD projects. Their contributions include implementing pilot initiatives and coordinating large-scale projects like Agro2circular, developing waste upcycling solutions and circular territorial solutions, and providing input on greenhouse gas emissions while developing technological roadmaps for sectors like food processing. They have led restoration projects, such as reconnecting wetlands to natural flood pulses in Romania and offered technical oversight and operations for conservation efforts. Additionally, NPOs have spearheaded advocacy and outreach activities, developed communication materials and built stakeholder networks. They have established digital environments for progress monitoring and reporting, created pathways for financing innovations, coordinated exchanges between organic farmers and public procurement, and organized EU policy events. NPOs have played a crucial role in both the practical implementation of projects and the dissemination of results, ensuring that the EGD's objectives reach a wide audience.

The governmental Body has contributed mainly through management and coordination roles. They have provided technical support for the economic and social development of regions, led studies on health effects of novel air pollution metrics, and managed partnerships and business modeling. Their involvement ensures that the projects are aligned with regional and national policies and development goals.

SIGNIFICANT ACHIEVEMENTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL INVOLVEMENT IN THE EGD

Question 12 asked, **"In your view, what has been the most significant achievement of your involvement in the Green Deal project?"** The responses, grouped by organization type, reveal various impactful contributions from Educational and Research Institutions, NPOs, and Governmental Bodies. The responses have been anonymized for confidentiality.

Educational and Research Institutions highlighted several key achievements. They have influenced the new air quality directive, showcasing their impact on policy. They have paved the way for the installation of more offshore renewable energy sources without negatively affecting the grid and power system. Their work also includes developing research and living labs, contributing to practical, on-the-ground implementation, and creating online tools to aid local decision-makers in planning exercises. Additionally, they have successfully managed projects to ensure high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) technologies for wildfire prevention, preparedness, detection, response, and restoration are ready for field deployment. Their analysis of green competencies portfolios and policy definition further emphasizes their role in advancing research, influencing policy, and developing practical solutions to complex environmental challenges.

NPOs reported a wide range of significant achievements. They have established operational methods for planting hedges and secured financial support for private forest owners, giving citizens the opportunity to participate and be heard, thus enhancing democratic engagement. Their development of new biodegradable plastic blends and plastic waste upcycling solutions demonstrates their innovative capabilities. They have also facilitated technical insights on restoration and expanded networks of collaborators. Acting as cluster coordinators, they have facilitated consensus and collaborative action among partners. Notably, they have been recognized as Key Innovators for their work on sustainable procurement and have developed tools to estimate the environmental impacts of food procurement. Their creation of the Ecotox Index to show the effects of synthetic chemical pesticides and fertilizers, promotion of sustainable diets in schools, and support for municipalities in implementing the Whole School Food Approach illustrate their extensive involvement in sustainability practices. Furthermore, they have supported the deployment of offshore renewable energy technologies and promoted interdisciplinary collaboration in restoration projects, bringing practical insights and promoting a holistic approach.

Governmental Bodies noted their significant achievement in designing and modeling a circular economy model by linking all value chain stakeholders.

COLLABORATION WITH STAKEHOLDERS IN EGD PROJECTS

Question 13 asked, **"How does your organization collaborate with other stakeholders (e.g., governments, private sector, other NGOs) within the Green Deal project?"** The responses are below summarized and grouped by organization type.

Educational and Research Institutions collaborate with stakeholders through several means. They develop research tools and transfer them to stakeholders, organize joint tasks and research workshops, and hold regular work package meetings and bilateral sessions with partners. Some institutions work

closely with numerous partners, including cities, regions, and local governments, organizing annual stakeholder meetings that involve local and national government representatives, first responders, the private sector, and other EGD projects.

NPOs reported extensive collaboration with a variety of stakeholders. They organize steering committees, site visits, and dissemination activities, involving local networks, governmental bodies, and private sector partners. They have long-standing cooperation with stakeholders in their demo sites, and regularly engage with a wide network, including participation in networking events and as hubs for larger initiatives. For example, one NPO works closely with African partners, organizing meetings with ministries, financial institutions, and local communities. Another coordinates closely with Italian partners and their schools, organizing awareness events and developing tools for continuous stakeholder engagement.

NPOs also engage stakeholders through events, workshops, and direct communication. They often disseminate research findings, organize stakeholder meetings, and collaborate on policy recommendations. Many projects involve a mix of partners from NGOs, governments, universities, and occasionally the private sector. NPOs play a key role in communication and outreach, often leading work packages dedicated to these tasks. Their extensive networking and collaboration efforts underline their importance in integrating diverse perspectives and driving project success.

Governmental Bodies collaborate by preparing project consortia that include stakeholders as members, and by promoting networking and initiatives. They contribute to stakeholder engagement through questionnaires and site visits, ensuring a comprehensive approach to project implementation. Their involvement helps align project activities with broader policy and governance frameworks.

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN IMPLEMENTING EGD PROJECTS

Question 14 asked, **"What challenges have you encountered while implementing the project, and how have you addressed them?"** Below we summarize the responses.

Educational and Research Institutions reported several challenges. One institution faced difficulties in research and stakeholder engagement for air quality projects. Another encountered issues with data sharing, the cost of raw materials, and delays due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the war. They also noted challenges related to regulatory barriers and financing for target groups, which were external to the project partners. The integration of social dimensions in formal approaches and the complexity of aggregating and disaggregating scales across models were also highlighted as significant issues. Furthermore, some partners leaving the consortium caused amendments and financial adjustments, leading to stress and slow progress. Despite these challenges, they addressed them through consistent communication, financial adjustments, and collaborative problem-solving.

NPOs faced a diverse range of challenges. One organization struggled to find motivated private forest owners to install hedges but overcame this by leveraging financial incentives and government aid schemes. Another organization had difficulty coordinating a large consortium of 40 partners, which they managed through proper project management plans. The challenge of integrating multiple viewpoints and maintaining a cross-sectoral approach was addressed by constant stakeholder engagement. Data collection from Hungary was challenging, and support from project partners and the National Statistical Office was crucial in overcoming this hurdle. Experimental equipment design issues were a focus for some, requiring continuous modifications. Large project sizes and new technologies posed numerous challenges, which were managed through trust, partnership, and regular communication.

Other NPOs reported difficulties in stakeholder coordination, which they mitigated through regular meetings and capacity-building frameworks. The bureaucratic nature of EU projects posed challenges, especially for smaller organizations with limited cash flows. Political challenges and a lack of legislative support also hindered advocacy efforts. Additionally, offshore energy projects' complexity and dependence on external factors like weather were significant challenges. Addressing these issues involved consistent communication, stakeholder engagement, and adapting methodologies to fit the project's needs.

Governmental Bodies faced regulatory challenges in implementation. These challenges required careful navigation of regulatory frameworks and constant coordination with relevant stakeholders. Their approach involved integrating these stakeholders into the project consortium and maintaining regular communication to ensure smooth project execution.

EFFECTIVENESS OF LONG-TERM SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGIES

Question 15 asked respondents: **On a scale from 1 to 10, how effective do you believe your organization's long-term sustainability strategies are in maintaining the project's impact post-completion?** The scale ranged from 1 (least effective) to 10 (highly effective).

Figure 20 presents the distribution of responses from Educational and Research Institutions, Governmental Bodies, and NPOs. The data indicates that most respondents rate their long-term sustainability strategies relatively high, with most responses clustering around 7 and 8. Specifically, the highest number of responses, eight, rated the strategies at 7, all of which came from NPOs. Another significant cluster, consisting of six responses, rated the strategies at 8, again predominantly from NPOs. This suggests a general confidence among NPOs in their ability to sustain project impacts post-completion. Educational and Research Institutions provided more varied responses but still generally rated their strategies highly. They had responses at 4, 7, 8, 9, and 10, indicating both confidence and recognition of areas needing improvement. Governmental Bodies provided a rating of 9 showing a high confidence in their sustainability strategies.

Figure 20 Effectiveness of Long-Term Sustainability Strategies in Maintaining Project Impact Post-Completion

MEASURES ENSURING SUSTAINABILITY AND LONG-TERM IMPACT OF PROJECT OUTCOMES

Question 16 asked respondents: **What measures are in place to ensure the sustainability and long-term impact of the project outcomes?** The findings are summarized below.

Educational and Research Institutions employ several measures to ensure sustainability. One institution supports the implementation of new air quality measurements aligned with the new Air Quality Directive. Another institution focuses on economic calculations and demonstrating the viability of hybrid offshore farms, which they believe will have a lasting impact on future installations and decommissioning of such farms. Good collaboration, robust networks, and efforts to secure follow-up funding are emphasized as critical factors. They also develop guidelines for logistics during wildfires and materials for critical infrastructure to ensure long-term impact. One institution has even created a new branch dedicated entirely to green initiatives, reflecting their commitment to sustainability.

NPOs have implemented a wide array of measures. Financial incentives, adaptation of tree species to diverse sites, and active communication are strategies used to ensure sustainability. Local partners' commitment to continuing pilot initiatives post-project is also a key measure. Continuous improvement of technologies, such as PHBV - poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)- production, and preparing business and exploitation plans that include environmental, social, and economic impact evaluations are essential strategies. They also highlight the economic benefits of nature-based solutions, promoting green businesses and sustainable agriculture.

Robust exploitation plans are in place to identify how project outcomes will be used after project completion, with coordinated communication and dissemination activities raising awareness among target groups. Long-term exposure to the biomass industry in Namibia is assured by locating projects within a Biomass Technical Demonstration Center. Stakeholder engagement, knowledge exchange, learning from best practices, and sustained collaboration with SMEs are also critical strategies. Organizing legacy events and having work packages specifically aimed at communication and outreach ensure that knowledge produced is actively shared with external partners and communities. The co-creation framework developed for wetland restoration aims to be useful for future practitioners, ensuring the long-term impact of project outcomes.

Governmental Bodies focus on translating technical pilot tests into digital twin tools, circular model designs, value chain business planning, exploitation strategies, and building financial pipelines. These measures ensure the long-term viability and scalability of project outcomes. They also emphasize the importance of stakeholders taking the time to learn from knowledge sites to sustain project impacts.

CONFIDENCE IN SUSTAINING PROJECT OUTCOMES OVER THE NEXT 5 YEARS

Question 17 asked respondents: **"On a scale from 1 to 10, how confident are you that your organization will sustain the project's outcomes over the next 5 years?"** The scale ranges from 1 (low confidence) to 10 (high confidence). The figure presents the distribution of responses.

Educational and Research Institutions reported their confidence levels primarily at scales 7, 8, 9, and 10, with the highest frequency at scales 7 and 9. This indicates a generally high level of confidence in sustaining project outcomes. Governmental Bodies gave only one response, which was at scale 8, suggesting a high confidence level but based on limited data.

NPOs showed a range of responses concentrated mainly at scales 7 and 8, with six responses at each level, indicating a general tendency towards moderate to high confidence in sustaining project outcomes. Additionally, one response at scale 10 indicates very high confidence, while another at scale 4 indicates low confidence. This distribution suggests that many NPOs feel reasonably assured about their capacity to sustain project outcomes, backed by adequate initiatives and measures. However, the presence of responses at the extremes highlights the variability within this sector, with some organizations facing significant concerns due to limited resources, while others exhibit extreme confidence due to robust strategies and strong institutional frameworks.

Figure 21 Confidence Levels of Non-Profit Organizations in Sustaining Project Outcomes Over the Next Five Years

RECOMMENDATIONS TO ENHANCE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FUTURE EGD PROJECTS

The recommendations collected via Question 18, “**What recommendations would you give to policymakers or funders to enhance the effectiveness of future Green Deal projects?**” are summarized as follows.

Educational and Research Institutions recommend linking directly with the Directorate-General for Environment (DG EN) and the Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) for significant project calls. They emphasize the need for hybridizing offshore wind farms with other technologies to improve renewable energy efficiency. Flexibility in innovation projects and better communication with projects are also highlighted, along with the importance of determining clear, measurable targets and improving the process. Institutions stress the need to turn research into practical applications and build long-term funding for real-time solutions.

NPOs suggest a variety of measures to enhance EGD projects. They call for incentives for private forest owners to ensure genuine ecosystem restoration efforts without over-relying on financial aid. There is an emphasis on involving the public in decision-making processes and educating the population from an early age. Recommendations include facilitating the end-of-waste status for by-products, promoting citizen awareness and education campaigns for the circular economy, and enhancing stakeholder cooperation and interregional information exchange. NPOs advocate for collaboration and integration, ensuring cross-sectoral synergies, policy alignment, social equity, and stakeholder engagement in co-creation and co-ownership. They suggest a limit on project partners, easing the removal of underperforming partners, and improving links with local governments for advice and support. Addressing regulatory frameworks and ensuring a second phase for adaptive management in restoration projects are also suggested.

Additionally, NPOs recommend that public institutions commit to formally adopting project-induced changes. They propose initiatives to connect European projects with EU Directorates-General, bringing science-based innovation into policies, and supporting the integration of financing pathways post-project to avoid pilot trap development. Emphasizing the importance of hybridizing renewable energy technologies, NPOs call for funding follow-up and replication activities, better-fitting working groups for climate change and biodiversity and reworking the Horizon Booster for relevance. They stress the need for social engagement, capacity building, developing financial mechanisms for ecosystem services, long-term involvement, monitoring, leadership, and resolving governance challenges. Finally, simplifying financial reporting procedures and implementing inflation-adjusted funding are highlighted as crucial.

Governmental Bodies recommend working on regulatory frameworks as a priority. They also suggest ensuring a second phase for adaptive management in restoration projects to enhance effectiveness.

FINAL COMMENTS GIVEN IN THE SURVEY

Educational and Research Institutions and NPOs provided a range of additional comments, insights, and suggestions regarding the EGD projects. Educational institutions emphasized the need for systematic follow-up and evaluation by the European Commission, advocating for a programmatic approach and the funding of a second phase to ensure the long-term impact of projects. They also expressed appreciation for the initiative, though some found certain questions challenging to answer due to their specific roles within the project consortium.

NPOs highlighted the ambitious nature of the EGD goals, and the challenges posed by powerful lobbying groups. They stressed the importance of embedding projects within a broader programmatic framework and ensuring systematic follow-up after evaluation. Several NPOs noted difficulties in answering some survey questions, particularly when responsibilities overlapped with other consortium partners. They also called for clearer distinctions between the measures taken by individual NGOs and those taken by the entire consortium.

One NPO expressed gratitude for the initiative (assumed to be the EGD) but pointed out the need for systematic follow-up and long-term funding to monitor the effectiveness of guidelines and training. Another organization echoed this sentiment, stressing the importance of phase 2 funding to assess the impact of recommendations. While some organizations had no additional comments, others expressed a desire to see the results of the research and hoped for continued engagement and transparency in the process.

CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FROM THE SURVEY ANALYSIS

The comprehensive survey conducted from April 18, 2024, to May 15, 2024, aimed to gather insights from NPOs involved in EGD projects. Despite receiving responses from 27 individuals representing 26 organizations, this survey provides valuable perspectives from a subset of the 237 NPOs and the broader context of 1,574 organizations participating in 73 EGD projects. This response rate, while seemingly limited, offers a snapshot of the challenges and recommendations from key players actively engaged in the EGD initiatives. The data, therefore, should be interpreted with an understanding of its scope within the larger ecosystem of participants.

NPOs displayed varied confidence levels, with most responses concentrated at scales 7 and 8, indicating moderate to high confidence in sustaining project outcomes. The presence of responses at extremes, such as scale 4 and scale 10, reflects the sector's diverse preparedness and resource availability. Educational and Research Institutions generally reported high confidence, with significant representation at scales 7, 8, 9, and 10, while the single response from Governmental Bodies at scale 8 suggests high confidence but provides limited data for broader conclusions.

STRATEGIC RECOMMENDATIONS DERIVED FROM THE SURVEY

The recommendations provided by the surveyed organizations underscore critical areas for enhancing the effectiveness of future EGD projects.

Non-Profit Organizations:

- Introduce incentives for private forest owners to ensure genuine ecosystem restoration without over-relying on financial aid.
- Engage the public in decision-making processes and prioritize early education on sustainability.
- Facilitate end-of-waste status for by-products, promote citizen awareness, and enhance stakeholder cooperation and interregional information exchange.
- Ensure cross-sectoral synergies, policy alignment, social equity, and stakeholder engagement in co-creation and co-ownership of projects.
- Limit the number of project partners and simplify the process for removing underperforming partners.
- Strengthen links with local governments for advice and support.
- Address regulatory frameworks comprehensively and ensure a second phase for adaptive management in restoration projects.
- Commit public institutions to formally adopting changes induced by projects and support integration of financing pathways post-project to avoid development traps.
- Simplify financial reporting procedures and implement inflation-adjusted funding.

Educational and Research Institutions:

- Establish direct linkages with the DG EN and the DG SANTE to streamline significant project calls.
- Emphasize the hybridization of offshore wind farms with other technologies to improve renewable energy efficiency.
- Promote flexibility in innovation projects, enhance communication, and establish clear, measurable targets.
- Focus on translating research into practical applications and securing long-term funding for real-time solutions.

Governmental Bodies:

- Prioritize the development of regulatory frameworks to support project implementation and sustainability.
- Ensure a second phase for adaptive management in restoration projects to enhance long-term effectiveness.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS DERIVED FROM THE SURVEY

The survey results, cross-checked with the broader analytical study, reveal significant insights for policymakers and funders:

- **Strengthen Regulatory Frameworks:** Develop comprehensive regulatory frameworks to support the long-term sustainability of EGD projects. This includes ensuring a second phase for adaptive management, particularly in restoration projects.
- **Enhance Public and Stakeholder Engagement:** Increase efforts to involve the public and stakeholders in decision-making processes to ensure inclusive and actionable policies. Prioritize educational initiatives from an early age to build a foundation of awareness and support for sustainability.
- **Promote Cross-Sectoral Collaboration:** Facilitate collaboration across sectors to ensure policy alignment, social equity, and effective co-creation. Enhance connections between projects and relevant EU Directorates-General and local governments to support integrated approaches.
- **Provide Long-Term Funding and Incentives:** Secure long-term funding to prevent the stop-and-go development trap. Introduce incentives for private sector participation in ecosystem restoration projects and ensure follow-up funding for replication activities.
- **Simplify Administrative Processes:** Simplify financial reporting procedures and implement inflation-adjusted funding to reduce administrative burdens, particularly for smaller organizations.
- **Support Technological Innovation:** Encourage hybrid solutions and technological innovations in renewable energy and other sectors to enhance project effectiveness and sustainability.
- **Enhance Communication and Measurability:** Improve communication with project partners and establish clear, measurable targets to track progress and outcomes effectively.
- **Systematic Monitoring and Evaluation:** Embed projects within a broader programmatic framework with systematic follow-up and evaluation to ensure the long-term impact of guidelines, training, and recommendations.

SURVEY ANALYTICAL INSIGHTS LIMITATIONS

The limited response rate highlights the need for cautious interpretation but also points to the representativeness of active and engaged NPOs. NPOs play a critical role in the EGD projects, often acting as the bridge between policy implementation and community engagement. Their feedback underscores the need for practical, flexible approaches and the importance of sustained, long-term support. The variability in confidence levels and the detailed recommendations reflect the sector's dynamic nature and the need for tailored, context-specific strategies to enhance project effectiveness.

CONCLUDING REMARKS: THE ROLE OF NPOS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EGD

This study investigates the pivotal role NPOs play in the implementation of the EGD, specifically focusing on their involvement and funding contributions. The research question guiding this analysis is:

What role do Non-Profit Organizations play in the implementation of the European Green Deal, and how does their involvement and funding contribute to the deal's objectives?

By examining the extent and impact of NPO participation in EGD projects, the study aimed to uncover how these organizations facilitate the achievement of the EGD's goals. NPOs' unique position enables them to address local environmental issues while contributing to broader policy objectives. However, the effectiveness of their contributions depends significantly on the level of strategic engagement and financial support they receive.

This research delved into the financial landscapes of EGD projects, revealing disparities in funding allocation and highlighting the necessity for a more equitable distribution of resources. It explored the geographical distribution of NPOs, the diversity of their roles within project consortia, and the challenges they face in executing their tasks. Through comprehensive data analysis and survey insights, the study provided a nuanced understanding of how NPOs' involvement enhances project outcomes and identifies areas where policy adjustments could further amplify their impact.

Ultimately, this research underscored the importance of NPOs in the EGD framework, arguing that their strategic engagement and adequate funding are vital for the success of Europe's sustainability and climate neutrality goals. The findings offer valuable recommendations for policymakers to optimize the role of NPOs, ensuring that their contributions are maximized to drive the EGD's ambitious agenda forward.

KEY INSIGHTS:

- **Statistical Insights and Disparities:** Statistical analysis highlights significant disparities in funding distribution among participating organizations. The average funding for all partners was €489,106.95, higher than the €448,999.22 average for NPOs. This suggests that while NPOs are essential, they may receive less funding per capita compared to other entities, potentially limiting their capacity to contribute to the EGD's ambitious goals.
- **Contribution to Project Implementation:** NPOs are pivotal in various capacities, from project management and advocacy to technical solutions and community engagement. For instance, projects like SchoolFood4Change and ZeroW involve a high number of NPOs, indicating their vital role in extensive collaborative efforts. The average project includes approximately 4 NPOs, reflecting their significant yet varied involvement across different initiatives.
- **Geographical Distribution and Engagement:** Geographic analysis reveals a concentration of NPOs in Western and Southern Europe, with countries like Belgium, Spain, and Italy hosting the highest numbers. This regional clustering suggests a need for increased support in other areas, particularly outside Europe, where NPO participation is sparse.
- **Impact and Achievements:** Survey data from 27 responses provide insight into the perceived impact of NPOs. The majority rate their contributions highly, particularly in areas such as research and analysis, community engagement, and advocacy. These organizations have been instrumental in policy influence, innovative technological solutions, and practical implementation of sustainability measures, demonstrating their effectiveness in driving EGD objectives.
- **Challenges and Sustainability:** NPOs face various challenges, including regulatory barriers, funding constraints, and coordination complexities. Despite these obstacles, many have implemented robust strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of project outcomes. Measures include economic calculations for hybrid offshore farms, guidelines for wildfire logistics, and comprehensive stakeholder engagement plans.
- **Recommendations for Policymakers and Funders:** Survey participants provided several recommendations to enhance future EGD projects. These include establishing direct linkages with relevant EU Directorates, promoting public engagement and education on sustainability, facilitating end-of-waste status for by-products, and ensuring regulatory and financial support for ecosystem restoration. Simplifying administrative procedures and implementing inflation-adjusted funding were also emphasized to reduce burdens on smaller organizations.

OVERARCHING POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Here are five overarching policy recommendations derived from the analysis of NPO involvement and survey insights, aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of EGD initiatives:

1. EQUITABLE FUNDING AND INCENTIVE STRUCTURES

- Ensure more equitable funding distribution to balance support between large and small NPOs, enhancing their collective impact on EGD goals.
- Secure long-term funding and introduce incentives for private sector participation, particularly in ecosystem restoration projects, to avoid development traps.
- Foster innovation through competitive funding mechanisms that support pilot projects and experimental programs.

2. ENHANCED COLLABORATION AND NETWORKING

- Promote strategic partnerships and cross-sectoral collaboration to boost EGD project effectiveness and ensure policy alignment and social equity.
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and resource sharing among NPOs, EU Directorates-General, and local governments to support integrated approaches and collaborative innovation.

3. CAPACITY BUILDING AND TECHNICAL SUPPORT

- Provide targeted technical assistance, training, and capacity-building to empower smaller NPOs and simplify administrative procedures, enabling them to focus on their core activities.
- Support technological innovation by encouraging hybrid solutions and innovations in renewable energy and other sectors to enhance project effectiveness and sustainability.

4. INCLUSIVE AND DIVERSE PARTICIPATION

- Incentivize diverse NPO engagement to bring varied perspectives and expertise, ensuring widespread benefits of the EGD and targeted outreach to underserved areas.
- Increase public and stakeholder engagement in decision-making processes to ensure inclusive and actionable policies, and prioritize educational initiatives to build a foundation of awareness and support for sustainability.

5. REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS AND MONITORING

- Develop comprehensive regulatory frameworks to support the long-term sustainability of EGD projects, including adaptive management phases for restoration projects.
- Simplify administrative processes and financial reporting procedures to reduce burdens, particularly for smaller organizations.
- Enhance communication with project partners, establish clear, measurable targets, and embed projects within a broader programmatic framework with systematic monitoring and evaluation to ensure long-term impact.

HYPOTHESIS VALIDATION AND BROADER IMPLICATIONS

The hypothesis that the effectiveness of the EGD in achieving its targets is disproportionately influenced by the strategic engagement and funding of NPOs finds substantial support in this study. The data shows that while NPOs play a critical role, their potential impact is hampered by inadequate and uneven funding distributions. NPOs, despite their significant contributions in areas such as research, community engagement, and policy advocacy, receive less financial support compared to other sectors. This funding disparity might limit their capacity to scale up successful initiatives, innovate, and sustain long-term project outcomes.

Furthermore, the involvement of NPOs is crucial in bridging the gap between policy objectives and on-the-ground implementation. Their grassroots connections and expertise in local community dynamics enable them to drive public engagement and foster societal acceptance of EGD initiatives. Projects with high NPO involvement exemplify the potential for broad-based collaboration and significant impact. However, the study highlights that the engagement of NPOs is not uniformly distributed, with significant clustering in Western and Southern Europe and sparse presence in other regions, particularly outside Europe. This disparity underscores the need for more inclusive strategies to engage NPOs across diverse regions, leveraging their unique strengths to address local challenges and promote sustainable development.

The challenges faced by NPOs, including regulatory barriers, funding constraints, and coordination complexities, further validate the hypothesis. These obstacles not only hinder their effectiveness but also reflect a broader systemic issue within the EGD's implementation framework. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive policy reforms, including streamlined administrative procedures, inflation-adjusted funding, and enhanced support for collaborative networks. By doing so, policymakers could unlock the full potential of NPOs, enabling them to contribute more effectively.

Moreover, the survey responses and analytical findings suggest that strategic engagement with NPOs can lead to significant innovations and practical solutions that align with EGD goals. For instance, NPOs' involvement in developing new biodegradable plastics, advancing renewable energy technologies, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices demonstrates their capacity to drive transformative change. Ensuring that these contributions are adequately funded and supported is essential for maximizing their impact and achieving long-term sustainability.

In summary, the hypothesis is strongly validated by the evidence presented. The strategic engagement and equitable funding of NPOs are not merely beneficial but essential for the success of the EGD. Policymakers and funders should recognize and address the critical role of NPOs, implementing measures that enhance their involvement, support their initiatives, and remove barriers to their effectiveness. Such an approach will not only amplify the impact of individual projects but also ensure the broader success of the EGD's objectives, fostering a sustainable and inclusive future for Europe.

In conclusion, NPOs are indispensable to the EGD's success, offering unique expertise, innovation, and community engagement. However, their full potential remains underutilized due to strategic and financial constraints. Policymakers and funders should address these gaps by providing equitable funding, fostering cross-sectoral collaboration, and simplifying administrative processes. Such measures will ensure that NPOs can effectively contribute to achieving the EGD's targets, thereby enhancing the overall impact of the EGD.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] European Commission, "The European Green Deal," [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en. [Accessed May 2024].
- [2] European Commission, "NextGenerationEU," [Online]. Available: https://next-generation-eu.europa.eu/index_en. [Accessed May 2024].
- [3] European Commission, "Green Deal Projects," [Online]. Available: <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/environment-and-climate/european-green-deal/green-deal-projects-support/green-deal-projects-interactive-map/projects>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [4] European Commission, "CORDIS - EU research results," [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/search/en>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [5] S. Bhandari and A. M. Dijkstra, "Interest groups and the European Green Deal: An analysis of strategies used to influence European climate policy," Roskilde University, Roskilde.
- [6] Donorbox, "Top 23 Global Nonprofits Protecting the Environment," 13 May 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://donorbox.org/nonprofit-blog/20-global-nonprofits-environment>. [Accessed 20 May 2024].
- [7] SHARED GREEN DEAL, "SHARED GREEN DEAL," [Online]. Available: <https://sharedgreendeal.eu/partners>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [8] Slow Food Foundation, "European Advocacy," [Online]. Available: https://www.slowfood.com/political_advocacy/european-advocacy-topics/. [Accessed May 2024].
- [9] The Urban Institute, "Building Capacity in Nonprofit Organizations," The Urban Institute, 2001.
- [10] A. Nishimura, R. Sampath, V. Le, A. M. Sheikh and A. Valenzuela, "Transformational Capacity Building," *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, vol. Fall 2020, no. Feature, 2020.
- [11] Unit4, "Top challenges for nonprofit organizations and how to overcome them," 16 January 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unit4.com/blog/8-challenges-for-nonprofit-organizations>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [12] Nonprofit Megaphone LLC, "Capacity Building for Nonprofits," [Online]. Available: <https://nonprofitmegaphone.com/capacity-building/>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [13] C. Rootes, *Environmental Movements: Local, National and Global.*, London: Routledge, 1999.
- [14] Urban Institute, "ATTIS Microsimulation Model," [Online]. Available: <https://www.urban.org/research-methods/attis-microsimulation-model#home>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [15] M. C. Ugwu, A. O. Adewusi and N. E. Nwokolo, "The Role of Public-Private Partnerships in Building Clean Energy Infrastructure in the United States and Nigeria.," *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1049-168, April 2024.
- [16] U. M. Adanma and E. O. Ogunbiyi, "Evaluating the effectiveness of global governance mechanisms in promoting environmental sustainability and international relations," *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, vol. 6, no. 5, May 2024.
- [17] J. Kim, D. Kim, J. Kim and H. Lee, "Collective Impact in Forest Governance: Insights from the Evolution of Stakeholder Networks in the Republic of Korea.," 21 May 2024. [Online]. Available: Kim, Juyeon and Kim, Donghee and Kim, Jaehyun and Lee, Heera, Collective Impact in Forest Governance: Insights from the Evolution of Stakeholder Networks in the Republic of Korea. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835203> or <http://dx.doi.org/1>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [18] R. Cox, *Environmental communication and the public sphere*, Sage, 2013.

- [19] M. Olson Jr, *The Logic of Collective Action: Public Goods and the Theory of Groups*, with a new preface and appendix, vol. 124, Harvard University Press, 1971.
- [20] E. Ostrom, *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action.*, Cambridge University Press., 1990.
- [21] J. S. Meka and P. Venkateswarlu, "Progress, Challenges, and Strategies towards attaining Sustainable Development Goals.," *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 2145-2161, 2024.
- [22] R. E. Freeman, *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach.*, Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [23] R. K. B. R. A. a. D. J. W. Mitchell, "Toward a theory of stakeholder identification and salience: Defining the principle of who and what really counts.," *Academy of management review*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 853-886, 1997.
- [24] T. a. L. E. P. Donaldson, "The stakeholder theory of the corporation: Concepts, evidence, and implications.," *Academy of management Review*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 65-91, 1995.
- [25] J. a. I. H. R. Elkington, "Cannibals with forks: The triple bottom line of 21st century business.," *Alternatives Journal*, vol. 25, no. 4, p. 42, 1999.
- [26] European Environment Agency, "Sustainability," [Online]. Available: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/at-a-glance/sustainability#:~:text=The%20European%20Green%20Deal%20covers,person%20or%20place%20left%20behind..> [Accessed May 2024].
- [27] European Union, "European Climate Pact," [Online]. Available: https://climate-pact.europa.eu/index_en. [Accessed May 2024].
- [28] Global Reporting Initiative, "<https://www.globalreporting.org/>," [Online]. [Accessed May 2024].
- [29] J. W. a. B. P. Selsky, "Cross-sector partnerships to address social issues: Challenges to theory and practice," *Journal of management*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 849-873, 2005.
- [30] T. Bovaird, "Public-private partnerships: from contested concepts to prevalent practice," *International review of administrative sciences*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 199-215, 2004.
- [31] United Nations, "Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [32] WWF - World Wide Fund For Natur, "EARTH HOUR," [Online]. Available: https://www.wwf.eu/campaigns/earth_hour/. [Accessed May 2024].
- [33] European Environmental Bureau, "EEB Annual Report 2021," 2022.
- [34] Greenpeace, "Annual Report 2022," Greenpeace, 2023.
- [35] Climate Action Network Europe, "Annual Report 2023," Climate Action Network Europe, 2024.
- [36] D. R. Young, "Alternative models of government-nonprofit sector relations: Theoretical and international perspectives," *Nonprofit and voluntary sector quarterly*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 149-172, 2000.
- [37] M. a. D. H. Edwards, "Too close for comfort? The impact of official aid on nongovernmental organizations," *World development*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 961-973, 1996.
- [38] G. A. a. C. G. Hodge, "Public-private partnerships: an international performance review," *Public administration review*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 545-558, 2007.
- [39] E. R. Yescombe, *Public-private partnerships: principles of policy and finance*, Elsevier, 2011.
- [40] J. M. a. D. W. B. Brinkerhoff, "overnment-nonprofit relations in comparative perspective: evolution, themes and new directions," *ublic Administration and Development: The International Journal of Management Research and Practice*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 3-18, 2002.
- [41] A. Najam, "NGO accountability: A conceptual framework," *Development policy review*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 339-354, 1996.

- [42] M. a. D. H. Edwards, "Too close for comfort? The impact of official aid on nongovernmental organizations," *World development*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 961-973, 1996.
- [43] European Climate Foundation Built by 89up, "Financials," [Online]. Available: <https://europeanclimate.org/financials/>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [44] Global Environment Facility, "Funding," [Online]. Available: <https://www.thegef.org/who-we-are/funding>. [Accessed May 2024].
- [45] N. a. D. H. Banks, "The role of NGOs and civil society in development and poverty reduction," *Brooks World Poverty Institute Working Paper*, vol. 171, 2012.
- [46] L. Boncinelli, L. Dallinger and T. Distefano, "SSRN," 21 May 2024. [Online]. Available: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4835203. [Accessed May 2024].
-

APPENDIX 1

European Green Deal (EGD) projects

Table 1 contains an overview of the 73 EGD projects that span diverse initiatives aimed at driving sustainability and addressing climate change through innovative approaches across Europe. These projects tackle issues such as renewable energy, waste management, climate adaptation, and sustainable agriculture. They leverage advanced technologies, stakeholder collaboration, and participatory frameworks to foster social justice, economic resilience, and environmental sustainability. Projects range from upcycling agrifood residues and promoting net-zero emission communities to developing climate adaptation solutions and enhancing air quality monitoring. Collectively, they aim to accelerate the green transition by integrating scientific research, community engagement, and policy support, ensuring a holistic approach to environmental challenges.

Table 1 Overview of EGD Projects

#	Acronym	Website	Short description
1	ACCTING	https://accting.eu/	Research experimentations and innovations to reduce inequalities in EGD policies, focusing on vulnerable groups, co-creating solutions, and empowering stakeholders for social justice. Academic fields: Sociology, Political Science. Economics Economic sectors: Sustainable Economy, Environmental Initiatives, Policy Design
2	Agro2Circular	https://agro2circular.eu/	First territorial systemic solution for upcycling agrifood residues, developing value chains for fruit, vegetable waste, and multilayer plastics, utilizing digital tools for traceability and predictive decision-making. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Agricultural Sciences, Materials Engineering Economic sectors: Agrifood, Waste Management, Sustainable Economy
3	ALTERNATIVE	https://alternative-project.eu	Develops a platform using 3D cardiac tissue models and machine learning to identify and prevent cardiotoxicity from chemical exposures, focusing on older adults and regulatory compliance. Academic fields: Medical Biotechnology, Pharmacology, Cardiology Economic sectors: Pharmaceuticals, Environmental Monitoring, Healthcare
4	ARSINOE	https://arsinoe-project.eu	Develops climate adaptation solutions using Systems Innovation Approach and Climate Innovation Window, creating regional, reusable innovation packages through stakeholder collaboration, demonstrated in nine varied regions. Academic fields: Environmental Sciences, Climatology, Social Innovation Economic sectors: Environmental Technology, Regional Planning, Climate Adaptation
5	ARV	https://greendeal-arv.eu/	Aims to accelerate the adoption of Climate Positive Circular Communities by integrating digital tools, circular economy principles, and simplicity into urban regeneration projects. Academic fields: Digital technology development, Environmental engineering, Sustainable architecture Economic sectors: Construction, Renewable energy, Policy and financial mechanisms
6	AURORA	https://www.aurora-h2020.eu	Engages citizens in sustainable energy practices through citizen science, crowdfunding solar facilities, and monitoring energy behaviors, aiming for near zero-emission communities across five European countries. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Political Science Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Crowdfunding, Civil Society Initiatives
7	Bio-FlexGen	https://bioflexgen.eu	Increases efficiency and flexibility of combined heat and power systems by integrating biomass and renewable hydrogen, contributing to energy system decarbonization and improved energy security. Academic fields: Electrical Engineering, Environmental Engineering, Climatology Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Biomass Energy, Hydrogen Energy
8	CIRCULAR FOAM	https://circular-foam.eu	Demonstrates a cross-sectoral circular solution for upcycling rigid polyurethane foams, transforming waste into new high-performance

			plastics, reducing landfill waste, and promoting climate neutrality. Academic fields: Polymer Sciences, Ecology, Environmental Engineering Economic sectors: Chemical Industry, Waste Management, Construction
9	CityCLIM	https://www.cityclim.eu/	Develops advanced city climate services using enhanced weather models and diverse data sources, focusing on urban climate monitoring and customizable services for European cities. Academic fields: Civil Engineering, Atmospheric Sciences, Environmental Sciences Economic sectors: Smart Cities, Weather Forecasting, Urban Planning
10	ClieNFarms	https://clienfarms.eu	Develops and tests innovative solutions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase carbon sequestration on farms through co-designed case studies, data hubs, and systemic approaches across diverse agricultural systems. Academic fields: Sustainable Agriculture, Environmental Science, Agricultural Economics Economic sectors: Agriculture, Carbon Management, Environmental Consulting
11	COMPAIR	https://www.wecompair.eu	Empowers citizens to monitor and improve air quality using low-cost sensors and data visualization tools, enhancing civic engagement and informing environmental policy in diverse urban areas. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Political Science, Public Administration Economic sectors: Environmental Monitoring, Civic Technology, Public Policy
12	ECF4CLIM	https://www.ecf4clim.net/	Develops and validates a European Competence Framework for climate action through participatory research, empowering educational communities with technical, behavioral, and organizational interventions for sustainability. Academic fields: Environmental Sciences, Education, Social Sciences Economic sectors: Education, Technology, Sustainability Consulting
13	ECO2Fuel	https://eco2fuel-project.eu	Develops a 1MW low-temperature electrochemical system to convert CO ₂ into sustainable liquid fuels using renewable electricity, targeting CO ₂ -heavy sectors like transport and energy. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Electrochemistry, Organic Chemistry Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Transport, Chemical Industry
14	EcoeFISHent	https://ecoefishent.eu	Develops a replicable circular economy cluster for valorizing fish industry side-streams into high-value products, fostering sustainability in food, cosmetics, packaging, and automotive industries. Academic fields: Fisheries, Industrial Biotechnology, Food Technology Economic sectors: Food and Beverage, Cosmetics, Packaging and Automotive
15	ENERGICA	https://energica-h2020.eu/	Fosters EU-Africa collaboration on energy access by developing innovative renewable energy solutions, such as nano-grids, biogas systems, and solar-powered e-mobility, benefiting over 1,500 stakeholders across Africa. Academic fields: Renewable Energy, Chemical Engineering, Climatology Economic sectors: Energy, E-Mobility, Water Purification
16	ENOUGH	https://enough-emissions.eu/	Develops technologies and methods to reduce GHG emissions and increase energy efficiency in the food industry, contributing to climate-neutral food systems by 2050, with broad stakeholder engagement. Academic fields: Environmental Sciences, Agricultural Sciences, Food Technology Economic sectors: Food Production, Energy Efficiency, Supply Chain Management
17	EU-SCORES	https://eurescores.eu/	Develops offshore renewable energy systems combining wind, solar, and wave power to enhance power stability, reduce costs, and support green hydrogen production, demonstrating in Belgium and Portugal. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Renewable Energy, Marine Engineering Economic sectors: Energy Production, Aquaculture, Shipping and Transportation
18	FIRE-RES	https://fire-res.eu	Develops integrated fire management solutions for resilient landscapes and communities by combining technology, policy, and community engagement to address root causes and impacts of extreme wildfire events.

			Academic fields: Governance, Innovation Management, Climatology Economic sectors: Environmental Management, Civil Protection, Technology Development
19	FIRELOGUE	https://firelogue.eu/	Coordinates and supports wildfire risk management by integrating findings from various stakeholders, promoting dialogue, and co-developing strategies through an inclusive and transparent platform. Academic fields: Governance, Crisis Management, Environmental Science Economic sectors: Forestry, Agriculture, Civil Protection
20	FORWARD-2030	https://forward2030.tech/	Accelerates tidal energy deployment by reducing costs, enhancing environmental and societal acceptance, integrating energy systems with battery storage and hydrogen production, and creating tools for monitoring and forecasting. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Renewable Energy, Marine Engineering Economic sectors: Energy Production, Environmental Monitoring, Green Hydrogen Production
21	FRONTSHP	https://frontship.eu/	Ensures the green transition of Poland's Lodzkie Region through circular economy models, engaging local stakeholders, and developing a Circular Economy Action Plan to promote sustainability and decarbonization. Academic fields: Political Science, Sustainable Economy, Environmental Science Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Waste Management, Local Governance
22	GreenH2Atlantic	https://www.greenh2atlantic.com/	Develops and demonstrates a 100 MW alkaline electrolyser using hybrid renewable energy, enhancing green hydrogen production and reducing GHG emissions, supporting multiple end-uses and creating jobs. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Renewable Energy, Electrical Engineering Economic sectors: Hydrogen Production, Renewable Energy, Chemical Industry
23	GreenHyScale	https://www.green-scent.eu/	Develops and tests a European Sustainability Competence Framework through participatory, experience-based learning, involving experts, researchers, and citizens across various educational levels and regions. Academic fields: Political Science, Sustainable Economy, Educational Sciences Economic sectors: Education, Policy Making, Human Resources
24	GreenSCENT	https://www.green-scent.eu/	Develops and tests a European Sustainability Competence Framework using participatory, experience-based learning, involving experts, researchers, and citizens across various educational levels and regions. Academic fields: Political Science, Sustainable Economy, Educational Sciences Economic sectors: Education, Policy Making, Human Resources
25	HYPERGRYD	https://hypergryd.eu/	Develops scalable solutions for integrating renewable energy into thermal and electrical grids, optimizing energy management in district heating and cooling systems, and promoting smart energy networks in local communities. Academic fields: Urban Engineering, Environmental Engineering, Electrical Engineering Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Smart Cities, Power Distribution
26	I-CHANGE	https://ichange-project.eu/	Engages citizens to address climate change and promote sustainable habits through participatory Living Labs, enhancing awareness and involvement in environmental protection and climate action. Academic fields: Ecology, Political Science, Climatology Economic sectors: Environmental Protection, Civil Society, Sustainable Development
27	I-CISK	https://icisk.eu/	Develops next-generation climate services by integrating local knowledge with scientific data through a customizable cloud-based platform, addressing climate impacts in various sectors and regions via Living Labs. Academic fields: Data Science, Political Science, Climatology Economic sectors: Agriculture, Energy, Tourism
28	ILIAD	https://www.ocea.eu/	Develops an interoperable, data-intensive Digital Twin of the Ocean to enhance marine data integration, visualization, and sustainability, supporting the blue economy and climate resilience.

		n-twin.eu/	Academic fields: Oceanography, Data Science, Internet of Things Economic sectors: Marine Economy, Environmental Monitoring, Digital Technology Development
29	IMPETUS	https://climate-impetus.eu/	Develops a comprehensive climate change adaptation framework for resilient regions, engaging stakeholders and integrating reliable data to co-design, assess, and monitor climate adaptation strategies across all EU biogeographical regions. Academic fields: Environmental Science, Data Science, Governance Economic sectors: Climate Adaptation, Sustainable Development, Public Policy
30	LIFESAVER	https://lifesaverproject.eu/	Develops a digital in vitro system to assess the impact of chemicals on fetal health, aiming to improve regulations and maternal care, thereby reducing preterm births and neonatal deaths. Academic fields: Pharmacology, Fetal Medicine, Embryology Economic sectors: Pharmaceuticals, Healthcare, Regulatory Affairs
31	LOCALISED	https://www.localised-project.eu/	Downscales national decarbonization trajectories to local levels, creating tools for authorities, citizens, and businesses to accelerate climate action and achieve net-zero targets. Academic fields: Political Science, Sustainable Economy, Public Administration Economic sectors: Local Government, Business Consulting, Environmental Services
32	MAGPIE	https://www.magpie-ports.eu/	Develops and demonstrates green energy and digital solutions for ports, enhancing efficiency and sustainability through green energy carriers, automation, and multimodal transport in a living lab environment. Academic fields: Environmental Engineering, Automation, Transportation Engineering Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Port and Harbor Operations, Sustainable Transport
33	MERLIN	https://project-merlin.eu/	Demonstrates and upscales nature-based solutions for freshwater ecosystem restoration, driving systemic change and economic growth through collaborations with local communities and economic sectors. Academic fields: Ecology, Sustainable Economy, Environmental Engineering Economic sectors: Agriculture, Water Supply, Insurance
34	NeoGiANT	https://www.neogiant.eu/	Develops natural grape extract-based products to reduce antibiotic use and improve health in farmed animals, utilizing eco-friendly extraction techniques to create antimicrobial and antioxidant feed, treatments, and sperm extenders. Academic fields: Infectious diseases, Pharmacology and drug resistance, Animal husbandry Economic sectors: Agriculture and livestock, Pharmaceutical, Sustainable economy
35	NetZeroCities	https://netzerocities.eu/	Accelerating cities' transition to net-zero emissions by 2030 through tailored support, a one-stop-shop platform, and pilot programs in 30 European cities. Academic fields: Urban engineering, Environmental science, Public policy Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Urban planning, Information technology
36	OLGA	https://www.olga-project.eu/	Achieve efficient, carbon-neutral airport operations, sustainable logistics, smart energy solutions, and biodiversity preservation through integrating sustainable aviation fuels and low-emission technologies. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Transportation engineering, Sustainable architecture Economic sectors: Aviation, Renewable energy, Sustainable construction
37	oPEN Lab	https://openlab-project.eu/	Creating replicable, commercially viable solutions for positive energy neighborhoods, integrating local energy systems and testing technologies in three urban living labs in Europe. Academic fields: Urban engineering, Environmental engineering, Public administration Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Construction, Urban planning
38	PANORAMIX	https://panoramix-h2020.eu/	The project develops a platform for optimizing autonomous and conventional vehicle fleet operations, improving ride-sharing, safety, energy conservation, and emission reductions while facilitating inclusive mobility.

			Academic fields: Automotive engineering, Software engineering, Public transport geography Economic sectors: Transportation, Information technology, Environmental services
39	PAUL	https://www.icos-cp.eu/projects/icos-cities-project	Developing integrated city observatories for greenhouse gases, enhancing urban emission assessments through innovative observation methods, co-designed services, and collaboration with city stakeholders. Academic fields: Urban engineering, Atmospheric sciences, Climatology Economic sectors: Environmental monitoring, Urban planning, Data analytics
40	PestNu	https://pe.stnu.eu/	Field-testing digital and space-based technologies alongside agro-ecological and organic practices to reduce pesticide and fertilizer use, and nutrient loss in greenhouse and open-field vegetable cultivation. Academic fields: Artificial intelligence, Food safety, Horticulture Economic sectors: Agriculture, Digital technologies, Biotechnology
41	PHOENIX	https://phoenix-horizon.eu/project/	Developing and testing democratic innovations to enhance citizen engagement in ecological transitions across Europe, through 11 pilots in 7 countries, fostering readiness for change and commitment. Academic fields: Political science, Public health, Environmental science Economic sectors: Public administration, Community development, Environmental consulting
42	PIONEERS	https://pioneers-ports.eu/	Four European ports will implement green innovations across clean energy, sustainable design, modal shift, and digital transformation to reduce greenhouse gas emissions while maintaining competitiveness. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Transportation engineering, Sustainable transport Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Port and harbor engineering, Logistics and transportation
43	PROBONO	https://www.probonoh2020.eu/	A multidisciplinary consortium will transform six European districts into Green Building Neighbourhoods with positive energy balance and zero carbon emissions, using digital and smart technologies. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Thermodynamic engineering, Computer and information sciences Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Construction, Urban planning
44	PROMISCES	https://promisces.eu/	Identifying industrial pollution barriers to the circular economy, PROMISCES will develop analytical methods and tools to manage and mitigate persistent, mobile substances in soil, sediment, and water. Academic fields: Environmental sciences, Water treatment processes, Sustainable economy Economic sectors: Water treatment, Agriculture, Waste management
45	PSLifestyle	https://pslifestyle.eu/	A digital application engages citizens across eight European countries to co-create and adopt sustainable lifestyles, monitor environmental impacts, and provide data for policy-making. Academic fields: Environmental science, Behavioral science, Political science Economic sectors: Technology, Consumer goods, Public policy
46	PYROCO2	https://www.pyroco2.eu/	The project will demonstrate the scalability and economic viability of converting industrial CO2 into climate-positive acetone using renewable hydrogen and thermophilic microbial processes. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Chemical sciences, Industrial biotechnology Economic sectors: Chemical production, Renewable energy, Industrial decarbonization
47	REACHOUT	https://reachout-cities.eu/	The project advances climate services for urban environments through tailored adaptation strategies in seven City Hubs, integrating resilient urban development with active citizen and private sector engagement. Academic fields: Civil engineering, Political sciences, Atmospheric sciences Economic sectors: Urban development, Climate adaptation services, Private sector engagement
48	REAL_DEAL	https://www.reald-eal.eu/	The project enhances citizen participation in deliberative processes for environmental governance, developing and testing innovative tools and formats for inclusive democracy in 13 European countries. Academic fields: Political sciences, Sociology, Law Economic sectors: Environmental governance, Civic engagement, Sustainable development

49	REFLECT AFRICA	https://www.reflect-africa.eu/	Innovative sustainable energy solutions in Africa through biomass waste valorization for on-grid and off-grid communities using biomass gasification, addressing climate adaptation and mitigation, and providing biochar fertilizers. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Public health, Agricultural sciences Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Agriculture, Circular economy
50	REFHYNE II	https://www.refhyne.eu/refhyne-2/	A 100MW PEM electrolyser will be installed in Cologne, Germany, using renewable power to produce green hydrogen and oxygen, decarbonizing refinery operations and improving efficiency while reducing costs. Academic fields: Chemical sciences, Electrochemistry, Renewable energy Economic sectors: Energy production, Chemical industry, Refinery operations
51	REGILIENCE	https://regilience.eu/	The project enhances regional climate resilience in 50 vulnerable EU regions, disseminating solutions, coordinating surveys, and fostering synergies across networks with over 700 activities. Academic fields: Political sciences, Atmospheric sciences, Sustainable economy Economic sectors: Climate adaptation, Regional development, Public policy
52	REST-COAST	https://rest-coast.eu/	The project demonstrates large-scale coastal restoration for low-carbon adaptation, risk reduction, and biodiversity gains in vulnerable ecosystems, overcoming barriers in governance, economics, and social structures. Academic fields: Earth and environmental sciences, Sociology/governance, Biological sciences/ecology Economic sectors: Fisheries, Sustainable economy, Climate adaptation and mitigation
53	RESTORE	https://www.restore-dhc.eu/	An innovative solution for district heating and cooling integrates thermochemical energy storage and organic Rankine cycle technologies to enable 100% renewable energy utilization and significantly improve environmental sustainability. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Energy and fuels, Thermochemical technology Economic sectors: Renewable energy, District heating and cooling, Waste heat recovery
54	RethinkAction	https://rethinkaction.eu/	A cross-sectoral platform engages citizens and decision-makers in climate action through land use-based solutions, enhancing awareness and decision-making for climate change mitigation and adaptation. Academic fields: Political sciences, Atmospheric sciences, Climatology Economic sectors: Land management, Environmental policy, Climate change mitigation
55	RI-URBANS	https://riurbans.eu/	Develops advanced air quality monitoring tools for urban and industrial areas, enhancing networks to evaluate and predict air pollution sources, constituents, and health effects, supporting policy and decision-making. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Environmental sciences, Nanotechnology Economic sectors: Urban planning, Environmental monitoring, Public health
56	SCENARIOS	https://scenarios-project.eu/	Develops technological solutions for detecting, monitoring, assessing, and remediating PFAS contamination, aiming for self-sustainable, near net-zero energy integration into circular economies. Academic fields: Environmental sciences, Health sciences, Economics Economic sectors: Environmental monitoring, Public health, Sustainable economy
57	SchoolFood4Change	https://schoolfood4change.eu/	Summary: SchoolFood4Change aims to shift EU school diets to sustainability, impacting over 3,000 schools and 600,000 children. It emphasizes sustainable food procurement, cooking education, and holistic dietary culture. Academic fields: Public health, Nutrition, Medical and health sciences Economic sectors: Public health, Education, Food industry
58	SESA	https://sesa-	Facilitates co-development and replication of innovative energy access solutions in Africa, with demonstrations in living labs and scalable business opportunities for local entrepreneurs.

		euafrica.eu/	Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Innovation management, Entrepreneurship Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Business development, Technology integration
59	SHARED GREEN DEAL	https://sharedgreendeal.eu/	The project unites 22 EU organizations to foster societal change through social experiments, focusing on democracy, energy, gender, and circular economy to support climate action and inclusivity. Academic fields: Sociology, Gender studies, Political sciences Economic sectors: Renewable energy, Circular economy, Public policy
60	SILVANUS	https://silvanus-project.eu/	The project aims to deliver a climate-resilient forest management platform to prevent and combat forest fires, utilizing advanced technologies, big data, and interdisciplinary collaboration for effective wildfire management. Academic fields: Environmental sciences, Forestry, Sociology Economic sectors: Utilities, Insurance, Forestry management
61	SISTERS	https://sistersproject.eu/	The project aims to reduce food loss and waste across the entire food value chain through innovative solutions like smart containers, bio-based packaging, and a short-chain platform for farmers. Academic fields: Agricultural sciences, Environmental engineering, Sociology Economic sectors: Agriculture, Food processing, Retail
62	SOCIO-BEE	https://socio-bee.eu/	The project uses community engagement, citizen science, and emerging technologies like drones and wearables to promote sustainable behaviors and reduce urban air pollution through scalable, low-cost innovations. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Electronic engineering, Political sciences Economic sectors: Technology, Public health, Environmental services
63	SophiA	https://sophia4africa.eu/	The project provides off-grid, carbon-neutral electricity, heating, cooling, and clean water to rural African health facilities, enhancing quality of life and supporting sustainable development and economic growth. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Renewable energy, Mechanical engineering Economic sectors: Healthcare, Renewable energy, Water treatment
64	STARGATE	https://www.greendealstargate.eu/	A consortium led by Brussels Airport will create green airports as multimodal hubs for sustainable mobility, focusing on digital twin technology, terminal optimization, and sustainable aviation fuels. Academic fields: Transportation engineering, Sustainable transport, Environmental engineering Economic sectors: Aviation, Renewable energy, Logistics
65	SteamBioAfrica	https://www.steambioafrica.com/	Converting invasive bush into biofuel and water, SteamBioAfrica addresses environmental damage, energy security, and rural economic development through superheated steam processing in Southern Africa. Academic fields: Renewable energy, Climatology, Biomass Economic sectors: Energy, Agriculture, Environmental management
66	StoRIES	https://www.storiesproject.eu/	Improving economic performance and competitiveness of energy storage technologies by fostering a European research and industry ecosystem, focusing on hybrid systems, material optimization, and cost reduction. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Materials science, Energy systems engineering Economic sectors: Energy, Research and development, Manufacturing
67	SUPERB	https://forest-restoration.eu/	Enabling large-scale forest restoration, enhancing biodiversity, ecosystem services, and carbon sequestration through multidisciplinary knowledge, best practices, and stakeholder engagement across Europe. Academic fields: Ecology, Environmental science, Forestry Economic sectors: Environmental management, Forestry, Conservation
68	TransformAr	https://transformar.eu/	Developing and demonstrating products and services for large-scale transformational adaptation to water-related climate risks in vulnerable European regions through innovation packages and adaptive solutions. Academic fields: Climatology, Governance, Environmental science Economic sectors: Water resources management, Climate adaptation technology, Environmental consulting
69	TREEADS	https://treeads-	Developing a holistic fire management system integrating advanced technologies for prevention, detection, and restoration of wildfire-affected areas, with real-time risk evaluation, drones, AI, and post-fire

		project.eu/	restoration techniques. Academic fields: Environmental science, Robotics, Crisis management Economic sectors: Forestry, Insurance, Technology development and manufacturing
70	TULIPS	https://tulips-greenairports.eu/	Demonstrating sustainable technologies for climate-neutral aviation, including green energy, multimodal transport, hydrogen fuel cells, and sustainable aviation fuel, across multiple European airports to reduce emissions and improve air quality. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Transportation engineering, Aerospace engineering Economic sectors: Aviation, Renewable energy, Transportation logistics
71	WaterLANDS	https://waterlands.eu/	Enables large-scale wetland restoration by overcoming socio-economic, engagement, governance, funding, and knowledge barriers through co-design with communities and stakeholders, promoting sustainable best practices. Academic fields: Ecology, Environmental Science, Socioeconomics Economic sectors: Renewable Energy, Water Management, Resource Management
72	ZeroPM	https://zeropm.eu/	Developing and implementing strategies to prevent, prioritize, and remove persistent, mobile substances from the environment, enhancing policy, market incentives, and next-generation remediation techniques for a toxic-free environment. Academic fields: Environmental engineering, Hydrology, Environmental sciences Economic sectors: Water treatment, Chemicals, Environmental policy and regulation
73	ZeroW	https://www.zerow-project.eu/	The project aims to halve food loss and waste by 2030 and reach near-zero by 2050 through systemic innovations in real-life food chains, enhancing collaboration and innovation advancement. Academic fields: Agricultural sciences, Environmental sciences, Social sciences Economic sectors: Agriculture, Food and beverage industry, Waste management

CONSORTIUM ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES IN EGD PROJECTS

When establishing a grant consortium for EGD projects, it is crucial to assign roles based on the level of participation to ensure effective collaboration and the achievement of project objectives.

- **Coordinator:** The Coordinator holds the central role in managing the project. Responsibilities include submitting reports and deliverables and acting as the intermediary for all contacts with the EU Granting Authority. The Coordinator ensures that the project progresses according to the plan and that all administrative requirements are met.
- **Participants:** Participants are the primary entities responsible for executing substantial parts of the project. Each Participant must implement their specific tasks and contribute to the overall grant administration, which includes preparing the grant documentation and reporting on progress. They are directly funded by the EU and are integral to the project's success.
- **Third Parties:** Third Parties provide additional support and resources necessary for the project but do not receive direct funding from the EU; instead, their funding is cascaded from the Coordinator or Participants. They can include organizations that offer in-kind contributions, associated partners, and subcontractors. Third Parties enhance the consortium's capabilities by supplying expertise, services, or goods that Participants may lack.

All consortium participants are jointly responsible for implementing the project activities as per the agreed proposal or description of action. If the project is not completed or is poorly implemented, the grant funding may be reduced for all participants, emphasizing the importance of collaborative effort and effective project management.

PROJECT CLASSIFICATION

A comprehensive database was created detailed fields including Acronym, Full Name, Summary, Duration, Contact Email, Project Website, Cordis Website, Program, Funded Under, Project ID, Total Cost, Total EU Contribution, Start Date, End Date, Project Description, Objectives, Keywords, Fields of Science, and Short Description.

- **Acronym†:** A short, unique identifier for the project (e.g., ACCTING).
- **Full Name*:** The complete title of the project (e.g., Advancing Behavioral Change Through an Inclusive EGD).
- **Summary†:** A brief overview of the project's objectives and scope.
- **Duration†:** The total time span of the project from start to end date.
- **Contact Email†:** The email address for contacting the project coordinators.
- **Project Website†:** The official website of the project.
- **Cordis Website*:** The project's page on the CORDIS database for additional details.
- **Program*:** The funding program under which the project falls (e.g., H2020).
- **Funded Under*:** Specific calls or initiatives the project was funded under (e.g., SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Climate action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials).
- **Project ID*:** The unique identifier assigned to the project by the funding body.
- **Total Cost*:** The overall budget allocated to the project.
- **Total EU Contribution*:** The amount of funding provided by the European Union.
- **Start Date*:** The date when the project began.
- **End Date*:** The date when the project is scheduled to be completed.
- **Project Description*:** A detailed description of the project's aims, methods, and expected outcomes.
- **Objectives*:** Specific goals the project intends to achieve.
- **Keywords*:** Key terms associated with the project to facilitate searches and categorization.
- **Fields of Science*:** Academic disciplines relevant to the project.
- **Short Description:** A concise summary of the project.
- **Matching Academic Category:** The specific academic and economic categories the project fits into.
- **Overarching Academic Category:** The broader academic category the project belongs to (e.g., Social Sciences and Governance).
- **Economic Category:** The specific economic focus of the project (e.g., Sustainable Economy).
- **Overarching Economic Category:** The broader economic category the project fits into (e.g., Environmental Sustainability).

The fields marked with a † were extracted from the [list of project descriptions](#)¹ and those ones * were extracted from the [CORDIS](#)². The field of the “Short Description” was generated using a Natural Language Processing (NLP) assistant feeding the long description extracted from CORIDS and requesting a short summary, three academic classifications and three economic sector classifications. The further classification into the Academic and Economic Categories was performed manually following the best match.

ACADEMIC CATEGORIES AND OVERARCHING CATEGORIES

Initially, we classified the projects into 20 academic categories:

1. **Agricultural Sciences:** Projects focusing on sustainable agriculture, food technology, and reducing agricultural waste.
2. **Biotechnology:** Projects in industrial biotechnology, bio-based product development, and ecosystem services.
3. **Climatology:** Projects focused on climate adaptation, greenhouse gas monitoring, and climate resilience.
4. **Crisis and Disaster Management:** Projects on crisis management, disaster resilience, and integrated fire management.
5. **Data Science and AI:** Projects using data integration, AI, and digital tools for monitoring and decision-making.
6. **Economics and Sustainable Economy:** Projects focusing on economic models, circular economy, and financial mechanisms supporting sustainability.
7. **Education and Communication:** Projects encompassing educational frameworks, citizen science, and behavioral change initiatives.
8. **Engineering (General):** Projects including civil, electrical, mechanical, and transportation engineering.
9. **Environmental Engineering:** Projects focusing on engineering solutions for environmental protection and sustainability.
10. **Environmental Sciences:** Projects encompassing various aspects of environmental engineering, sustainability, and climate adaptation.
11. **Governance and Law:** Projects including governance frameworks, legal aspects, and regulatory compliance for environmental and social justice.
12. **Innovation and Entrepreneurship:** Projects covering innovation management and entrepreneurial initiatives in sustainable technologies and practices.
13. **Marine and Ocean Sciences:** Projects related to marine ecology, oceanography, and coastal restoration.
14. **Materials Science:** Projects dealing with new materials, recycling, and upcycling of waste materials.
15. **Medical and Health Sciences:** Projects focusing on biotechnology, pharmacology, and healthcare-related innovations.
16. **Political Science:** Projects dealing with policy design, governance, and societal transitions towards sustainability.
17. **Renewable Energy:** Projects focusing on solar, wind, hydrogen, and other renewable energy sources and technologies.
18. **Social Sciences:** Projects including sociology, public administration, and community engagement efforts.
19. **Urban Planning and Development:** Projects aimed at smart cities, urban climate services, and sustainable urban development.
20. **Water Resources Management:** Projects focused on water treatment, hydrology, and sustainable water use in agriculture and industry.

These categories were then consolidated into five overarching academic categories:

1. **Environmental and Earth Sciences:** Includes Climatology, Marine and Ocean Sciences, Water Resources Management, and Environmental Sciences.

¹ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/environment-and-climate/european-green-deal/green-deal-projects-support/green-deal-projects-interactive-map/projects>

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/search/en>

2. **Engineering and Technology:** Encompasses Renewable Energy, Environmental Engineering, Materials Science, Data Science and AI, Biotechnology, and General Engineering.
 3. **Social Sciences and Governance:** Includes Political Science, Social Sciences, Governance and Law, Economics and Sustainable Economy, and Education and Communication.
 4. **Health and Medical Sciences:** Includes Medical and Health Sciences, and Biotechnology.
 5. **Agricultural and Food Sciences:** Includes Agricultural Sciences and Food Technology.
- Table 2 presents the matches the initial academic categories with their overarching categories.

Table 2 Match of the initial academic categories with their overarching categories

Overarching Academic Category	Academic Category
Agricultural and Food Sciences	Agricultural Sciences
Engineering and Technology	Data Science and AI
Engineering and Technology	Engineering (General)
Engineering and Technology	Environmental Engineering
Engineering and Technology	Materials Science
Engineering and Technology	Renewable Energy
Environmental and Earth Sciences	Climatology
Environmental and Earth Sciences	Crisis and Disaster Management
Environmental and Earth Sciences	Environmental Sciences
Environmental and Earth Sciences	Marine and Ocean Sciences
Environmental and Earth Sciences	Water Resources Management
Health and Medical Sciences	Biotechnology
Health and Medical Sciences	Medical and Health Sciences
Social Sciences and Governance	Economics and Sustainable Economy
Social Sciences and Governance	Education and Communication
Social Sciences and Governance	Governance and Law
Social Sciences and Governance	Innovation and Entrepreneurship
Social Sciences and Governance	Political Science
Social Sciences and Governance	Social Sciences
Social Sciences and Governance	Urban Planning and Development

ECONOMIC CATEGORIES AND OVERARCHING ECONOMIC CATEGORIES

Initially, we classified the projects into 20 economic sectors:

1. **Sustainable Economy:** Focuses on economic models and practices that promote environmental sustainability and social equity.
2. **Waste Management:** Involves the collection, transportation, processing, and recycling of waste materials.
3. **Renewable Energy:** Includes the development and implementation of energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydrogen.
4. **Environmental Technology:** Encompasses technologies designed to protect the environment and reduce pollution.
5. **Agrifood:** Covers the entire food production chain, from agriculture to food processing and packaging.
6. **Healthcare:** Involves the provision of medical services, pharmaceuticals, and medical technology.
7. **Civil Society Initiatives:** Includes projects that engage and empower citizens in societal and environmental issues.
8. **Climate Adaptation:** Focuses on developing strategies and solutions to adapt to climate change impacts.
9. **Environmental Monitoring:** Involves the systematic observation and analysis of environmental conditions.
10. **Education:** Includes formal and informal education systems, curriculum development, and educational technology.
11. **Technology Development:** Covers the research, development, and implementation of new technologies across various fields.
12. **Policy Design and Governance:** Encompasses the creation of policies and governance frameworks to address societal challenges.
13. **Smart Cities:** Involves the integration of technology and data to improve urban living and sustainability.
14. **Carbon Management:** Focuses on reducing carbon emissions and managing carbon footprints.

15. **Water Management:** Involves the sustainable management and treatment of water resources.
16. **Circular Economy:** Promotes the reuse and recycling of materials to create a closed-loop system, minimizing waste.
17. **Public Health:** Covers the protection and improvement of community health and well-being.
18. **Innovation and Entrepreneurship:** Involves the creation and growth of new business ventures and innovative solutions.
19. **Transportation and Logistics:** Includes the movement of goods and people, focusing on efficiency and sustainability.
20. **Forestry and Land Management:** Encompasses the management and conservation of forest resources and land.

These categories were then consolidated into five overarching economic categories:

1. **Environmental Sustainability:** Focuses on sustainable practices and technologies that promote environmental protection and resource conservation.
2. **Energy and Resource Management:** Encompasses the development, implementation, and management of energy resources and waste materials.
3. **Societal Development and Governance:** Includes initiatives related to public health, education, policy design, and governance frameworks.
4. **Technology and Innovation:** Covers the advancement and application of new technologies and innovative solutions across various sectors.
5. **Infrastructure and Urban Development:** Involves the planning and development of sustainable cities, transportation systems, and urban infrastructure.

Table 2 shows the matches the initial economic categories with their overarching categories:

Table 3 Match of the initial economic categories with their overarching categories

Overarching Economic Category	Economic Category
Energy and Resource Management	Waste Management
Energy and Resource Management	Renewable Energy
Energy and Resource Management	Water Management
Environmental Sustainability	Sustainable Economy
Environmental Sustainability	Agrifood
Environmental Sustainability	Climate Adaptation
Environmental Sustainability	Environmental Monitoring
Environmental Sustainability	Carbon Management
Environmental Sustainability	Circular Economy
Environmental Sustainability	Forestry and Land Management
Infrastructure and Urban Development	Smart Cities
Infrastructure and Urban Development	Transportation and Logistics
Societal Development and Governance	Healthcare
Societal Development and Governance	Civil Society Initiatives
Societal Development and Governance	Education
Societal Development and Governance	Policy Design and Governance
Societal Development and Governance	Public Health
Technology and Innovation	Environmental Technology
Technology and Innovation	Technology Development
Technology and Innovation	Innovation and Entrepreneurship

LIMITATIONS OF PROJECT CLASSIFICATION IN EGD DATABASE

The classification system for EGD projects, while comprehensive and systematic, is subject to several limitations due to the integration of manual processes and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools. These limitations, despite efforts to minimize them through repeated checks and expert involvement, can introduce potential inaccuracies. Below is an academic discussion of these limitations:

- **Subjectivity in Manual Classification:** Manual classification involves subjective decisions, which can lead to inconsistencies. Different experts may interpret project descriptions and objectives differently, especially when categorizing nuanced or interdisciplinary projects. This subjectivity can affect the uniformity of the classification, even when guidelines are strictly followed.
- **Human Error:** The involvement of humans in data processing and classification is prone to errors. Despite multiple checks, there remains a risk of inaccuracies in data entry, categorization, and

interpretation. For instance, similar projects might be classified differently by different individuals due to oversight or misunderstanding.

- **Limitations of NLP Tools:** NLP tools used to generate summaries and classifications can sometimes misinterpret the context or nuances in project descriptions. While NLP technology has advanced significantly, it is not infallible and can produce erroneous or overly simplistic summaries. This limitation can lead to misclassification if the generated summaries do not accurately reflect the project's scope and objectives.
- **Language and Translation Issues:** Projects described in multiple languages require accurate translation to ensure consistent classification. Misinterpretations during translation can lead to incorrect categorization. Additionally, regional terminologies and idiomatic expressions may not translate directly, causing potential misunderstandings.
- **Ambiguities in Project Descriptions:** Project descriptions can be ambiguous, especially when projects span multiple disciplines or sectors. Determining the primary focus of a project can be challenging and subjective. For example, a project involving both renewable energy and climate adaptation may be difficult to categorize under a single economic or academic category.
- **Dynamic Nature of Projects:** Projects often evolve over their lifecycle, potentially changing focus, scope, or objectives. A classification made at the project's outset may become outdated as the project progresses. Continuous updates are necessary to maintain accuracy, but this can be resource-intensive and may not always be feasible.
- **Granularity and Overlap of Categories:** The detailed classification into 20 academic and 20 economic categories, consolidated into overarching categories, can lead to overlaps. For example, the category "Environmental Technology" under "Technology and Innovation" might overlap with "Environmental Monitoring" under "Environmental Sustainability." This overlap can cause confusion and inconsistencies in categorization.
- **Dependence on Source Data Quality:** The accuracy of classification is highly dependent on the quality and completeness of the source data from the CORDIS database and project websites. Incomplete or inaccurately described projects can lead to misclassification. Additionally, discrepancies between the CORDIS data and project-specific details can introduce inconsistencies.
- **Limited External Validation:** While the database relies on reputable sources and expert reviews, external validation through third-party audits or cross-referencing with other databases is limited. Independent verification could enhance accuracy but is often constrained by resource and time limitations.
- **Complexity in Matching Academic and Economic Categories:** Matching projects to specific academic and economic categories, especially when projects are interdisciplinary, can be complex. Projects that cover multiple categories might be forced into a single category, oversimplifying their scope and potentially misrepresenting their objectives.

The classification system for EGD projects, despite its thorough design and expert involvement, faces inherent limitations due to the integration of manual processes and NLP tools. These limitations include subjectivity, human error, language issues, ambiguities in project descriptions, and the dynamic nature of projects.

PARTNER CLASSIFICATION

We constructed a comprehensive database to classify and analyze the participants of the EGD projects. Using detailed information from the CORDIS database, we included fields such as:

- **Project:** The name of the project. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Partner Name in Country's Native Language:** The name of the partner organization in its native language. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Partner Name in English:** The English translation of the partner organization's name. *Source:* Inferred from the CORDIS database.
- **Country:** The country where the partner organization is based. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Acronym:** A short identifier for the partner organization. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Country Acronym:** The acronym representing the country of the partner organization. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Full Acronym:** A unique identifier for the partner organization constructed using two fields: "Acronym" and the "Country Acronym". *Source:* Data processing.
- **Role in the Project:** The specific role of the partner organization in the project (e.g., Coordinator, Participant). *Source:* CORDIS database.

- **Primary Partner Acronym:** The acronym of the primary partner, if the organization is a third party. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Net EU Funding:** The amount of funding provided by the European Union to the partner organization. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Total Cost:** The overall budget allocated to the partner organization. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Region Name in Native Language:** The region where the partner organization is located, in the native language. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Region Name in English:** The English translation of the region's name. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **SME:** Indicates whether the partner organization is a Small or Medium-sized Enterprise (Yes/No). *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Website:** The official website of the partner organization. *Source:* Collected from the organization's website.
- **Overarching Category - Activity Type:** A high-level classification of the partner organization's activities. *Source:* CORDIS database.
- **Activity Type:** The specific type of activity the partner organization is involved in. *Source:* Manual classification based on all information, as explained below.
- **Main Activities:** A brief description of the primary activities of the partner organization. *Source:* Collected from the organization's website or other resources on internet.
- **Non-Profit Status:** Indicates whether the partner organization is a non-profit (Yes/No). *Source:* Collected from the organization's website or other resources on internet.
- **NGO/Association Status:** Indicates whether the partner organization is an NGO, association, federation, or similar type (Yes/No). *Source:* Collected from the organization's website or other resources on internet.
- **Overarching Group - Org Type:** A high-level classification of the type of organization (e.g., Governmental Bodies, Private Sector Entities). *Source:* Manual classification based on all information, as explained below.
- **Org Type:** A more specific classification of the type of organization (e.g., Foundation, University, Company). *Source:* Manual classification as explained below.
- **Major Category - Sector:** A high-level classification of the economic sector the organization operates in (e.g., Energy and Environmental Solutions). *Source:* Manual classification based on all information, as explained below.
- **Category - Sector:** A specific classification of the economic sector (e.g., Technology and Innovation). *Source:* Manual classification based on all information, as explained below.
- **Sector:** The detailed economic sector of the partner organization (e.g., Science & Research, Education & Research). *Source:* Manual classification based on all information, as explained below.

Further explanations on the key-categories is shown below.

ORGANIZATION AND ACTIVITY TYPE CLASSIFICATION

For further classification, we considered the main activities of the organizations and identified 59 distinct activity types, with a detailed focus on NPOs.

These activity types were then matched with overarching organizational categories, similar to those used by CORDIS:

1. **Governmental Bodies:** Organizations that operate at various government levels and are responsible for implementing laws, regulations, and policies. Examples include Government, Government Agency, Government Ministry, and Public Body.
2. **Private Sector Entities:** Privately owned, for-profit organizations varying in size and industry. Examples include Private Company, Private for-profit entities, and GmbH.
3. **Educational and Research Institutions:** Organizations focused on providing education and conducting research, ranging from primary schools to specialized institutes. Examples include University, Research Institute, and Higher Education Institution.
4. **Non-Profit Organizations:** Organizations that operate for purposes other than profit, focusing on social, educational, charitable, or environmental goals. Examples include Charities, NGOs, and Social Enterprises.
5. **International Organizations:** Organizations that operate across multiple countries, often focusing on global issues such as trade, health, and development. Examples include the United Nations and the World Health Organization.

The detailed matching is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Match of the Activity types with the matches the initial economic categories with their overarching categories
Overarching Activity Types

Activity Type	Overarching Group - Org Type
Education Organisation	Educational and Research Institutions
Education/Research Organisation	Educational and Research Institutions
Higher Education	Educational and Research Institutions
Higher Education Establishment	Educational and Research Institutions
Higher Education Institution	Educational and Research Institutions
Higher or Secondary Education Establishment	Educational and Research Institutions
Public Research Organisation	Educational and Research Institutions
Research Institute	Educational and Research Institutions
Research Institution	Educational and Research Institutions
Research Organisation	Educational and Research Institutions
University	Educational and Research Institutions
University Department	Educational and Research Institutions
University of Applied Sciences	Educational and Research Institutions
Public bodies	Governmental Bodies
Government	Governmental Bodies
Government Agency	Governmental Bodies
Government Ministry	Governmental Bodies
Governmental Agency	Governmental Bodies
Governmental Department	Governmental Bodies
Governmental organisation	Governmental Bodies
Public Body	Governmental Bodies
Public Organisation	Governmental Bodies
Public Utility	Governmental Bodies
Intergovernmental network	International Organization
International Organization	International Organization
Non-Profit Organisation	Non-Profit Organisation
Association	Non-Profit Organisation
Federation	Non-Profit Organisation
Charity	Non-Profit Organisation
Confederation	Non-Profit Organisation
Consortium	Non-Profit Organisation
Think tank	Non-Profit Organisation
Union	Non-Profit Organisation
Cooperative	Non-Profit Organisation
Foundation	Non-Profit Organisation
Company	Private Sector Entities
Corporation	Private Sector Entities
GmbH	Private Sector Entities
Private Company	Private Sector Entities
Private for-profit entities	Private Sector Entities
Private Organisation	Private Sector Entities
Public Company	Private Sector Entities
Transport consulting firm	Private Sector Entities

CLASSIFICATION AND EXAMPLES OF NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS IN EGD PROJECTS

For our analysis of the non-profit organizations participating in the EGD projects, we classified them into ten distinct activity types. This classification helps to understand the varied roles these organizations play in supporting and implementing EGD initiatives.

1. **Association:** A group of people or organizations united for a common purpose or activity. Examples include [ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH](#) (Local government sustainability initiatives) and [Asociación Empresarial de Investigación Centro Tecnológico del Calzado y del Plástico de la Región de Murcia](#) (Technology and innovation in footwear and plastics).
2. **Charity:** An organization set up to provide help and raise money for those in need. Examples include [Westcountry Rivers Trust LBG](#) (Environmental Conservation) and [The Scottish Wildlife Trust LBG](#) (Wildlife conservation and environmental education).

3. **Confederation:** A union of organizations or groups united for a common purpose. An example is the [Lithuanian Confederation of Industrialists](#) (Industrial and employer advocacy).
4. **Consortium:** An association of several companies or organizations formed to undertake an enterprise beyond the resources of any one member. Examples include [Tecnoalimenti SCPA](#) (Food technology research) and [Open Geospatial Consortium Europe](#) (Development of geospatial and open-source software standards).
5. **Cooperative:** An organization owned and operated by its members for their mutual benefit. Examples include [Cooperativa Sociale Il Rastrello Società Cooperativa a Responsabilità Limitata - ONLUS](#) (Social Cooperative).
6. **Federation:** A group of organizations, each of which retains control of its own activities but agrees to act together for a common purpose. Examples include [International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements EU Regional Group](#) (Organic Agriculture Advocacy) and European Environmental Bureau (Environmental Protection Advocacy).
7. **Foundation:** An institution established with an endowment, dedicated to funding and supporting initiatives in a specific area. Examples include [European Science Foundation](#) (Scientific research funding) and [Fundación Primafrío](#) (Logistics and transportation research).
8. **Non-Profit Organisation:** Used for those entities that could not be specifically classified into the above categories. Examples include [Pompiers De L'urgence Internationale](#) (Public Safety and Emergency Services).
9. **Think Tank:** A research institute or organization dedicated to studying and providing advice on social, economic, political, or environmental issues. Examples include [Collaborating Centre On Sustainable Consumption And Production GGMBH](#) (Research on sustainable consumption and production) and [Den Institute](#).
10. **Union:** An organized association of workers or groups formed to protect and further their rights and interests. An example is [Enosi Katanaloton Poioitita Tis Zois](#) (Consumer rights and quality of life improvement).

ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES CLASSIFICATION

We classified the partners in the projects based on their economic activities, inferred from their websites and other information sources. Initially, we identified 531 distinct entries for sector descriptions, which were then categorized into 30 sectors and further consolidated into 15 major categories.

The 30 initial categories include:

1. **Aerospace and Aviation:** Includes all aerospace, defense, aviation services, and related technologies.
2. **Agriculture and Food Production:** Encompasses agriculture, agri-food, organic farming, food production, and food technology.
3. **Biotechnology and Biochemical Research:** Includes biotech, biological sciences, and all biochemical research areas.
4. **Business and Consulting Services:** Covers business development, consulting in various sectors, and business services.
5. **Climate and Environmental Sciences:** Encompasses climate change, environmental advocacy, and environmental sciences.
6. **Construction and Engineering:** Includes all fields related to construction, civil engineering, and architecture.
7. **Consumer Goods and Services:** Encompasses industries involved in producing and providing consumer goods and services.
8. **Education and Training:** Covers all educational fields, training services, and educational research.
9. **Energy and Power Systems:** Includes energy production, sustainability in energy, and energy technologies.
10. **Engineering and Technology:** General engineering, technology development, and applied sciences.
11. **Environmental and Sustainability Consulting:** Consulting services focused on the environment and sustainability.
12. **Finance and Insurance:** Financial services, insurance, and related fields like real estate.
13. **Food Science and Nutrition:** Encompasses food science, nutrition, and food quality research.
14. **Forestry and Natural Resources:** Includes forestry, conservation, and related natural resource management.
15. **Government and Public Services:** Government operations, municipal services, and public administration.

16. **Health and Medical Sciences:** Covers healthcare, medical research, and health-related services.
17. **Information and Communication Technology:** ICT, software services, and digital services.
18. **Manufacturing and Industrial Services:** Includes all aspects of manufacturing and industrial sector services.
19. **Marine and Oceanography:** Marine research, oceanography, and related maritime fields.
20. **Marketing and Media Communications:** Media, marketing, and communication services.
21. **Materials Science and Engineering:** Materials research, chemical engineering, and materials technology.
22. **Public Safety and Emergency Services:** Emergency management, safety technologies, and firefighting.
23. **Research and Development:** Multidisciplinary research, scientific research, and innovation.
24. **Social Sciences and Humanities:** Social sciences, cultural studies, and humanities research.
25. **Sustainability and Environmental Policy:** Policy-making related to sustainability and environmental protection.
26. **Technology and Innovation:** Broad tech innovation, technology services, and high-tech industries.
27. **Telecommunications:** Telecommunication services and technologies.
28. **Transportation and Logistics:** Transport planning, logistics, and related infrastructure.
29. **Urban Planning and Development:** Urban development, city planning, and sustainable urban practices.
30. **Water Management and Treatment:** Water sector services, water management, and treatment technologies.

The 15 major categories are the following:

1. **Aerospace, Defense, and Aviation:** Includes industries and services related to aircraft, spacecraft, defense technologies, and aviation services. This encompasses design, manufacturing, and operations in aerospace and defense sectors.
2. **Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources:** Covers all aspects of agriculture, from farming and agri-food production to organic practices and sustainable natural resource management. Includes food technology and the production of consumables.
3. **Biotechnology and Life Sciences:** Encompasses fields that combine biological and technological processes to develop new practices and products. This includes genetic research, pharmaceuticals, and healthcare innovations.
4. **Business, Finance, and Consulting:** Involves sectors providing business management, financial services, and consulting in various areas such as strategy, planning, and operational improvements.
5. **Construction, Engineering, and Architecture:** Includes the design, construction, and maintenance of buildings and infrastructure. This field combines civil engineering, architecture, and construction management.
6. **Education and Research:** Covers all educational services, institutions, and research activities. This includes schools, universities, and dedicated research facilities conducting multidisciplinary studies.
7. **Energy and Environmental Solutions:** Focuses on energy production (traditional and renewable), environmental protection, and the development of technologies to sustain natural resources and energy efficiency.
8. **Health and Medical Services:** Encompasses the healthcare industry, medical research, and the provision of health services, including hospitals, clinics, and medical research facilities.
9. **Industry and Manufacturing:** Includes all aspects of industrial production and manufacturing processes, from design to machinery, and the output of goods.
10. **Information, Communication, and Technology:** Covers technologies in information processing, software, and communication systems, including IT services, software development, and telecommunications.
11. **Public Services and Government:** Involves government operations, public administration, and the delivery of civic services to the community.
12. **Safety, Emergency, and Security:** Focuses on public safety, emergency management, and security services, including firefighting, police work, and disaster response.
13. **Science, Technology, and Innovation:** A broad category encompassing scientific research, technological development, and innovative processes across various fields, aiming to advance knowledge and application.
14. **Transportation and Urban Development:** Involves the planning, management, and development of transportation systems and urban areas, focusing on sustainable growth and infrastructure improvements.

15. **Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies:** Covers the media industry, marketing strategies, and the study of cultural phenomena. This includes advertising, public relations, and media production.

The detailed matching is presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Match of the 30 Economic Categories with the 15 Overarching Economic Categories

Major Category	Category
Aerospace, Defense, and Aviation	Aerospace and Aviation
Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources	Agriculture and Food Production
Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources	Food Science and Nutrition
Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources	Forestry and Natural Resources
Biotechnology and Life Sciences	Biotechnology and Biochemical Research
Business, Finance, and Consulting	Business and Consulting Services
Business, Finance, and Consulting	Finance and Insurance
Construction, Engineering, and Architecture	Construction and Engineering
Education and Research	Education and Training
Education and Research	Research and Development
Energy and Environmental Solutions	Climate and Environmental Sciences
Energy and Environmental Solutions	Energy and Power Systems
Energy and Environmental Solutions	Environmental and Sustainability Consulting
Energy and Environmental Solutions	Sustainability and Environmental Policy
Energy and Environmental Solutions	Water Management and Treatment
Health and Medical Services	Health and Medical Sciences
Industry and Manufacturing	Consumer Goods and Services
Industry and Manufacturing	Manufacturing and Industrial Services
Industry and Manufacturing	Materials Science and Engineering
Information, Communication, and Technology	Information and Communication Technology
Information, Communication, and Technology	Telecommunications
Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies	Marketing and Media Communications
Media, Marketing, and Cultural Studies	Social Sciences and Humanities
Public Services and Government	Government and Public Services
Safety, Emergency, and Security	Public Safety and Emergency Services
Science, Technology, and Innovation	Engineering and Technology
Science, Technology, and Innovation	Marine and Oceanography
Science, Technology, and Innovation	Technology and Innovation
Transportation and Urban Development	Transportation and Logistics
Transportation and Urban Development	Urban Planning and Development

LIMITATIONS OF MANUAL CLASSIFICATION IN PARTNER DATABASE FOR EGD PROJECTS

The classification system used in the construction of the comprehensive database for EGD projects, while detailed and methodical, inherently contains several limitations, primarily due to the manual components involved. These limitations, despite being mitigated through repeated checks and expert review, can introduce potential biases and inaccuracies. Below, we discuss these limitations in a structured, academic manner:

- **Subjectivity in Interpretation and Categorization:** Despite expert involvement, the manual interpretation of data can introduce subjectivity. Different experts might have varying

perspectives on how to categorize certain organizations or activities, especially when nuances in language or regional terminology come into play. For instance, the term "institute" might be perceived differently in various countries, potentially leading to inconsistent classifications.

- **Human Error and Inconsistency:** Human error is an unavoidable aspect of manual data processing. Even with multiple checks, the sheer volume of data increases the likelihood of occasional mistakes in data entry or classification. Inconsistent application of classification criteria can result in some entries being inaccurately categorized.
- **Translation and Language Barriers:** Translating the names of organizations and regions from their native languages into English can lead to loss of meaning or inaccuracies. Some terms might not have direct equivalents in English, leading to potential misclassification.
- **Ambiguities in Organizational Roles and Activities:** Organizations often engage in multiple activities that span various sectors, making it challenging to classify them under a single category. For example, a research institution might be involved in both educational activities and commercial projects, complicating its classification. The choice of primary versus secondary activities can be subjective and vary among experts.
- **Granularity and Overlap in Categories:** The detailed classification system, with 59 distinct activity types and multiple organizational categories, can sometimes result in overlap. For instance, "Research Institute" and "Research Organization" might refer to similar entities, leading to redundancy and potential confusion. This granularity, while aimed at providing detailed insights, can sometimes hinder clarity and consistent application.
- **Limited External Validation:** While the database relies heavily on the CORDIS database and other reputable sources, external validation of the classifications is limited. Independent verification from third-party audits or cross-referencing with other databases could enhance accuracy but is not always feasible due to resource constraints.

APPENDIX 3

The reader may refer to the survey link [here](#) (closed on 15 May 2024).

SURVEY TRANSCRIPT

Survey: NGOs' Impact on the European Green Deal

This form is part of an analytical study by [Dr. Edith Euan Diaz](#), for obtaining the degree of [Executive Master](#) in International Association Management at [Solvay Brussels School of Economics & Management](#).

Dear Participant, Your Insights Matter!

As we strive for a sustainable future, understanding the pivotal role of Non-Profit Organizations (NGOs) in the implementation of the European Green Deal is paramount.

The Context:

The European Green Deal represents our collective hope for a sustainable and climate-neutral continent by 2050. This ambitious initiative aims to transform our economy and society by addressing critical areas such as clean energy, biodiversity preservation, and sustainable industry.

NGOs might play a crucial role in bridging the gap between policy ambitions and on-the-ground action. Help us better understand your actions.

Organization Details:

While individual responses will be anonymized, details about your organization may be used to reinforce conclusions and provide specific examples of how NGOs are contributing to the Green Deal. This information will be crucial in illustrating the impact and diversity of NGO involvement.

Every Contribution Counts!

This questionnaire is exclusive for NGOs that are participating in one (or more) [Green Deal Project\(s\)](#). One questionnaire per project would be ideal.

Privacy and Confidentiality:

Your participation in this study is voluntary. Email addresses and Names are collected solely to follow up if there are any questions about your responses. All responses will be anonymized before analysis, and no personal details will be used in any reports or publications resulting from this research.

* Indicates required question

1. Email*
2. **Your Name***
3. **Name of the Non-Profit Organization***
4. **Type of Non-Profit Organization***

Mark only one oval.

- Association
- International Organization
- Foundation
- Federation
- Confederation
- Cooperative
- Other:

5. **Please provide a brief description of your organization's mission and main activities.***

6. **Which [Green Deal Project](#) is your organization involved in? ***

Mark only one oval.

- ACCTING
- Agro2Circular
- ALTERNATIVE
- ARSINOE
- ARV
- AURORA
- Bio-FlexGen

- CIRCULAR FOAM
- CityCLIM
- ClieNFarms
- COMPAIR
- ECF4CLIM
- ECO2Fuel
- EcoeFISHent
- ENERGICA
- ENOUGH
- EU-SCORES
- FIRE-RES
- FIRELOGUE
- FORWARD-2030
- FRONTSHIP
- GreenH2Atlantic
- GreenHyScale
- GreenSCENT
- HYPERGRYD
- I-CHANGE
- I-CISK
- ILIAD
- IMPETUS
- LIFESAVER
- LOCALISED
- MAGPIE
- MERLIN
- NeoGiANT
- NetZeroCities
- OLGA
- oPEN Lab
- PANORAMIX
- PAUL
- PestNu
- PHOENIX
- PIONEERS
- PROBONO
- PROMISCES
- PSLifestyle
- PYROCO2
- REACHOUT
- REAL_DEAL
- REFLECT AFRICA
- REFHYNE II
- REGILIENCE
- REST-COAST
- RESTORE
- RethinkAction
- RI-URBANS
- SCENARIOS
- SchoolFood4Change
- SESA:
- SHARED GREEN DEAL
- SILVANUS
- SISTERS
- SOCIO-BEE
- SophiA
- STARGATE
- SteamBioAfrica
- StoRIES
- SUPERB

- TransformAr
- TREADS
- TULIPS
- WaterLANDS
- ZeroPM
- ZeroW

7. What is the scale of your organization's involvement in the project? *

Check all that apply.

- Leading Role: Your organization directs the project, handling strategic decisions, project management, and coordination among stakeholders.
- Major: Your organization has significant responsibilities, managing major components or influencing several aspects of the project.
- Moderate: Your organization is involved in specific, limited areas, contributing specialized expertise or activities within the project.
- Minor: Your organization plays a supportive role, providing occasional resources or expertise that facilitates project activities but does not drive them.

8. How was your organization selected to participate in this Green Deal project? Please select the method that best describes your entry into the project.*

Check all that apply.

- Application: We applied independently through a formal proposal or application process.
- Invitation from Lead Organization: We were directly invited by the project's lead organization to join the consortium.
- Partnership Formation: We formed a partnership with other entities to jointly enter the project.
- Government Recommendation: We were recommended or mandated by a government body to participate.
- Network or Association Membership: Our involvement stemmed from our membership in a network or association that is part of the project.
- Research Collaboration: We were invited based on previous research collaborations with one or more of the project members.
- Expertise or Technological Capability: We were selected for our specific expertise or technological capabilities needed for the project.
- Other: _____

9. In what capacity is your organization involved in the Green Deal project? Select all that apply.*

Check all that apply.

- Advocacy: Promoting and advocating for the project's objectives to public and private stakeholders.
- Project Management: Directly managing or coordinating project activities and resources.
- Funding: Providing financial support or managing funding allocations for the project.
- Policy Development: Contributing to the drafting, development, or refinement of policies related to the project.
- Research and Analysis: Conducting scientific or social research, data analysis, or providing technical expertise.
- Community Engagement: Facilitating involvement and support from the community, local organizations, or the public.
- Education and Training: Offering training sessions, workshops, or educational materials related to the project's themes.
- Technical Solutions: Developing or implementing technological solutions or innovations that support the project's goals.
- Sustainability Practices: Implementing or advising on sustainability practices and green technologies within the project.
- Other:

10. How would you rate the impact of your organization's contributions to the project on a scale from 1 to 10?*

Mark only one oval.

1- No noticeable impact - Our contributions have made no discernible difference to the project's outcomes.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

10 -Extremely impactful - Our contributions have been crucial in achieving the project's objectives and have led to significant positive outcomes.

11. **What specific contributions has your organization made to the project's execution and outcomes?***
12. **In your view, what has been the most significant achievement of your involvement in the Green Deal project?***
13. **How does your organization collaborate with other stakeholders (e.g., governments, private sector, other NGOs) within the Green Deal project?***
14. **What challenges have you encountered while implementing the project, and how have you addressed them? ***
15. **On a scale from 1 to 10, how effective do you believe your organization's long-term sustainability strategies are in maintaining the project's impact post-completion?***

Mark only one oval.

1- Least Effective: The strategies have minimal or no potential to sustain the project's impacts; they are poorly designed or inadequately implemented.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

10-Highly Effective: The strategies are robust and well-implemented, ensuring that the project's impacts are sustained effectively and comprehensively over time.

16. **What measures are in place to ensure the sustainability and long-term impact of the project outcomes?***
17. **On a scale from 1 to 10, how confident are you that your organization will sustain the project's outcomes over the next 5 years? Please provide a rating and describe the key initiatives that will support this level of sustainability.***

Mark only one oval.

1 - Low Confidence: You have minimal confidence in sustaining any of the project outcomes, with very few or no initiatives in place to support continuity.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

10 - High Confidence: You are highly confident that all project outcomes will be sustained, backed by strong, effective initiatives and clear measures for continuity.

18. **What recommendations would you give to policymakers or funders to enhance the effectiveness of future Green Deal projects?***
19. **Final Comments:**

Please use the space below to share any additional comments, insights, or suggestions you have. We value your unique perspective and detailed input.

20. **I consent to my email being used to contact me for further clarification regarding my answers. I understand that my responses to the questionnaire will be anonymized and no personal details**

will be used in the analysis or reporting of this research.

*

Check all that apply.

Yes

APPENDIX 4

GENERAL ANALYSIS OF THE EGD

This Appendix delves into a comprehensive financial analysis of the EGD projects, focusing on the allocation and utilization of EU funding across various initiatives. By examining 73 projects that received a cumulative €960.61 million in EU funding, we aim to uncover patterns and insights into how these funds are distributed and utilized. On average, each project received approximately €13.16 million, though this figure conceals substantial variability in funding and total project costs, which reflect the diverse scopes and financial structures of the projects. This analysis not only highlights the strategic priorities of the EGD but also underscores the financial dynamics driving its initiatives, particularly in areas such as Engineering and Technology, Environmental Sustainability, and Energy and Resource Management.

A detailed statistical examination of EU funding per project reveals an average funding amount of €13.16 million with a notable standard error, indicating the precision of this estimate. The funding amounts are skewed towards lower values, with significant variability ranging from €50,000 to nearly €53 million per project. This skewness suggests a concentration of projects receiving moderate funding, with a few outliers receiving much larger sums. Similarly, total project costs vary widely, averaging €17.01 million per project, further emphasizing the diverse nature of these initiatives. This variability is crucial for understanding the financial landscape of the EGD, as it reflects the different scales and scopes of the projects involved.

In addition to the overall funding analysis, this chapter also explores the distribution of funds across different academic and economic categories. By breaking down the data, we can see which sectors receive the most support and how resources are allocated to drive innovation and sustainability. For instance, Engineering and Technology projects receive the lion's share of funding, reflecting their critical role in advancing the EGD's objectives. Environmental Sustainability and Energy and Resource Management also receive substantial funding, highlighting their importance in achieving a greener future. This targeted analysis provides valuable insights into the strategic focus areas within the EGD, showcasing the EU's commitment to supporting diverse, impactful projects.

FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF EGD PROJECTS

This section provides a detailed financial analysis of EGD projects, examining the distribution of EU funding and total project costs across various categories. We analyzed 73 projects, which received a total of €960.61 million in EU funding, covering an average of €13.16 million per project. The analysis reveals significant variability in funding and costs, reflecting diverse project scopes and financial structures. Additionally, we explore funding distribution across academic and economic categories, highlighting the emphasis on Engineering and Technology, Environmental Sustainability, and Energy and Resource Management. This comprehensive examination underscores the financial dynamics and strategic priorities within the EGD initiatives.

FUNDING PER PROJECT

We analyzed 73 EGD projects, which received a total of €960,606,057.15 in EU funding. The total cost of these projects amounts to €1,241,802,041.35, with the difference covered by investments from project partners, either through their own funds or other funding sources. This indicates that project partners contribute significantly, ensuring the projects' financial viability beyond the EU's contributions. The further statistical analysis is shown in Table 6 and Table 7. It was found that the average EU funding per project is approximately €13.16 million, with a standard error of €1.15 million, indicating precision in this estimate. The median funding is €11.02 million, suggesting half the projects received more and half less, while the mode of €5.55 million is the most common funding amount. The high standard deviation of €9.80 million and positive skewness of 1.50 indicate significant variability and a concentration of lower funding amounts. The range of funding spans from €50,000 to €52.99 million, totaling €960.61 million. For total project costs, the mean is €17.01 million with a standard error of €2.40 million, reflecting accuracy in the average estimate. The median cost is €11.73 million, and the mode is €6.51 million, showing frequent lower-cost projects. The standard deviation of €20.47 million and skewness of 4.28 highlight substantial variability and a tendency towards lower costs. The costs range from €71,429 to €148.96 million, with a total of €1.24 billion. The 95% confidence levels indicate that the true mean EU contribution and total cost per project are within €13.16 million ± €2.29 million and €17.01 million ± €4.77 million, respectively. These statistics underscore the diversity in funding and expenses, essential for understanding the financial landscape of the EGD initiatives.

Table 6 Statistical Analysis: Total net EU Contribution per Project

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
----------------------	-------	----------------

Mean	€ 13,158,987.08	The average EU funding per project.
Standard Error	€ 1,147,424.25	The accuracy of the mean funding estimate.
Median	€ 11,022,995.27	The midpoint of the funding amounts, indicating half of the projects received more and half received less.
Mode	€ 5,549,458.75	The most frequently received funding amount.
Standard Deviation	€ 9,803,597.06	Indicates high variability in funding amounts.
Sample Variance	9.61 x 10 ¹³	The dispersion of funding amounts.
Kurtosis	3.04	Shows a peaked distribution, with more extreme values than a normal distribution.
Skewness	1.50	Positive skew, meaning more projects received lower funding amounts.
Range	€ 52,946,604.88	Difference between the highest (€52,996,604.88) and lowest (€50,000) funding amounts.
Minimum	€ 50,000.00	The smallest funding amount received by a project.
Maximum	€ 52,996,604.88	The largest funding amount received by a project.
Sum	€ 960,606,057.15	The total EU funding received by all 73 projects.
Count	73	The number of projects analyzed.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	€ 2,287,348.43	We are 95% confident that the mean EU contribution per project is within €13,158,987.08 ± €2,287,348.43.

Table 7 Statistical Analysis: Total Cost per Project

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	€ 17,010,986.87	The average total cost per project.
Standard Error	€ 2,395,253.77	The accuracy of the mean total cost estimate.
Median	€ 11,725,328.75	The midpoint of the total costs, indicating half of the projects cost more and half cost less.
Mode	€ 6,511,232.50	The most frequently occurring total cost.
Standard Deviation	€ 20,465,057.16	Indicates high variability in project costs.
Sample Variance	4.19 x 10 ¹⁴	The dispersion of total costs.
Kurtosis	24.38	Indicates a highly peaked distribution, with many extreme values.
Skewness	4.28	Positive skew, meaning more projects have lower total costs.
Range	€ 148,884,976.00	Difference between the highest (€148,956,405.00) and lowest (€71,429) total costs.
Minimum	€ 71,429.00	The smallest total cost of a project.
Maximum	€ 148,956,405.00	The largest total cost of a project.
Sum	€ 1,241,802,041.35	The total cost of all 73 projects.
Count	73	The number of projects analyzed.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	€ 4,774,851.12	We are 95% confident that the mean total cost per project is within €17,010,986.87 ± €4,774,851.12.

Figure 22 illustrates the distribution and cumulative percentages of net EU funding and total costs for 73 EGD projects. The blue bars represent the number of projects receiving specific ranges of net EU funding, while the orange bars show the number of projects with corresponding total costs. The cumulative percentage lines for net EU funding and total costs are depicted in green and grey, respectively.

The distribution of net EU funding shows a significant concentration around the €5 million mark, with 13 projects, accounting for approximately 23.29% of the total. This is followed by a notable number of projects in the €5-10 million range, highlighting that many projects are funded within this mid-range bracket. The cumulative percentage line for net EU funding demonstrates a steep increase up to €20 million, covering around 80.82% of the projects, indicating that most projects receive funding below this threshold.

On the other hand, the distribution of total project costs shows a more spread-out pattern, with a significant number of projects clustered around the €5-6 million mark and the €25 million mark. The total cost cumulative percentage line rises sharply up to €25 million, covering 83.56% of the projects, suggesting that most projects have total costs below this level. The overall analysis reveals that while net EU funding tends to concentrate around lower to mid-range amounts, the total project costs exhibit greater variability, reflecting diverse project scopes and funding structures.

Figure 22 Distribution of EU funding and Total Costs across 73 EGD projects

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS ON FUNDING PER PROJECT

Projects at the high end of the funding spectrum illustrate significant financial commitment and large-scale impact. [REFHYNE II](#), with the highest total cost of €148.96 million and a substantial EU contribution of €32.43 million, exemplifies major investment and ambition in achieving the EGD objectives. This project focuses on installing a 100 MW PEM electrolyzer in Cologne, Germany, to produce green hydrogen and oxygen using renewable power, thus decarbonizing refinery operations and improving efficiency. Similarly, [GreenH2Atlantic](#) highlights significant funding, with a total project cost of €76.61 million and an EU contribution of €30 million. This initiative develops and demonstrates a 100 MW alkaline electrolyzer utilizing hybrid renewable energy, enhancing green hydrogen production and reducing GHG emissions across multiple sectors.

Mid-range projects reflect balanced funding levels, representing a broad spectrum of initiatives with varied scopes and impacts. [MAGPIE](#), involving a total cost of €30.76 million and an EU contribution of €24.96 million, is situated in the mid-high range and indicates robust financial backing from both the EU and partners. This project aims to enhance port efficiency and sustainability through green energy carriers, automation, and multimodal transport solutions. Another example, [ENOUGH](#), with a total project cost of €11.69 million and an EU contribution of €11.02 million, focuses on reducing GHG emissions and increasing energy efficiency in the food industry. The project engages a wide range of stakeholders to develop technologies and methods that contribute to climate-neutral food systems by 2050.

Projects at the low end of the funding spectrum are equally crucial, often focusing on niche or highly specific areas with lower financial requirements. [PANORAMIX](#) has the lowest total cost at €71,429 and an EU contribution of €50,000, reflecting the diversity of projects and the EU's support for smaller-scale, targeted initiatives. This project optimizes vehicle fleet operations to improve ride-sharing, safety, and emission reductions. [IMPETUS](#), with a total cost and EU contribution of €899,160, represents another low-end project that develops a comprehensive climate change adaptation framework for resilient regions. By engaging stakeholders and integrating reliable data, IMPETUS co-designs, assesses, and monitors climate adaptation strategies across various EU biogeographical regions, demonstrating how smaller projects can significantly contribute to the overall goals of the EGD through focused, efficient use of funds.

FUNDING DISTRIBUTION PER ACADEMIC CATEGORY

Figure 23 illustrates the distribution of EU funding across five overarching academic categories within the EGD projects. Engineering and Technology received the highest proportion of funding, accounting for 42% of the total EU contributions. This category includes projects related to Renewable Energy, Environmental Engineering, Materials Science, Data Science and AI, Biotechnology, and General Engineering. Environmental and Earth Sciences followed with 24% of the funding, encompassing Climatology, Marine and Ocean Sciences, Water Resources Management, and Environmental Sciences. Social Sciences and Governance received 19% of the funding, covering areas such as Political Science, Social Sciences, Governance and Law, Economics and Sustainable Economy, and Education and Communication. Health and Medical Sciences, which includes Medical and Health Sciences and Biotechnology, received 8% of the funding. Agricultural and Food Sciences, including Agricultural Sciences and Food Technology, received the smallest share at 7%.

Figure 23 Total Net EU contribution by Overarching Academic Category

Table 8 below provides a detailed summary of the total EU contributions and total costs for each academic category, along with the difference between these two values.

Table 8 Summary of Total EU Contribution and Total Costs by Overarching Academic Categories

Overarching Academic Category	Sum of Total EU Contribution	Sum of Total Cost	Difference
Agricultural and Food Sciences	€ 63,438,195.50	€ 72,867,509.36	€ 9,429,313.86
Engineering and Technology	€ 401,747,724.40	€ 640,889,905.04	€ 239,142,180.64
Environmental and Earth Sciences	€ 234,306,534.24	€ 250,525,119.99	€ 16,218,585.75
Health and Medical Sciences	€ 75,155,785.97	€ 83,420,548.46	€ 8,264,762.49
Social Sciences and Governance	€ 185,957,817.04	€ 194,098,958.50	€ 8,141,141.46
Grand Total	€ 960,606,057.15	€ 1,241,802,041.35	€ 281,195,984.20

Table 8 shows that Engineering and Technology not only received the highest EU contribution (€401,747,724.40) but also had the highest total cost (€640,889,905.04), resulting in a significant funding gap of €239,142,180.64. Environmental and Earth Sciences followed with an EU contribution of €234,306,534.24 and a total cost of €250,525,119.99, leaving a difference of €16,218,585.75. Social Sciences and Governance, Health and Medical Sciences, and Agricultural and Food Sciences also show funding gaps, with differences of €8,141,141.46, €8,264,762.49, and €9,429,313.86, respectively. Overall, the total EU contribution for all categories was €960,606,057.15, while the total cost amounted to €1,241,802,041.35, resulting in a combined funding gap of €281,195,984.20.

Furthermore, breaking the overarching Academic categories into the 20 more granular ones we obtained the following: Figure 24 illustrates the distribution of projects funded under the EGD, classified into five overarching academic categories and further broken down into 20 specific academic categories.

Engineering and Technology stands out with the highest number of projects, particularly in fields like Materials Science, Environmental Engineering, and Engineering (General), reflecting the emphasis on technological innovation and engineering solutions. This category includes 24 projects in total. Environmental and Earth Sciences also show significant representation with 19 projects, mainly focused on Environmental Sciences, Marine and Ocean Sciences, and Climatology, highlighting the importance of environmental protection and climate resilience.

Social Sciences and Governance account for 19 projects, with notable contributions from Social Sciences, Urban Planning and Development, and Economics and Sustainable Economy, emphasizing governance and societal impact. Health and Medical Sciences include 5 projects, primarily in Medical and Health Sciences and Biotechnology, underscoring the focus on health-related innovations. Lastly, Agricultural and Food Sciences comprise 6 projects, all dedicated to Agricultural Sciences, highlighting sustainable agriculture and food technology.

Figure 24 Distribution of Projects Across Academic Categories

FUNDING DISTRIBUTION PER ECONOMIC CATEGORY

Figure 25 illustrates the allocation of EU funds across five primary economic categories within the EGD projects. The largest portion of funding, 46%, is dedicated to Energy and Resource Management, underscoring the emphasis on the development, implementation, and management of energy resources and waste materials. Environmental Sustainability receives 32% of the total EU contribution, highlighting the focus on sustainable practices and technologies that promote environmental protection and resource conservation.

Infrastructure and Urban Development accounts for 12% of the funding, reflecting the priority given to the planning and development of sustainable cities, transportation systems, and urban infrastructure. Societal Development and Governance, which includes initiatives related to public health, education, policy design, and governance frameworks, is allocated 7% of the funds. Lastly, Technology and Innovation, which covers the advancement and application of new technologies across various sectors, receives the smallest portion at 3%.

Figure 25 Total Net EU Contribution by Overarching Economic Categories

Table 9 shows that the highest total EU contribution is for projects under Energy and Resource Management (€ 437,752,758.28), followed by Environmental Sustainability (€ 308,651,360.58). Infrastructure and Urban Development, Societal Development and Governance, and Technology and Innovation receive comparatively smaller amounts. The differences between the total EU contributions and the total costs indicate significant investments from project partners in all categories, especially in Energy and Resource Management.

Table 9 Distribution of EU Contributions by Overarching Economic Categories

Row Labels	Sum of Total EU Contribution	Sum of Total Cost	Difference
Energy and Resource Management	€ 437,752,758.28	€ 668,014,331.95	€ 230,261,573.67
Environmental Sustainability	€ 308,651,360.58	€ 339,779,917.64	€ 31,128,557.06
Infrastructure and Urban Development	€ 113,996,830.87	€ 128,283,784.35	€ 14,286,953.48
Societal Development and Governance	€ 66,542,413.38	€ 69,694,970.25	€ 3,152,556.87
Technology and Innovation	€ 33,662,694.04	€ 36,029,037.16	€ 2,366,343.12
Grand Total	€ 960,606,057.15	€ 1,241,802,041.35	€ 281,195,984.20

To gain deeper insights into the distribution of funds within the EGD projects, we further analyzed the overarching economic categories by breaking them down into 20 specific sectors, the results are

shown in Figure 26. This granular examination allows us to understand the specific areas of focus and the strategic priorities within each broader category.

Figure 26 shows that the largest allocation, comprising 28 projects, falls under "Environmental Sustainability." This category emphasizes sustainable practices and technologies that promote environmental protection and resource conservation, encompassing sectors such as agrifood, climate adaptation, and environmental monitoring. Following this, "Energy and Resource Management" includes 25 projects, highlighting significant efforts in renewable energy and waste management, reflecting a strong focus on energy efficiency and sustainable resource use. These analyses reveal the strategic priorities within the EGD, demonstrating a robust commitment to both environmental sustainability and efficient resource management.

"Infrastructure and Urban Development" includes six projects, focusing on sustainable urban planning, smart cities, and transportation systems. This reflects the importance of developing sustainable urban infrastructures to support green initiatives. "Societal Development and Governance" accounts for 11 projects, covering public health, education, policy design, and governance frameworks. This indicates an emphasis on societal well-being and effective governance in addressing environmental and social challenges. Lastly, "Technology and Innovation" encompasses three projects, which focus on the advancement and application of new technologies across various sectors, underscoring the role of innovation in achieving sustainability goals.

Figure 26 Distribution of Projects by Economic Categories

ANALYSIS AND DISTRIBUTION OF PARTNERS IN EGD PROJECTS

This section provides a comprehensive statistical analysis of consortium roles and participation in EGD projects. We examine the distribution of consortium sizes, types of organizations involved, and funding allocation among partners. Our analysis reveals that the average consortium comprises approximately 27 partners, with notable variability across projects. Educational and research institutions, private sector entities, NPOs, and governmental bodies play significant roles, reflecting diverse contributions to these initiatives. Furthermore, we explore the disparities in EU funding distribution, highlighting the need for equitable resource allocation to enhance overall project effectiveness and impact.

PARTNERS PER PROJECT

European funded projects typically involve a consortium of partners, which can include Coordinators, Partners, and Third Parties. Each partner assumes a specific role within the project, contributing to its successful execution. In this analysis, we examine the statistical distribution of the number of partners involved in such projects.

Table 10 contains the statistical analysis of the 73 funded projects shows that the average consortium size is approximately 27 partners, with the most frequent size being 16. There is considerable variability, with the number of partners ranging from 1 to 58. The data distribution is slightly positively skewed and relatively flat, indicating some projects have significantly more partners than others. The 95% confidence interval of 3.36 confirms that the sample mean is a reliable estimate.

Table 10 Statistical Analysis: Total number of Partners per Project

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
----------------------	-------	----------------

Mean	26.90	The average number of partners per project is approximately 27, indicating a moderately large consortium size.
Standard Error	1.69	This indicates the accuracy of the sample mean estimate, suggesting that the sample mean is relatively stable.
Median	22	The median number of partners per project is 22, meaning that half of the projects have fewer than 22 partners and half have more.
Mode	16	The most frequently occurring number of partners in these projects is 16, showing a common consortium size.
Standard Deviation	14.42	This measure shows that the number of partners typically deviates from the mean by about 14, indicating considerable variability among project sizes.
Sample Variance	208.00	The variance of 208 indicates the extent to which the number of partners per project varies around the mean.
Kurtosis	-0.78	A negative kurtosis value indicates a relatively flat distribution compared to a normal distribution, with fewer extreme outliers.
Skewness	0.54	The positive skewness indicates a slight asymmetry, with a longer tail on the right side of the distribution.
Range	57	The range of 57 demonstrates a significant difference between the smallest and largest number of partners in these projects.
Minimum	1	The smallest project in terms of partners has only 1 partner, showing that some projects can be highly concentrated.
Maximum	58	The largest project involves 58 partners, indicating the potential for very large collaborative efforts.
Sum	1964	The total number of partners across all 73 projects is 1964, reflecting the scale of collaboration in European funded projects.
Count	73	There are 73 projects in the sample, providing a solid basis for statistical analysis.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	3.36	The 95% confidence interval suggests that the true mean number of partners per project is within 3.36 partners of the sample mean, indicating robust reliability.

Figure 27 illustrates the distribution and cumulative percentage of partners in European funded projects. Most projects have between 15 and 25 partners, with the highest frequency at 20 partners. The cumulative percentage line shows that about 56.16% of projects have 25 or fewer partners, indicating that over half of the projects involve up to 25 partners. The frequency of projects decreases as the number of partners increases, although there are peaks at certain intervals, such as 20, 25, and 40 partners. The cumulative percentage reaches 100% at 60 partners, showing the full range of partner numbers in the dataset. This distribution provides insights into the typical consortium sizes in European funded projects, emphasizing moderate-sized collaborations.

Figure 27 Distribution of Partners in EGD Funded Projects

TYPES OF PARTNERS PER PROJECT

Figure 28 shows the number of projects having the involvement of at least one type of partner. The classification follows the overarching organizational categories explained in Appendix , section Organization and Activity Type Classification. Educational and research institutions participate in 72 projects, the highest among all categories, reflecting the emphasis on research and innovation. Private sector entities are involved in 71 projects, highlighting their crucial role in driving investment and technological advancement. NPOs participate in 58 projects, indicating their significant contribution to social and environmental goals. Governmental bodies are involved in 39 projects, underscoring the importance of public sector leadership. International organizations, participating in 5 projects.

Figure 28 Organizational Involvement in EGD Projects

Figure 29 provides a detailed breakdown of the distribution of EGD projects according to the number and type of organizations involved. The chart illustrates the distribution of EGD projects according to the number and type of organizations involved. Educational and research institutions are the most prevalent, particularly peaking at 4, 7, and 11 organizations, reflecting their central role in these projects. Governmental bodies are primarily involved in smaller groups, with the highest frequency at 1 or 2 entities per project. Private sector entities also show significant participation, commonly in groups of 2, 3, and 6; notably, this sector has the major involvement of organization per project with 39 organizations in one of them, indicating their substantial involvement in various consortium sizes. NPOs are widely distributed, with notable peaks at 1, 2 and 4 entities per project. International organizations have limited participation, generally appearing in pairs.

Figure 29 Distribution of Organizational Participation in EGD Projects

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS ON PARTNERS PER PROJECT AND THEIR TYPES

Projects at the high end of the partner spectrum, such as [ILIAD](#) and [OLGA](#), demonstrate the extensive collaborative efforts required for large-scale and complex initiatives. [ILIAD](#), with 58 partners, focuses on developing an interoperable, data-intensive Digital Twin of the Ocean. This ambitious project necessitates input from 28 educational and research institutions, 19 private sector entities, and various other stakeholders to enhance marine data integration and sustainability, supporting the blue economy and climate resilience. Similarly, [OLGA](#), with 53 partners, aims to achieve efficient, carbon-neutral airport operations through sustainable aviation fuels and low-emission technologies. The project's consortium includes 32 private sector entities and 13 educational institutions, highlighting the necessity of broad and multidisciplinary collaboration to address comprehensive and intricate environmental challenges. Additionally, [TREEADS](#), with 53 partners, aims to develop a holistic fire management system integrating advanced technologies for prevention, detection, and restoration of wildfire-affected areas, involving 22 private sector entities and 18 educational institutions.

Mid-range projects, such as [ENOUGH](#) and [MERLIN](#), which involve 33 and 47 partners respectively, reflect balanced consortium sizes that integrate diverse expertise and resources. [ENOUGH](#) focuses on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing energy efficiency in the food industry, engaging 16 private sector entities and 15 educational institutions. This project exemplifies how moderate-sized collaborations can effectively address significant environmental issues through innovation and stakeholder engagement. [MERLIN](#) aims to upscale nature-based solutions for freshwater ecosystem restoration, bringing together 23 educational institutions and 11 governmental bodies. This project underscores the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in driving systemic change and promoting economic growth through sustainable practices. Another notable example is [ARV](#), with 38 partners, aiming to accelerate the adoption of Climate Positive Circular Communities by integrating digital tools and circular economy principles, involving 16 private sector entities and 10 educational institutions.

At the low end of the partner spectrum, projects like [PANORAMIX](#) and [IMPETUS](#) involve minimal partners, with 1 and 7 partners respectively. [PANORAMIX](#), focusing on optimizing vehicle fleet operations to improve ride-sharing and emission reductions, involves just a single private sector entity, demonstrating that even small-scale collaborations can have a significant impact on specific environmental challenges. On the other hand, [IMPETUS](#), which develops a climate change adaptation framework for resilient regions, includes 5 private sector entities and 2 educational institutions. This project illustrates how targeted and specific collaborations can effectively contribute to the overarching goals of the EGD by leveraging focused expertise and resources. Similarly, [AURORA](#), with 9 partners, engages citizens in sustainable energy practices through citizen science and crowdfunding solar facilities, involving 5 educational institutions and 2 private sector entities, highlighting the role of community-based initiatives in promoting sustainability.

ANALYSIS OF ORGANIZATIONAL INVOLVEMENT AND FUNDING IN EGD PROJECTS

This section examines the roles and distribution of partner organizations within 73 EGD projects, highlighting their diverse participation and funding. Utilizing a unique identifier method, **we identified 1,574 unique partners from a total of 1,964 partner organizations**, reflecting multiple project participations. The analysis covers consortium roles, regional and global distribution, and funding allocations, revealing significant variability in organizational involvement and funding. By understanding these dynamics, we can better appreciate the strategic contributions and financial landscapes that underpin the success of the EGD initiatives.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF CONSORTIUM ROLES

Our analysis departs using the definitions given in Appendix , section: CONSORTIUM ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES IN EGD PROJECTS for the consortium roles within the EGD projects reveals the following:

- **Total number of single organizations:** 1,574
- **Organizations acting as Coordinators in other projects:** 27
- **Third Parties also acting as Coordinators:** 7
- **Third Parties also acting as Participants in other projects:** 31
- **Organizations only acting as Coordinators:** 39
- **Organizations only acting as Participants:** 1,338
- **Organizations only acting as Third Parties:** 142
- **Organizations involved in all roles (Coordinator, Participant, and Third Party):** 5

This data highlights the diverse involvement of organizations within the EGD projects. While the majority (1,338) are primarily Participants, a smaller number are dedicated solely to coordination (39) or function as Third Parties (142). Notably, some organizations (27) have dual roles as Coordinators in

other projects, indicating a high level of expertise and engagement. A few entities (5) are involved in all capacities, demonstrating their comprehensive participation in the EGD initiatives. This distribution underscores the multifaceted nature of consortium participation and the importance of strategic role assignment to leverage the strengths of various partners effectively.

DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANIZATIONS AND FUNDING PER OVERARCHING ORGANIZATIONAL CATEGORIES

Figure 30 provides a visual representation of the composition of 1,574 organizations participating in EGD projects. The chart categorizes these organizations into five distinct groups provided in Appendix (Section: Organization and Activity Type Classification): Educational and Research Institutions, Governmental Bodies, International Organizations, Non-Profit Organizations, and Private Sector Entities.

The data reveals that Private Sector Entities constitute the largest group, comprising 684 organizations, which accounts for 43% of the total. Educational and Research Institutions follow, representing 496 organizations or 32% of the total. NPOs make up 237 organizations, corresponding to 15%. Governmental Bodies include 149 organizations, forming 9% of the total. Finally, International Organizations are the smallest group, with only 8 organizations, representing 0,5%. This distribution highlights the significant involvement of the private sector and educational institutions in the EGD projects, emphasizing their critical roles in driving innovation and implementation. NPOs also play a vital role, contributing to the social and environmental goals of these initiatives.

Figure 30 Organizational Composition of European Green Deal Project Participants

Figure 31 and Table 11 illustrate the allocation of €960.61 million in EU funding among different types of organizations involved in EGD projects. The chart categorizes the funding into five groups: Educational and Research Institutions, Governmental Bodies, International Organizations, NPOs, and Private Sector Entities. The data shows that Private Sector Entities receive the largest share of the funding, amounting to €406.99 million, which represents 42% of the total EU funding. Educational and Research Institutions follow closely, receiving €390.60 million, accounting for 41% of the total. NPOs are allocated €106.412 million, making up 11% of the funding. Governmental Bodies receive €54.05 million, which constitutes 6% of the total. International Organizations receive the smallest share, with €2.25 million, representing 0,2%.

Figure 31 Allocation of Net EU Funding Across Organizational Categories in European Green Deal Projects

Table 11 Net EU Funding Distribution by Organizational Category

Organizational Category	Sum of Total Net EU Funding
Educational and Research Institutions	€ 390.603.145,23
Governmental Bodies	€ 54.348.444,67
International Organization	€ 2.252.453,75
Non-Profit Organization	€ 106.412.815,09
Private Sector Entities	€ 406.989.198,41
Grand Total	€ 960.606.057,15

This distribution highlights the significant financial support directed towards private sector entities and educational institutions, emphasizing their pivotal roles in the implementation and innovation of EGD projects. NPOs also receive substantial funding, reflecting their importance in addressing social and

environmental goals. The relatively smaller shares for governmental and international organizations indicate their more focused but critical contributions to the overall success of the EGD initiatives.

REGIONAL DISTRIBUTION

Figure 32 shows a map of the distribution of partners of the EGD projects across various countries. Spain leads with 193 organizations involved, followed by Italy with 165, and Belgium with 135. The Netherlands and France also have significant participation, with 132 and 130 organizations respectively. Germany contributes 121 organizations, while the United Kingdom and Portugal participate with 66 and 64 organizations. Greece, Sweden, and Austria show moderate involvement, with 54, 38, and 38 organizations respectively. Poland, Norway, and Denmark each contribute between 30 and 37 organizations. Switzerland, Romania, and Ireland have notable participation with 29, 27, and 26 organizations respectively. Other countries, including Finland, Croatia, Estonia, Israel, and several African nations, participate to a lesser extent, reflecting the global reach and diverse involvement in EGD projects. This distribution underscores the widespread commitment to sustainability initiatives, with a strong concentration in European countries and notable contributions from several non-European nations.

Figure 32 Map of Project Participation by Country

Figure 33 illustrates the distribution of organizations involved in EGD projects across different continents. Europe overwhelmingly leads with 1,460 entities, accounting for 93% of the total. Africa follows with 57 organizations, representing 3.6%, indicating a modest but notable participation. Asia contributes 43 entities, making up 2.7% of the total, showing significant engagement from this continent. South America and the combined region of Europe/Asia each have 3 organizations, representing 0.2% each, while Australia has 3 entities, accounting for 0.2% as well. North America is represented by 2 entities, constituting 0.1% of the total. This distribution highlights the predominant involvement of European organizations in EGD projects, with other continents contributing to a lesser but still meaningful extent.

Figure 33 Distribution of Organizations Across Continents

Figure 34 illustrates the distribution of organizations involved in EGD projects across different regions within Europe. Western Europe leads with 594 organizations, indicating the highest level of participation. Southern Europe follows with 512 organizations, showing strong engagement in EGD initiatives. Northern Europe contributes 239 organizations, reflecting significant involvement from this region. Eastern Europe has 115 organizations participating, indicating moderate engagement. The combined region of Eastern Europe and Northern Asia has the least participation, with only 3 organizations. This distribution highlights the predominant involvement of Western and Southern Europe in EGD projects, with substantial contributions from Northern Europe and moderate participation from Eastern Europe.

Figure 34 Distribution of Organizations in European Regions

Figure 35 displays the distribution of organizations involved in EGD projects across various regions outside Europe. Western Asia leads with 38 organizations, indicating substantial participation. Eastern Africa follows with 17 organizations, showing significant involvement from this region. Northern Africa and Western Africa contribute 12 and 13 organizations respectively, reflecting moderate engagement. Southern Africa has 14 organizations participating, highlighting its notable contribution. Other regions, including Australia and Oceania, Eastern Asia, and Northern America, each have 3 organizations, while Southeast Asia and Eastern South America have 2 organizations each, indicating limited but present involvement. Central Africa has the least participation with 1 organization. This distribution underscores the diverse global engagement in EGD projects, with significant contributions from various African regions and Western Asia.

Figure 35 Distribution of Organizations Outside Europe

ANALYSIS OF FUNDING ALLOCATION AMONG UNIQUE PARTNERS

Table 6 shows the statistical analysis of EU funding allocation among 1,574 unique partners in the EGD projects and reveals significant disparities. The mean funding per partner is € 489,106.95, substantially higher than the median of € 304,000.00, indicating a skewed distribution with a few partners receiving large amounts while many receive less. This is further evidenced by a high standard deviation of € 1,174,802.23 and extreme kurtosis and skewness values, showing heavy-tailed and right-skewed distribution, respectively. The distribution of net EU funding for single organizations participating in EGD projects is highly skewed, with most organizations receiving lower amounts and a few receiving very high amounts. **This analysis highlights the need for examining the equity of funding distribution to ensure broader participation and impact across all involved organizations.** Notably, 31 organizations receive no funding, making € 0 the mode. The wide range from € 0 to € 36,480,465.00 underscores the variability in funding amounts. These findings suggest that while some organizations benefit greatly, a considerable number receive minimal or no support, highlighting the need for a more equitable distribution of funds to enhance participation and impact across all partners.

Table 12 Net EU Funding Allocation Among Unique Partners

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	€ 489,106.95	On average, each partner receives approximately € 489,106.95 in EU funding.
Standard Error	€ 26,509.04	The mean EU funding has a standard error of € 26,509.04, indicating the precision of the mean estimate.

Median	€ 304,000.00	The median value of € 304,000.00 shows that half of the partners receive less than this amount, and half receive more.
Mode	€ 0	The most frequently occurring value is € 0, indicating that some organizations do not receive any funding.
Standard Deviation	€ 1,174,802.23	There is considerable variability in the funding amounts, with a standard deviation of € 1,174,802.23.
Sample Variance	1.38016E+12	The variance of 1.38016E+12 further reflects the wide range of funding amounts.
Kurtosis	474.9583728	The high kurtosis value indicates a distribution with heavy tails, meaning there are many extreme outliers.
Skewness	17.97067431	The positive skewness suggests that the distribution of funding amounts is heavily skewed to the right, with a few partners receiving significantly higher funding.
Range	€ 36,480,465.00	The difference between the maximum and minimum funding amounts is € 36,480,465.00.
Minimum	€ 0	The lowest funding amount is € 0, indicating that some organizations do not receive any funding.
Maximum	€ 36,480,465.00	The highest funding amount received by a single organization is € 36,480,465.00.
Sum	€ 960,606,057.15	The total EU funding allocated across all partners is € 960,606,057.15.
Count	1,964	The total number of funding allocations analyzed is 1,964.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	€ 51,988.82	We can be 95% confident that the true mean EU funding per partner lies within € 51,988.82 of the sample mean.

Figure 36 illustrates the distribution of net EU funding across single organizations participating in EGD projects. The histogram displays the frequency of funding amounts, while the cumulative percentage line indicates the proportion of the total number of organizations up to each Net EU funding bin. The x-axis represents Net EU funding bins, with increments ranging from €0 to €37,000,000, and the y-axis on the left denotes the frequency of organizations within each funding bin. The frequency distribution shows a high concentration of organizations receiving lower amounts of funding, with the highest frequency observed in the €150,000 bin (159 organizations). As funding amounts increase, the frequency of organizations receiving these amounts decreases, with only a few organizations receiving the highest levels of funding. The y-axis on the right represents the cumulative percentage of organizations, where the curve shows a steep increase at lower funding levels, indicating that a large proportion of organizations receive smaller amounts of funding. The cumulative percentage approaches 100% as funding amounts increase, with the final data point indicating that 100% of organizations fall within the €0 to €37,000,000 range.

The data reveals that a significant number of organizations (31) receive no funding (mode: €0), representing 1.97% of the total. Net EU funding bins up to €500,000 encompass the majority of organizations, with a steep cumulative percentage rise indicating that around 69% of organizations receive up to €500,000. The distribution exhibits a long tail, with a few organizations receiving significantly higher funding amounts, exemplified by the highest bin (€37,000,000) containing only one organization (0.06%). The frequency steadily decreases beyond the €500,000 mark, illustrating a wide dispersion in funding allocation among partners. The cumulative percentage curve becomes less steep as it approaches 100%, indicating that higher funding amounts are allocated to a smaller number of organizations. Approximately 95% of organizations receive up to €2,000,000 in funding, reflecting the predominance of lower to mid-range funding levels within the dataset. **This analysis highlights the need for examining the equity of funding distribution to ensure broader participation and impact across all involved organizations.**

Figure 36 Distribution of Net EU Funding for Single Organizations

PARTNER HIGHLIGHTS AND NET EU FUNDING DISTRIBUTION ANALYSIS

Analyzing the funding distribution, it is evident that larger sums are predominantly allocated to entities with established infrastructures and a broad scope of influence, particularly in innovation and large-scale project implementation. This stratification ensures that significant portions of the EGD 's budget are invested in high-impact areas with the potential for widespread environmental benefits. Meanwhile, the moderate and smaller funding allocations play a crucial role in supporting specialized projects and fostering innovation at grassroots levels, ensuring a comprehensive and inclusive approach to achieving EGD objectives.

The top tier of funding recipients reflects significant contributions to the EGD from pivotal entities, emphasizing substantial projects and innovative solutions. Leading this group is [Climate-KIC Holding BV](#) from the Netherlands, receiving a remarkable €37,075,219.13. This substantial funding underscores its central role in driving climate innovation and sustainability across Europe. Similarly, [Sintef AS](#) from Norway, with €21,151,685.72, and [Danmarks Tekniske Universitet](#) from Denmark, receiving €13,162,492.60, highlight the Scandinavian commitment to research and technological advancements in green initiatives. [Mcphy Energy Italia Societa A Responsabilita Limitata](#) in Italy also stands out with €12,947,326.01, focusing on green hydrogen production, which is crucial for clean energy transition.

In the middle spectrum, partners are notable for their diverse approaches and significant yet moderate funding. [Aéroports de Paris SA](#) in France, with €7,119,329.13, exemplifies efforts to green aviation infrastructure, a key area for reducing carbon emissions. [Oceans of Energy BV](#) in the Netherlands, securing €7,100,377.38, showcases innovation in offshore renewable energy solutions. Belgium's [Brussels Airport Company \(BAC\)](#) and [Vlaamse Instelling Voor Technologisch Onderzoek N.V. \(VITO\)](#), with funding of €8,747,996.25 and €8,888,371.25 respectively, indicate a strong national focus on integrating sustainable practices in both transportation and research sectors.

At the lower end of the funding spectrum, smaller but crucial contributions are directed towards niche and targeted green initiatives. For instance, [Hochschule Karlsruhe](#) in Germany, with €1,526,756.25, is pivotal in fostering educational advancements and sustainable technology research. The [University College Dublin](#) in Ireland, receiving €2,699,055.00, highlights the significant role of academia in the EGD, focusing on innovative research and development. Meanwhile, [Anglia Ruskin University](#) in the UK, with €689,096.25, and [Ben-Gurion University of the Negev](#) in Israel, receiving €1,519,297.50, illustrate the geographical and institutional diversity in contributing to sustainable solutions.

The very low end features partners like [Wetlands International - European Association](#) (Netherlands) with €198,362.50, [Fundacion Corporacion Tecnologica De Andalucia](#) (Spain) with €180,125.00, and [Municipality of Amaroussion](#) (Greece) with €258,289.43. These entities, though receiving less funding, contribute to niche areas like wetland conservation, regional technological advancement, and municipal sustainability projects. Their efforts are vital in creating a comprehensive and inclusive approach to the EGD 's objectives.

CASCADING FUNDING TO THIRD PARTIES

Cascading funding involves identifying organizations that act as third parties within EGD projects and calculating the total amount of net EU funding allocated to them. Our analysis identified 105 single organizations functioning as third parties. Notably, a single partner organization can have multiple third parties under its purview. This approach ensures that funds are distributed to various entities contributing to the project's objectives, even if they do not participate as primary beneficiaries or affiliated entities.

The analysis shown in of cascading funding to third parties shown in Table 13 reveals substantial disparities in the distribution of funds. The mean funding amount is € 540,057.96, which is significantly higher than the median of € 167,396.22, indicating a right-skewed distribution with a few third parties receiving much larger amounts. The mode of € 30,000.00 suggests that this amount is the most common funding level among third parties.

The high standard deviation and variance values point to considerable variability in the funding amounts. The kurtosis value of 67.66001276 and the skewness of 7.717031482 further emphasize the presence of extreme outliers in the data. The range from € 6,345.65 to € 16,349,208.17 highlights the wide span of funding received by different third parties.

The substantial differences in funding allocations suggest a need for careful consideration in the distribution process to ensure that the funds are effectively supporting the diverse range of third parties involved in EGD projects.

Table 13 Statistical Analysis of Cascading Funding to Third Parties

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	€ 540,057.96	On average, each third party receives € 540,057.96 in EU funding.
Standard Error	€ 169,455.45	The standard error of € 169,455.45 indicates the precision of the mean estimate.
Median	€ 167,396.22	The median funding amount is € 167,396.22, suggesting that half of the third parties receive less than this amount and half receive more.
Mode	€ 30,000.00	The most frequently occurring funding amount is € 30,000.00.
Standard Deviation	€ 1,736,401.69	The high standard deviation indicates substantial variability in the funding amounts among third parties.
Sample Variance	3.01509E+12	The variance of € 3.01509E+12 reflects the wide range of funding amounts.
Kurtosis	67.66001276	The high kurtosis value indicates a distribution with heavy tails, suggesting many extreme outliers.
Skewness	7.717031482	The positive skewness indicates a right-skewed distribution with a few third parties receiving much higher funding.
Range	€ 16,342,862.52	The range of € 16,342,862.52 shows the difference between the minimum and maximum funding amounts.
Minimum	€ 6,345.65	The smallest funding amount allocated to a third party is € 6,345.65.
Maximum	€ 16,349,208.17	The largest funding amount received by a single third party is € 16,349,208.17.
Sum	€ 56,706,085.51	The total funding distributed to all third parties amounts to € 56,706,085.51.
Count	105	The analysis is based on 105 third parties.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	€ 336,036.52	We can be 95% confident that the true mean funding per third party lies within € 336,036.52 of the sample mean.

Figure 37 illustrates the distribution of net EU funding allocated to third parties within EGD projects. The histogram displays the Number of organizations with such Net EU funding amounts, while the cumulative percentage line indicates the proportion of organizations up to each funding bin.

The x-axis represents Net EU funding bins, incrementally ranging from €0 to €17,000,000, and the y-axis on the left denotes the Number of organizations within each funding bin. The frequency distribution shows a higher concentration of organizations receiving lower funding amounts, with the peak frequency in the €50,000 bin, which includes 16 organizations. As funding amounts increase, the frequency of organizations decreases, indicating fewer organizations receive higher amounts of

funding. The cumulative percentage curve rises rapidly at lower funding levels, reflecting that a significant proportion of organizations receive smaller amounts. It gradually flattens as it approaches 100%, indicating the inclusion of higher funding levels for fewer organizations.

The data reveals that a substantial number of organizations receive funding within the lower bins. Specifically, around 60% of third parties receive up to €200,000. The distribution is right-skewed, with a long tail extending towards higher funding amounts, implying most third parties receive modest funding while a few receive significantly larger amounts. Approximately 95.24% of organizations receive up to €1,900,000, with the range extending to €17,000,000 for one organization. This skewness suggests a need for balanced funding strategies to ensure a broader and more equitable distribution of resources, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness and impact of the EGD initiatives.

Figure 37 Distribution of Cascading Net EU Funding to Third Parties

Figure 38 illustrates the distribution of the number of organizations against the total number of third parties involved in EGD projects. The x-axis represents the number of third parties each organization collaborates with, ranging from 1 to 10, while the y-axis shows the number of organizations. The data reveals a significant concentration at the lower end, with 70 organizations collaborating with only one third party. As the number of third parties increases, the number of organizations decreases markedly, with 14 organizations collaborating with two third parties, and this number continuing to decline further. Only one organization each is seen collaborating with five, six, nine, and ten third parties. This pattern indicates a strong preference among organizations for limited third-party involvement, likely to maintain simplicity and control in their projects.

Figure 38 Distribution of Organizations by Number of Third-Party Collaborations in EGD Projects

CONCLUSIONS OF APPENDIX 4: GENERAL ANALYSIS OF THE EGD

The Analysis presented Appendix 4: General analysis of the provides a comprehensive financial analysis of the EGD projects, focusing on the allocation and utilization of EU funding across various

initiatives. By examining 73 projects that received a cumulative €960.61 million in EU funding, key insights into the distribution patterns, financial dynamics, and strategic priorities of the EGD have been uncovered.

Key figures:

1. **Average Funding Per Project:** The average EU funding per project is €13.16 million, with substantial variability (range: €50,000 to €52.99 million). The mean total project cost is €17.01 million, indicating significant partner contributions.
2. **Funding Distribution:** Engineering and Technology projects receive the highest proportion of funding (42%), followed by Environmental and Earth Sciences (24%), and Social Sciences and Governance (19%).
3. **Economic Categories:** Energy and Resource Management projects receive the largest share of funding (46%), followed by Environmental Sustainability (32%), and Infrastructure and Urban Development (12%).
4. **Consortium Sizes:** The average consortium size is 27 partners, with the number of partners ranging from 1 to 58. Educational and research institutions are involved in 72 out of 73 projects, and private sector entities in 71.
5. **Geographic Distribution:** Spain has the highest number of participating organizations (193), followed by Italy (165) and Belgium (135). Europe accounts for 93% of the organizations, with notable contributions from Africa (3.6%) and Asia (2.7%).
6. **Funding Equity:** Significant disparities exist in funding allocation among organizations, with the mean funding per partner being €489,106.95 and the mode at €0, indicating many organizations receive no funding. The range of funding is from €0 to €36,480,465.00.
7. **Cascading Funding:** The average funding for third parties is €540,057.96, with substantial variability (range: €6,345.65 to €16,349,208.17). A large number of third parties receive lower funding amounts, indicating a skewed distribution.
8. **Partner Participation:** Private sector entities constitute 43% of the total participating organizations, followed by educational and research institutions at 32%, and NPOs at 15%.

The analysis underscores several critical points:

1. **Significant Funding Variability:** The average funding per project is €13.16 million, with substantial variability ranging from €50,000 to nearly €53 million. This wide range reflects the diverse scopes and financial requirements of the projects, highlighting the EU's commitment to supporting both large-scale initiatives and smaller, specialized projects.
2. **Strategic Focus Areas:** Engineering and Technology projects receive the highest proportion of funding, accounting for 42% of the total EU contributions. This category, along with Environmental Sustainability and Energy and Resource Management, underscores the strategic focus on advancing technological innovations, environmental protection, and efficient resource use to achieve the EGD's objectives.
3. **Equity in Funding Distribution:** The analysis reveals disparities in funding allocation among different academic and economic categories, as well as among various regions and organizational types. While private sector entities and educational institutions receive significant funding, there is a need for more equitable distribution to ensure broader participation and impact across all sectors and regions.
4. **Role of Private Sector and Educational Institutions:** Private sector entities and educational and research institutions play pivotal roles in the success of EGD projects, receiving the largest shares of funding. Their involvement is crucial in driving technological advancements, conducting essential research, and implementing sustainable practices.
5. **Global and Regional Participation:** The widespread commitment to the EGD is evident in the diverse regional distribution of project partners. European countries dominate participation, but there is also significant involvement from African and Asian organizations. This global engagement highlights the collaborative nature of the initiatives and the importance of coordinated efforts to address environmental challenges.
6. **Need for Enhanced Monitoring and Evaluation:** Effective monitoring and evaluation frameworks are essential for assessing the success and impact of EGD projects. These mechanisms can ensure transparency, accountability, and continuous improvement, informing future funding decisions and strategies.

The financial analysis of EGD projects demonstrates the EU's strategic priorities in fostering a sustainable, low-carbon economy. By addressing the identified disparities in funding distribution, enhancing support for critical sectors, and promoting global collaboration, the EU can maximize the impact and

effectiveness of the EGD initiatives. This comprehensive approach will ensure progress towards a greener, more resilient future, benefiting both Europe and the global community.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS DERIVED FROM APPENDIX 4: GENERAL ANALYSIS OF THE

1. ENHANCE FUNDING ALLOCATION STRATEGIES

Recommendation: Implement a tiered funding allocation system to balance support between large-scale and smaller, innovative projects.

The analysis indicates substantial variability in project funding, with a high concentration of funds in large-scale projects and significant financial gaps in smaller initiatives. A tiered funding approach can ensure that while substantial projects receive necessary support, smaller, innovative projects also have adequate funding. This strategy can foster a diverse range of solutions and innovations across different sectors, enhancing the overall impact of the EGD.

2. STRENGTHEN SUPPORT FOR ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY PROJECTS

Recommendation: Increase targeted investments in Engineering and Technology, with a focus on renewable energy and environmental engineering.

Engineering and Technology projects receive the highest proportion of funding, reflecting their critical role in advancing EGD objectives. Continued and enhanced investment in these areas, particularly in renewable energy technologies and environmental engineering, can drive significant advancements in sustainability. By focusing on these sectors, the EU can accelerate the development and deployment of cutting-edge technologies essential for achieving carbon neutrality.

3. PROMOTE EQUITABLE RESOURCE DISTRIBUTION

Recommendation: Address funding disparities by ensuring a more equitable distribution of resources among all project categories and regions.

The current funding distribution reveals disparities, with certain regions and project categories receiving more support than others. To maximize the EGD's effectiveness, it is essential to adopt policies that promote equitable funding allocation. This includes providing additional resources to underfunded sectors and regions, ensuring that all areas can contribute to and benefit from the green transition.

4. FOSTER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS

Recommendation: Encourage and facilitate more public-private partnerships to leverage additional funding and expertise.

Private sector entities and educational institutions are significant recipients of EGD funding, highlighting their pivotal role. Strengthening public-private partnerships can leverage additional resources, enhance innovation, and ensure the successful implementation of projects. Policies that incentivize collaboration between public bodies, private companies, and research institutions can further enhance the EGD's impact.

5. SUPPORT SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMES) AND NPOS

Recommendation: Implement specific funding mechanisms to support SMEs and NPOs actively involved in green initiatives.

SMEs and NPOs play crucial roles in addressing specific environmental and social goals. However, they often face challenges in securing adequate funding. Creating dedicated funding streams and support programs for these entities can enhance their contributions and ensure a diverse range of projects under the EGD. This approach can also stimulate grassroots innovations and community-based sustainability initiatives.

6. ENHANCE REGIONAL AND GLOBAL COLLABORATION

Recommendation: Strengthen international cooperation and regional partnerships to address global environmental challenges.

The analysis shows significant contributions from non-European countries, emphasizing the global nature of environmental challenges. Policies that promote international collaboration, knowledge exchange, and joint projects can enhance the EGD's global impact. Strengthening partnerships with

countries in Africa, Asia, and other regions can also help address cross-border environmental issues and promote global sustainability.

7. IMPLEMENT ROBUST MONITORING AND EVALUATION MECHANISMS

Recommendation: Develop and implement comprehensive monitoring and evaluation frameworks to track project progress and outcomes.

Effective monitoring and evaluation are critical for assessing the success and impact of EGD projects. Establishing robust frameworks to track project performance, funding utilization, and environmental outcomes can provide valuable insights and inform future funding decisions. These mechanisms can also ensure transparency and accountability, enhancing stakeholder confidence and support.

APPENDIX 5

TABLES CONTAINING ALL DESCRIPTIVE STATISTIC RESULTS

NPO PRESENCE IN EGD PROJECTS

ANALYSIS OF NPO ORGANIZATION INVOLVEMENT IN EGD PROJECTS

Table 14 Statistical Summary of NPO Involvement in EGD Projects

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	3.88	On average, each project includes approximately 4 NPOs organizations.
Standard Error	0.49	The mean number of NPOs per project is estimated with an error of 0.49.
Median	3	Half of the projects have 3 or fewer NPOs.
Mode	0	15 projects do not have any NPOs in their ranks.
Standard Deviation	4.19	There is considerable variability in the number of NPOs across projects.
Sample Variance	17.55	The variance indicates a high dispersion in the number of NPOs per project.
Kurtosis	3.49	The distribution has a higher peak and heavier tails compared to a normal distribution.
Skewness	1.71	The distribution is positively skewed, indicating a longer tail on the right.
Range	21	The difference between the projects with the most and the least NPOs is 21.
Minimum	0	Some projects do not include any NPOs.
Maximum	21	The highest number of NPOs in a single project is 21.
Sum	283	The total number of NPOs across all projects is 283. This count includes multiple participations by some of the 237 unique NPOs.
Count	73	The analysis is based on 73 EGD projects.
Confidence Level (95%)	0.98	We are 95% confident that the true mean number of NPOs per project falls within ± 0.98 of the sample mean.

NPO PARTICIPATION IN MULTIPLE EGD PROJECTS

Table 15 Statistical Analysis of NPO Participation in EGD Projects

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	1.18	On average, each NPO participates in approximately 1.18 projects.
Standard Error	0.05	The mean number of projects per NPO is estimated with an error of 0.05.
Median	1	Half of the NPOs participate in 1 or fewer projects.
Mode	1	The most common number of projects per NPO is 1. There are 210 NPOs involved in only one project.
Standard Deviation	0.81	There is considerable variability in the number of projects each NPO participates in.
Sample Variance	0.66	The variance indicates the dispersion in the number of projects per NPO.
Kurtosis	133.53	The distribution has a very high peak and heavy tails, indicating many NPOs participate in very few projects, but a few participate in many.
Skewness	10.44	The distribution is highly positively skewed, indicating a long right tail with some NPOs involved in many projects.
Range	11	The difference between the NPO participating in the most projects (12) and the least (1) is 11.
Minimum	1	The smallest number of projects any NPO is involved in is 1.
Maximum	12	The largest number of projects any single NPO is involved in is 12.
Count	237	There are 237 unique NPOs analyzed.

Confidence Level (95.0%)	0.10	We are 95% confident that the mean number of projects per NPO lies within ± 0.10 of the observed mean.
--------------------------	------	--

ANALYSIS OF NET EU FUNDING DISTRIBUTION TO NPOS IN EGD PROJECTS

GENERAL ANALYSIS OF NET EU FUNDING

Table 16 Statistical Analysis of EU Funding Allocated to NPOs in EGD Projects

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	€448,999.22	On average, each NPO receives approximately €448,999.22 in EU funding.
Standard Error	€38,079.13	The mean funding per NPO is estimated with an error of €38,079.13.
Median	€279,125.00	Half of the NPOs receive €279,125.00 or less in EU funding.
Mode	€0	Three organizations do not receive any funding from the EU.
Standard Deviation	€586,220.72	There is significant variability in the amounts of EU funding received by NPOs.
Sample Variance	€3.44E+11	The variance indicates high dispersion in the funding amounts.
Kurtosis	51.54	The distribution has a very high peak and heavy tails, indicating many NPOs receive relatively small amounts, while a few receive very large amounts.
Skewness	5.73	The distribution is highly positively skewed, indicating a long right tail with some NPOs receiving significantly higher funding.
Range	€6,580,153.74	The difference between the highest (€6,580,153.74) and lowest (€0) funding amounts is €6,580,153.74.
Minimum	€0	Some NPOs do not receive any EU funding.
Maximum	€6,580,153.74	The highest amount of EU funding received by a single NPO is €6,580,153.74.
Sum	€106,412,815.10	The total EU funding received by all NPOs is €106,412,815.10.
Count	237	The analysis is based on 237 NPOs.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	€75,018.43	We are 95% confident that the mean EU funding per NPO lies within $\pm$ €75,018.43 of the observed mean.

ANALYSIS OF NET EU FUNDING DISTRIBUTION TO THIRD PARTIES

ANALYSIS OF CASCADING FUNDING TO THIRD PARTIES IN EGD PROJECTS

Table 17 Statistical Analysis of Cascading Funding from NPOs to Third Parties in EGD Projects

Statistical Variable	Value	Interpretation
Mean	€ 277,719.64	On average, each NPO cascades approximately €277,719.64 to third parties.
Standard Error	€ 79,157.22	The mean cascading funds per NPO are estimated with an error of €79,157.22.
Median	€ 192,500.00	Half of the NPOs cascade €192,500.00 or less to third parties.
Mode	€ 30,000.00	The most frequently occurring amount of cascading funds is €30,000.00.
Standard Deviation	€ 326,373.58	There is significant variability in the amount of cascading funds across projects.
Sample Variance	€ 1.0652E+11	The variance indicates high dispersion in cascading funding amounts.
Kurtosis	0.93	The distribution has slightly heavier tails than a normal distribution, indicating some extreme values.

Skewness	1.46	The distribution is positively skewed, indicating a long tail on the right with some projects cascading significantly higher amounts.
Range	€ 1,056,438.00	The difference between the highest (€1,056,438.00) and lowest (€0) cascading funds is €1,056,438.00.
Minimum	€ 0	Some NPOs do not cascade any funds to third parties.
Maximum	€ 1,056,438.00	The highest amount of cascading funds provided to third parties by a single NPO is €1,056,438.00.
Sum	€ 4,721,233.87	The total amount of cascading funds distributed across all NPO partners is €4,721,233.87.
Count	17	The analysis is based on 17 NPO.
Confidence Level (95.0%)	€ 167,805.81	We are 95% confident that the mean cascading funds per NPO lie within $\pm$ €167,805.81 of the observed mean.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	2
Introduction	2
Importance of non-profit organizations (NPOs) in EGD	3
Theoretical framework	3
Role of civil society in environmental governance	3
Theories on collective action and environmental advocacy	3
Stakeholder theory in environmental projects	4
Collaboration Models: NPOs, Governments, and the Private Sector	4
Frameworks for PPPs in Environmental Initiatives	5
Effectiveness of NPOs in Environmental Policy Implementation	5
Funding Patterns and Their Impact on NPOs' Effectiveness	5
Problem Statement	6
Research question	6
Hypothesis	6
Methodology	6
Analytics	6
Project classification	6
Partner classification	6
Overarching category - activity type	6
Economic activities classification.....	7
Survey	7
Final version of the survey.....	7
Analytical study: Non-Profit Organizations	8
Insights gained from the general analysis of the EGD	8
Geographic Distribution Of NPOs	9
NPOs presence in EGD projects	10
Analysis of NPOs involvement in EGD projects	10
Consortium roles and responsibilities in EGD projects	11
NPOs participation in EGD projects	11
Diversity and distribution of NPO types	12
Distribution of net EU funding among the types of NPOs	13
Distribution of NPOs and their funding across economic sectors.....	13
NPOs participation in multiple EGD projects.....	14
Analysis of net EU funding distribution to NPOs in EGD projects	15
General analysis of net EU funding for NPOs	15
Comparison between net EU funding for all organizations and NPOs	16
Analysis of net EU funding distribution to Third Parties.....	17
Concluding remarks of the analytical study	18
Policy recommendations emerging from the analytical study	18
Survey analysis	19
Survey analysis of organizational involvement in EGD projects	19
Geographic distribution of the survey responses	20

Representativeness of survey responses among npos in EGD projects.....	20
Survey results and discussion.....	21
Topical involvement in egd projects.....	21
Organizational impact on EGD projects	22
Contributions of organizations to egd projects	22
Significant achievements of organizational involvement in the EGD	23
Collaboration with stakeholders in EGD projects	23
Challenges encountered in implementing EGD projects	24
Effectiveness of long-term sustainability strategies	24
Measures ensuring sustainability and long-term impact of project outcomes	25
Confidence in sustaining project outcomes over the next 5 years	25
Recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of future EGD projects.....	26
Final comments given in the survey	26
Conclusions and policy recommendations from the survey analysis	27
Strategic recommendations derived from the survey.....	27
Policy recommendations derived from the survey	28
Survey analytical insights limitations.....	28
Concluding remarks: the role of NPOs in the implementation of the EGD.....	28
Key insights:.....	29
Overarching policy recommendations.....	29
1. Equitable Funding and Incentive Structures.....	29
2. Enhanced Collaboration and Networking	29
3. Capacity Building and Technical Support.....	29
4. Inclusive and Diverse Participation	29
5. Regulatory Frameworks and Monitoring.....	29
Hypothesis validation and broader implications	30
Bibliography.....	32
Appendix 1	35
European Green Deal (EGD) projects	35
Appendix 2	43
Consortium roles and responsibilities in EGD projects.....	43
Project classification	43
Academic categories and overarching categories	44
Economic categories and overarching economic categories	45
Limitations of project classification in egd database	46
Partner classification	47
Organization and Activity Type Classification	48
Limitations of manual classification in partner database for EGD projects	52
Appendix 3	54
Survey transcript	54
Appendix 4	59
General analysis of the EGD.....	59
Financial analysis of EGD projects.....	59
Analysis and distribution of partners in EGD projects.....	64
Analysis of organizational involvement and funding in EGD projects	67
Conclusions of Appendix 4: General analysis of the EGD.....	74
Policy recommendations derived from Appendix 4: General analysis of the	76
Appendix 5	78

Tables containing all descriptive statistic results	78
NPO presence in EGD projects.....	78
Analysis of net eu funding distribution to NPOs in EGD projects.....	79